

OPERATIONAL RELEASE OF ACTIVITY PLANS

[Deliverable 4.2]

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ER4STEM - EDUCATIONAL ROBOTICS FOR STEM

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1	Executive Summary	8
1.1	<i>Role, Purpose and Objectives of the Deliverable</i>	8
1.2	<i>Correlation to Other ER4STEM Deliverables.....</i>	8
1.3	<i>Structure of THE DELIVERABLE</i>	9
2	ACTIVITY TEMPLATE Revised VERSION	9
2.1	<i>ACTIVITY PLAN TEMPLATE.....</i>	10
	Focus, Set up and Requirements of the activity	10
	Students and space.....	11
	Social Orchestration	12
	Learning Procedures.....	12
	“How to” in the classroom	12
	Assessment Procedures.....	15
3	ACTIVITY BLOCKS	15
3.1	<i>Introducing</i>	16
	Play the robot.....	16
	What a robot could do for you: Create a mind map	17
3.2	<i>Entering the school.....</i>	18
	Approaching the students	18
3.3	<i>Collaborating</i>	18
	Explaining Collaboration rules.....	18
	Group formulation: Creating random groups.....	19
3.4	<i>Experimenting.....</i>	19
	Providing examples for hypothesis testing.....	19
	Modifying a given example.....	19
	From simple to complex constructions	20
3.5	<i>Teaching for Resilience</i>	20

Taking the risk to share ideas20

The intimidation of what seems impossible21

Handling failure22

3.6 *Reflecting*.....22

 Video advice22

 Promo Video.....25

 Something to remember: video25

 Suggestions for topics of reflective activities26

3.7 *Being Creative*.....26

 A storytelling path26

 Find a mission for your robot28

4 REVISION OF ACTIVITY PLANS 28

4.1 *Second year changes*29

4.2 *Collaboration and Argumentation*.....30

4.3 *Creativity*30

4.4 *Multiple entry points*30

4.5 *Use of activity Blocks*31

5 ACTIVITY PLANS: OVERVIEW AND REFLECTION 31

5.1 *Main objectives*33

 Arts related objectives: Video34

 Arts related objectives: Storytelling34

 Color creation34

5.2 *Multi-disciplinarity and multiple entry points*.....35

 Activity plans developed around powerful ideas35

 Conceptual fields in activity plans36

 Multiple entry points37

5.3 *Student age, setting and connection to the curriculum*.....37

5.4 *Student Collaboration*.....39

 Division of labor – turn taking40

 Groups of special focus and intra-group collaboration40

 Collaboration Rules and reflection on collaboration.....41

5.5 *Argumentation*42

 Topics of discussion:.....42

 Forms of student dialogue:42

5.6 *Learning process and Reflection*.....43

6 Concluding remarks and Considerations for the final version of activity plans..... 45

6.1 *Progress since year 1*45

6.2 *Reflection and alignment with the first year considerations - recommendations*..46

6.3 *Considerations for the final version of activity plans*.....47

7 OPERATIONAL RELEASE OF ACTIVITY PLANS 48

7.1 *New Activity Plans*48

 Engaging with robots in a fun way48

 Visualizing mathematics with the Mathbot.....59

 ER4STEM Workshops – Robot-video (Elementary)77

 ER4STEM Workshops – Robot-video (Advanced).....82

 Identification and avoidance (bypassing) of obstacles.....87

 Robots for sustainability.....92

 SLurtles Introduction & Orientation97

 SLurtles & Geometry 1104

 Exploring the properties of shapes with SLurtles111

 Robotics workshop with Bee bots and Lego Mindstorms121

 Robotics workshop with Lego Mindstorms130

 Robotics workshop with hedgehog139

7.2 *Revised Activity Plans*149

Exploring with Dash, and, programming Dash	149
Educational Robotics and Creativity Workshop	156
An introduction to robotics (exploring planet ektonis)	171
Building a robot and making it smart	178
Robotic Insect	182
Robots in a maze	187
8 Glossary / Abbreviations.....	191
9 BIBLIOGRAPHY=.....	191

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1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

1.1 ROLE, PURPOSE AND OBJECTIVES OF THE DELIVERABLE

This deliverable addresses the second year of work in Work Package 4: “Pedagogical Design and Innovation for Educational Robotics”. In accordance to the Description of Work (DoW), D4.2 reports on the second (operational) version of activity plans developed for ER4STEM to be implemented in the second round of workshops. The operational version of activity plans is based on the first year evaluation, on partner interactions with the ETL research team, who is coordinating the design process, and on the revised version of the activity plan template. The activity plan template was revised according to a) partner comments during the first year of designing activity plans b) Scientix evaluation which was performed during the first year of the project and which highlighted some sections of the activity plan as very academic c) ETLs analysis of the first year activity plans. The revised activity plan template informed the main structure and functionalities of the activity design instrument included in the educational repository (WP5). Furthermore, as we mentioned in D.4.1 the activity plan template was developed by UoA-ETL with the aim to provide tools to the stakeholders of educational robotics to design activity plans that integrate key learning activities like the following:

- transition from individual to collaborative learning perspectives
- an identification of key skills including collaboration, argumentation, taking individual responsibility in groups, creativity and innovation, constructionism, coding/programming robot behaviours, interactions
- a focus on skill development through the sharing of productions
- a focus on problems which the students perceive as real world
- the encouragement for students to come up with robotics ideas to solve real problems
- teacher roles and strategies encouraging the generation of meanings and self-regulation

1.2 CORRELATION TO OTHER ER4STEM DELIVERABLES

WP4 is connected to the following WPs: WP1 (Framework), WP2 (Educational Robotics workshops) WP3 (Educational Robotics Conferences), WP5 (Technology of Educational Robotics – T.5.1 Creation of an educational Repository) and WP6 (Evaluation). Of course, there is two-way interaction between WP4 and the rest of the work packages, although we can observe some strong – one-way influence between the specific deliverables, described next.

Specifically, D4.2 draws from developments in:

- D.1.2, which describes adaptations to the framework and from D.1.1, which offered the roadmap for the second year
- D.6.4, which presents the evaluation results of the first year implementation of workshops

On the other hand, D.4.2 offers input to:

- D.2.2 and D.3.2, which use the activity plans for the implementation of workshops and ECER conferences
- D.5.4, D.5.4, which draw from the activity plan template for the development of the repository

The refinement of the activity plans for the final year of the project will also be based (apart from the work reported in D.4.2) on the analysis of the evaluation data, which will be reported in D.6.4.

1.3 STRUCTURE OF THE DELIVERABLE

This document begins by describing the revised version of the activity template, which was the design instrument for the ER4STEM partners to develop the operational version of activity plans (section 2). Next, we present activity blocks, a new construct, developed for ER4STEM as a response to the first year evaluation results. Activity blocks are smaller concrete constructs, which are developed to support partners to design Educational Robotics activities that aim to the fostering of creativity, collaboration and reflection and that to offer multiple entry points to robotics. In section 4 we present an overview of the changes in the second year activity plans, based on a structured reflection organized by ETL with the ER4STEM Partners.

In section 5 we present a critical overview on the characteristics of the thirteen (18) activity plans developed for the first year of the project. This overview focuses on the main recommendations, based on the first year evaluation: multiple entry points – multidisciplinary, collaboration, argumentation and reflection. Section 6, resumes the progress of WP4 during year two and outlines the main considerations that will direct –along with D.6.5- the work in WP4 during the third year of the project (D.4.3). In the final section of this deliverable (section 7) we include the actual activity plans organized in two subsections: one includes the new and the other includes the revised activity plans designed for implementation in the second year workshops. Both types of activity plans (new and revised) took into account the recommendations from the first year evaluation of activity plans as theoretical constructs (in D.4.1) and as implemented designs (D.6.3)

2 ACTIVITY TEMPLATE REVISED VERSION

The revised version of the activity template keeps its initial orientation as a design instrument for teachers and stakeholders that are interested to design educational activities for Robotics. In our effort to define the activity plan template in D.4.1 we explained that: *“The template provides a generic design instrument that identifies critical elements of teaching and learning with robotics based in theory and practice and is expected to contribute to the description of effective learning and teaching with robotics. Thus, this template is in essence, an abstraction of what we have identified as essential and transferrable elements of learning with robotics. Our aim is to find a balance between a) a level of abstraction that it will make the template adaptable to different settings and b) a level of detail that will demonstrate the influence of a specific pedagogical approach, it will address the particularities of Robotics and it will augment the affordances of the specific robotic kit used in each activity plan.”* The main pedagogical idea underlying the template is that it addresses Robotics as a multidisciplinary constructionist activity (i.e. drawing from the pedagogical theory of constructionism Papert,1980) with an inherent social dimension which includes sharing ideas and learning from others.

There are two main changes in the revised version of the activity plan template. These are drawn from the Scientix evaluation of the activity plans during year 1, the analysis of activity plans

designed in year 1 and the partner comments who designed activity plans during the first year. One change involves removing the aspects of the activity plan template that made it a very academic document in the sense that they involved abstract theories of teaching and learning and they could not be connected to the practices described in the activity plan. The second change was oriented towards supporting teachers and stakeholders to connect the “how to in the classroom” i.e. the practical description of how they are going to organize their workshop or seminar with the stated objectives, teaching methods, student social practices and student constructions. These included an addition at the end of each phase in the how to section of the following structure:

Supported objectives:

Expected student constructions:

Expected forms of student dialogue:

Teaching method:

These additions we expect that would allow for the teachers to reflect on the objectives they stated at the beginning of the activity plan and make sure that these are supported by specific activities in the classroom. The main structure of the activity plan template with the connection of objectives to the activities, has become the basis for the Activity Design Instrument integrated in the ER4STEM framework.

2.1 ACTIVITY PLAN TEMPLATE

Provide the title of the activity as it is mediated to students

AUTHOR:

Name(s) of teacher (s), designer(s), researcher(s)..

Focus, Set up and Requirements of the activity

CURRICULUM

Select NO if the scenario is not aligned with the curriculum of your country and YES if it is. Please mention the relevant subject matter.

NO YES Subject:

CONTENT

Choose categories and give a rating of the level of emphasis on concepts from each of the following domains

<input type="checkbox"/> Science	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Technology	<input type="checkbox"/> Business	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Engineering	<input type="checkbox"/> Arts	<input type="checkbox"/> Mathematics
(0-10)	(0-10)	(0-10)	(0-10)	(0-10)	(0-10)
0	10	0	6	0	0

10

OBJECTIVES

<i>Subject related</i>	e.g. Study the angle and position of all materials (servo motors, circuits, sensors), as well as the construction of the legs in order for the robot - insect to be autonomous and move correctly
<i>Technology use related</i>	e.g. Programming with Arduino, or with in LEGO EV3 programming environment
<i>Social and action related</i>	e.g. Develop collaborative skills, take roles within groups, communicate with other groups to exchange ideas and tips, advice
<i>Argumentation and fostering of maker culture:</i>	e.g. practice making conjectures about how the robot will react to external stimuli based on the program given or formulate and define an authentic problem, make assumptions, test possible solutions, choose the best solution, communicate with other “makers”.

TIME

Duration: e.g. 4 weeks

Schedule: e.g. 2 hours per week

MATERIALS AND ARTIFACTS

<i>Digital artifact</i>	e.g. programming language (Lego EV3 programming environment), visual interface, robot simulation
<i>Robotic artifact</i>	i.e. The technology and the robot form: LEGO WEDO – form: 'an insect', 'a car' ... 'a simple vehicle'
<i>Student's workbook and manual</i>	e.g. Manual with step-by-step instructions for the electronic part and programming part too, activity sheets, Lego electronic manual, evaluation sheet
<i>Teacher's instruction book and manual:</i>	e.g. Teacher's notes with a template of e.g. three incisive stages and five steps for the first two stages.

Students and space**STUDENTS (TARGET AUDIENCE)**

<i>Sex and Age:</i>	e.g. boys & girls, 12-15 years old
<i>Prior knowledge:</i>	e.g. little if any knowledge of Arduino but experts on electronics; basic knowledge of programming concepts (like if-then concepts)
<i>Nationality and cultural background</i>	e.g. 5 pupils are from Albania and 10 from Greece
<i>Social status and social environment</i>	e.g. underprivileged area OR mainstream public school OR elite private school
<i>Special needs and abilities</i>	e.g. ADD, dyslexia, Soc. Em. Behavior Disorders, gifted, other OR Lego programming environment is in English. English is not native language for participants

SPACE INFO

Organizational and cultural context: For example: in school at the technology laboratory; OR during project time in/after school; OR established voluntary club activity; OR after school activity at Computer Lab.

Physical characteristics: indoors/outdoors

Social Orchestration

POPULATION

Students: e.g. 9

Tutors: e.g. 2; **Assistants:**3

GROUPING:

Grouping criteria	e.g. mixed ability, mixed gender OR mixed specialties (for Vocational Schools)
Setting:	e.g. Students in a normal classroom OR around light mobile tables OR looking at the blackboard or in small groups OR students in front of computers with one lego EV3 kit available for each group

INTERACTION DURING THE ACTIVITY (EMPHASIS)

Actions	e.g. Exchange ideas, dialogue, negotiation, debate
Relationships	e.g. Collaborative, competitive
Roles in the group	e.g. pre-defined roles; emergent roles; role exchange in the group
Support by the tutor(s)	e.g. Intervene, monitor, facilitate

Learning Procedures

EXPECTED STUDENT ACTIVITY

Students during the activity are expected to engage in the following actions: construct, observe, communicate, create, present their work in a blog, exchange ideas, etc.

STUDENT LEARNING PROCESSES

<i>Designed Conflicts and misconceptions</i>	Do the activity designers wish to bring students in conflict with mistaken conceptions documented in educational research or their teaching practice?
<i>Learning processes emphasized:</i>	e.g. emphasis on analyzing robot behavior in order to refine and reflect on the code that defines this behavior
<i>Expected relevance of alternative knowledge</i>	e.g. students are expected to investigate the structure of an insect's body (biology) in order to construct their robot

“How to” in the classroom

In this section of the activity plan we describe how we expect the teaching and the learning process to evolve. We might use phases or activities for this description. The phases or activities should

support the objectives stated and make use of the materials, tools and teaching and learning processes mentioned earlier in the activity plan. Next, we provide an example of phase description.

PHASE 1: INTRODUCTION AND EXPERIMENTATION

Duration: 2 hours

Orchestration: group work

Description: Children are engaged in discussion about robotic behaviors and how the creator-programmer can give the desired functionalities and characteristics to a robotic device. Students are introduced to available parts, sensors, motors. They experiment with different values and settings and observe the results on the class floor.

Supported objectives: Develop an understanding of what a virtual world is, how to move and interact within it.

Expected student constructions: Avatar customisation

Expected forms of student dialogue: In class sharing and instruction.

Teaching method: Guided discovery and peer-teaching.

PHASE 2: SEQUENTIAL PROGRAMMING

Duration: 2 hours

Orchestration: group work

Description: Students implement their first programs that have programming blocks in a row. No loops or selection structures are needed. The first program should move the robot on a predefined path on the floor. The robotic vehicle is pre-assembled so students have to focus on programming and debugging their own programs. After a successful first program, they are asked to enhance the program by repeating the movements on the floor and ensuring that the robot returns to the initial position.

Supported objectives:

Expected student constructions

Expected forms of student dialogue:

Teaching method:

PHASE 3: USING LOOPS

Duration: 2 hours

Orchestration: group work

Description: Students try to find a way to simplify their programs by avoiding using the same sequence of blocks many times in the same program. Almost spontaneously they try to use loops with programming blocks. With teacher assistance, they recognize the usage, the conditions and the characteristics of the new programming structure and also the role of the sensors in executing a loop block.

Supported objectives:

Expected student constructions

Expected forms of student dialogue:

Teaching method:

PHASE 4: GIVING “SMART” BEHAVIOR: THE USAGE OF SELECTION/SWITCH BLOCKS

Duration: 2 hours

Orchestration: group work

Description: A robot in order to be “smart” (autonomous) has to avoid any obstacle that could be in its path. Students discuss the new problem and are introduced with a new programming block: “switch block”. Firstly they use the new block once to avoid one obstacle. Very soon they realize that this is not a very “smart” behavior and of course this is not a real-life solution. So, they are encouraged to combine the “switch block” with the “loop block” to have a permanent solution. Students experiment with the position of the two blocks in the program as well as with the various settings that read and control the sensors and motors.

Supported objectives:

Expected student constructions

Expected forms of student dialogue:

Teaching method:

PHASE 5: FEEDBACK AND EVALUATION

Duration: 30 minutes

Orchestration: individual and class work

Description: In addition with the activity sheets that students complete during activity phases, finally they discuss in classroom the difficulties, the different solutions, the limitations that may have found in every step. They also fill in an evaluation questionnaire and teacher gets short informal open interviews from students that want to share their experience.

Supported objectives:

Expected student constructions

Expected forms of student dialogue:

Teaching method:

Assessment Procedures

Suggestions¹ for procedures, methods and tools that can facilitate the achievement of the teaching objectives stated at the beginning of the activity plan. (e.g. post activity tests, reflective videos etc)

RESEARCH QUESTION/ASSESSMENT	ASSESSMENT METHOD OR TOOL
<i>Are popular gender stereotypes about STEM held?</i>	Draw a scientist
<i>Past experience and existing attitudes to STEM subjects and careers</i>	Pre-questionnaire
<i>Past experience and existing attitudes to STEM subjects and careers Includes questions about the activities to help understand learner's experiences of the workshop as a whole, what participants feel they have learned and what their future intentions are</i>	Post-questionnaire
<i>Understand the experience of participants and their reasons for particular actions</i>	Interview with focus group
	Peer assessment
	Group reflection (essays, blog posts, tests, post cards, mini-interviews, create a video, a poster, post a picture)
	Artifacts of learning and student productions (code-robots-textual communication – presentations, etc.)
	Observation notes
	Reflection Sheet

3 ACTIVITY BLOCKS

Activity blocks are a new construct focusing mainly on the practical aspect (i.e. the how to in the classroom) of the activity plan. Activity blocks are adjustable short activities (that can last from 10 minutes to 1 or 2 hours) a combination of which constitutes the “how to” in the classroom section

¹ This part of the activity plan template has been created in collaboration and with reference to the evaluation process of ER4STEM led by the University of Cardiff. Detailed descriptions of the assessment methods and tools are provided in the deliverables of Work Package 6 (D.6.1 and D.6.2)

of the activity plan. They are smaller units in comparison to activity plans and they belong to the third level of the activity plan hierarchy: (i.e Activity template (1st level), Activity Plan (2nd Level) Activity Block (3rd level). An activity plan, and specifically the section “how to” consists of 3- 7 or more activities or activity blocks. In several cases, the activity blocks are accompanied by relevant worksheets that are designed to facilitate the implementation of the activity.

The activity blocks were designed as a result of the first year evaluation, aiming to support the fostering of creativity, collaboration and reflection and to offer multiple entry points for the activity plans. Furthermore, activity blocks were designed to demonstrate the level of detail required so that the “how to” section was sufficiently informative for third party users. This was a common observation coming from the ETL analysis of activity plans, from the Cardiff University first year evaluation and from Scientix Ambassadors.

The Activity blocks created are grouped in seven (7) categories

- Introducing (introductory activities regarding educational robotics)
- Entering the school (involves mainly workshops where there is a need to establish contact in the school e.g. a company introducing a workshop this is not applicable to teachers who plan to implement the workshop in their classroom)
- Experimenting (methods for students to experiment with constructing and programming a robot)
- Collaborating
- Teaching for resilience
- Reflecting
- Being Creative

Two more categories of activity blocks have been proposed for development

- Prototyping
- Asking for help

The main properties of the activity blocks are the following:

- They are adjustable. The descriptions provided can be altered and adjusted to fit various activity plans
- They can be combined with other activity blocks, or they can be integrated
- They have a practical character showing how the theory of introducing creativity, collaborative and reflective learning in educational robotics can be transformed to educational practice. This characteristic makes activity blocks.

Next, we present the activity blocks developed during the first year based on: a) best practices from year one workshops b) reflection on the year one workshops c) review of the literature and d) ETL’s expertise.

3.1 INTRODUCING

Play the robot

The rationale of this activity is to familiarize students with the functioning of the robots and the importance of sensors. This activity can be performed with the whole class. Two students will be

blindfolded (and they could wait outside of the classroom). The rest of the class with the help of the teacher creates a sort of maze using the tables or the chairs to create a path that should be followed by the blindfolded students. Another option is to use masking tape (or sticky tape) to form a maze on the floor of the room. The class suggests instructions that should be followed by the blindfolded person in order to exit the maze. These instructions should be formulated following two rules: all instructions should be given to the blindfolded person before entering the maze - no further instructions should be given during the movement in the maze. The second rule is that the blindfolded students should move in the maze without bumping on its walls. If this is performed as a whole class activity then the teacher notes down the instructions suggested by the class and then reads them to the first blindfolded person. If the movement in the maze is not successful the first time the class discusses corrections in the instructions, the teacher records them and reads the instructions to the second person entering the maze. After the second trial, the teacher discusses with the class the problems in the first or second trial, the characteristics of the instructions in order to be easily followed by the robot. Here the blindfolded students can offer also their views. Another orchestration in the context of formal education could be group work. Students are divided in groups of 4-5 they choose one person to play the robot, the rest members of each group studies the maze and writes down the instructions for their "robot" and then hands them to the teacher. Then the blindfolded students enter the class and each group reads the instructions to their robot. Discussion around the characteristics of the instructions and the problems encountered can be done at group and/or classroom level.

Tags: whole class activity or group activity; formal and non formal settings; student age 6-12

Supported objectives (in the form of keywords): Familiarization with the functioning of robots - importance of precise instructions, need for sensors

Material needed: sticky tape or lightweight tables and chairs, clear space so that a real maze can be created.

Worksheet: N/A

What a robot could do for you: Create a mind map

A short discussion begins in the classroom around what a robot is. A motivating question for this discussion could be to ask students if they have ever seen a robot in real life or in a movie. Collect the answers and then ask the students what are the characteristics of a robot and what it normally does. Another option is to show students a short video about what a robot is and then initiate a discussion about its characteristics and how it works, about the advantages of using robots in everyday life and the disadvantages. Next, tutors or the teacher present students with their task: to design a mind map about what a robot could do for them as children or as grown-ups. They show an example of a mind map and they explain how it works. Next students are provided with A3 or A4 paper and colored pens. They can work individually, or as a group. If students work as a group then the topic for their design should be an open theme addressing aspects of everyday life or of general interest like: How robots could help our society, our families; the environment; the everyday life of the impoverished etc.

Tags: Individual or group activity; brainstorming; connecting robots with everyday life

Objectives (in keywords): Think about the general characteristics of the robots; Connect robotics with aspects of everyday life and with student's lives

Material needed: Paper and colored pencils for drawing mind maps – alternative: mind mapping software.

Worksheet: N/A

3.2 ENTERING THE SCHOOL

Approaching the students

The tutors introduce themselves and explain what they do and why they came in the school. They also explain what they find fascinating about robots and what is the task for the specific day. Next they ask from the students to introduce themselves, one option is to ask them to say their first names and one word that best describes them. The purpose is to become familiar with the students get to know some names and show that they are interested to learn with whom they are going to work with.

Tags: Companies and instructors giving workshops at schools

Objectives (in keywords): These are not learning objectives and involve mainly the instructors and how they plan to approach students and teachers they have never met before.

Material needed: N/A

Worksheet: N/A

3.3 COLLABORATING

Explaining Collaboration rules

Explain to the students that in order to complete the task they need to collaborate with other students. The work of one person, no matter how good it is, is not going to be better than the collective work. Disagreement in a group is not a bad thing, instead it can be very productive if the group knows how to handle it: Handling disagreement involves: a) asking questions that promote understanding (i.e. if a group member makes a suggestion then they others are expected to ask why this suggestion is appropriate for what the group attempts to do) b) asking questions that challenge suggestions (why is this a good idea?) c) Being open to trying new ideas d) respect the other's opinions and do not offend the team members if an idea is not appropriate e) the group takes responsibility for all the choices made and responsibility is not an issue of the individual (the one who made a wrong suggestion) f) trying to identify what each member is good at and use his/her abilities to support group work g) try to engage all group members in the task. Each group can have these rules in a list and ask them while they are working to mark which rules they used most. Another option is to ask groups to identify challenges in collaboration and suggest solutions and rules of working within the group. Then the tutor or the teacher can record the different rules suggested by the groups and create one list with the rules suggested by the students, enrich them with some of the above rules if necessary and distribute them among the groups to mark which rule they need to employ in critical moments.

Tags: collaboration; group work; formal, non-formal settings

Objectives: Learning how to collaborate around robots

Material needed: Paper and pen to write down the rules and mark those used

Worksheet: N/A

Group formulation: Creating random groups

A technique to create random groups could be the following: determine what is the number of the groups you wish to create according to the number of students. If for example you have 21 students and you need to create groups of 3 then you have 7 groups. The next step is to write the number of each group three times in separate pieces of paper (e.g. group 1, group 1, group 1, in three pieces of paper, then group 2, group 2, group 2 in another three pieces of paper and repeat the same process for all seven groups). Then fold the papers so that the side with the writing is hidden and mix them. Ask the students to choose one piece of folded paper. Then those three students who chose the three “group 3” folded papers will be assigned to group 3. You can follow the same process with pieces of colored straws mixed in a bag and asking students to close their eyes while choosing one straw. Students with the same straw color belong to the same team. You need as many colors as the teams you wish to create.

Tags: collaboration, group formulation, formal non formal settings

Objectives: there are no learning objectives This is a supportive activity to facilitate group formulation especially with instructors that enter a new school. This practice might be useful if the teacher does not make suggestions for the group formulation and helps to avoid situations where some students are left out.

Material needed: paper for writing down the groups; or colored straws – bag/ box

Extension: This block will be extended to include processes for creating mixed ability groups and groups with complementary expertise.

3.4 EXPERIMENTING

Providing examples for hypothesis testing

Instead of employing direct instruction (i.e. introducing loops) to introduce a concept or explain an example, constructionist methodology might focus on providing students with an example and ask them to test it and observe the behavior of the robot with the aim of identifying the role of specific programming concepts and structures like loops. This is a teaching and learning process which makes use of the affordances of digital constructionist environments where the observation of the generated behavior (i.e. feedback) and its analysis provide the grounds for the formulation of a hypothesis about how the robot works. Example on how to introduce Loops: Give students a predefined program with a simple loop. The program can include one “move” block that results in the following behavior: the robot moves until it detects an object at 20 cm away. Ask from the students to test the program and find out the role of loop and its parameters

Tags: experimentation, group or individual activity; formal and non-formal settings:

Objectives: Facilitate hypothesis formulation and testing

Modifying a given example

Provide a readymade example and ask from the students to change it so that it demonstrates a slightly different behavior. After the obstacle detection, the robot will perform a U-turn and will move for 4 floor plates. For example: Give students a predefined program with a simple loop. The program can include one “move” block that results in the following behavior: the robot moves until it detects an object at 20 cm away. Ask from the students to modify the program so that, after the obstacle detection, the robot will perform a U-turn and will move for 4 floor plates.

Tags: experimentation, group or individual activity; formal and non-formal settings:

Objectives: analysis of robot behavior; mapping robot behavior to programming concepts; extending the programmed behavior

From simple to complex constructions

(To be expanded) Tasks with gradual complexity can be a good method to introduce students in a complex concept or construct. The idea is to start with simple procedures or physical constructions and in consecutive steps add new elements in the process. The teacher asks students to create a program that results in moving the robot on a predefined path (a rectangular path) on the floor. The robotic vehicle is pre-assembled so students have to focus on programming and debugging their own programs. They are facing two real issues: a) How the real distance on the floor is related to distance parameter on the program b) How a robot can turn 90 degrees as it cannot understand “degrees” by default. After a successful first program, they are asked to enhance the program by repeating the movements on the floor and ensuring that the robot returns to the initial position.

Tags: experimentation, group or individual activity; formal and non-formal settings:

Objectives: “translating” a simple robot behavior to a program; mapping robot behavior to programming concepts; extending the programmed behavior

3.5 TEACHING FOR RESILIENCE

Taking the risk to share ideas

Ask from each student to complete a worksheet (an example is provided below) which will be held secret from the other members of the group. In this worksheet students write down ideas that for some reason they do not wish to share with the group because they think that they are not useful or that the others will make fun of them or because someone else in the group is always the first to make suggestions and to try them out. Reserve five or ten minutes for the resilience worksheet at the end of each session. At the end of the activity ask from each student to count how many ideas they hesitated to share with their group and how many of them were proven completely irrelevant. Ask from those students who have the highest number of not shared ideas to communicate with the classroom at least one of their ideas that they did not communicate and ask from the classroom to discuss around this. The class should also discuss how they could provide space for all members of a group to share their ideas, how to make them feel safe in saying what they think. Then ask from each student to write down in the resilience workbook what he she can do in order for the next time to take the risk of sharing an idea.

WORKSHEET

Write down the ideas that you decided not to share with your group today. Explain why did you decide not to share this idea. Estimate if this idea indeed should not be shared with the others.

Date

Idea

Reason

It was a right decision not to share this idea. YES – NO

Date

Idea

Reason

It was a right decision not to share this idea. YES - NO

Date

Idea

Reason

It was a right decision not to share this idea. YES - NO

Date

Idea

Reason

It was a right decision not to share this idea. YES - NO

The intimidation of what seems impossible

This can also be used as an introductory activity.

Students quite often do not engage with new things because they feel that they are beyond their reach and there is no way to make it. This can be used as an introductory activity and help students develop a methodology in approaching what seems impossible to achieve. A suggestion for such an activity could be to show students with a video of the robot they are going to make. Ask your students if they think they can make this robot and if not why. Next explain the divide and conquer methodology: i.e. break down the problem into smaller parts (i.e. what do they need to have or to do in order to construct such a robot) and start resolving those they are more confident with.

Handling failure

The aim for this activity is to teach students that failure is not something abnormal, nor something to be blamed for, nor something to take it personally by feeling incompetent or not clever enough. Failure is part of everyday life efforts, especially when people engage with something new and difficult. If failure it is not associated with feelings of incompetence can be very productive. An analysis of the failure and identification of what went wrong provides you with new ideas on how to reach your goal. Ask from your students to complete the relevant worksheet at least two or three times during the whole workshop activity. At the end of the activity ask each group to reflect on their failures, their feelings, their attitude towards failure and help them to understand that failure is a very useful part of the learning process and of living.

WORKSHEET: HANDLING FAILURE

"Ever tried. Ever failed. No matter. Try again. Fail again. Fail better." S. Beckett

GROUP NAME

Date

- Short description of what went wrong:
- What was the reason for the failure?
- What do you feel about this failure? (Record the feelings of all group members)
- Is this the time to give up? Why?
- Can you do something to repair the problem? What is it?
- Did you learn something useful from this failure? What was it?
- Was this failure helpful somehow to reach your final goal?

3.6 REFLECTING

Video advice

Ask the group of students to create a short video with what they would consider best advice for other students who would like to construct something similar with their robot. Their video should focus on a) one tip for the construction of the robot b) one tip for the programming (if the group engages with it) and c) one tip on how it is best collaborate. Students, before embarking on the video, should create a script about the main scenes of the video (introduction, construction scene, programming scene, collaboration scene, ending scene). An indicative form for the creation of such a script is provided here. The aim of this activity is for the students to reflect on the most important parts of their activity. Normally we expect here students to identify issues that were tricky and explain them so that someone else can find them useful. This is an assessment method of student learning, engaging students with challenging concepts and elaborate on them using different modalities (picture, short texts, audio) The video could be uploaded to a Youtube channel and be offered to younger students or students from other classes that are engaged with the same activity. Furthermore, each video could be evaluated (likes - and comments) by students of the same class or other collaborating classrooms. Before embarking on evaluation, ask your students to focus on the following criteria: how useful is the video (here the focus is on the themes picked: did the group

actually chose an interesting topic to address as advice?); quality of the music, the graphics and the texts used; other characteristics that make the video to capture the attention of the viewer (e.g. humor). Ask your students to provide comments along with their evaluation.

Tags: Teamwork; reflection; digital media literacy; Target age: 10-18

Objectives: Creative reflection on student work; Elaborating on ideas and difficult concepts using multiple modalities (audio, short text, pictures).

Material: Worksheet, video creation software

Resources: <https://animoto.com/blog/education/creative-ways-engage-students-video/>

<https://www.edutopia.org/blog/using-video-in-classroom-ron-peck>

Students can also use the MS PowerPoint as a video creation software and then save their presentation as a video

WORKSHEET “VIDEO ADVISE- SCENARIO”

GROUP NAME	
Video introduction SCENE	Define what will appear in the first scene of the video: a title with the motto of the team, the highlight of the advice – determine if there will be a picture in the first scene and what this picture will depict (provide a short description for all the above here).
Construction Scene	Describe your advice about the construction Determine if this advice will be in audio or written form or in both Determine what kind of pictures you need to demonstrate this advice or if you need a short video of someone of you demonstrating the construction

Programming Scene	<p>Describe your advice about the programming of your robot</p> <p>Determine if this advice will be in audio or written form or in both</p> <p>Determine what kind of pictures you need to demonstrate this advice or if you need a short video of someone of you demonstrating this advice about programming</p>
Collaboration Scene	<p>What is the best way to collaborate in order to be successful in creating this robot? What are the problems that might be encountered?</p> <p>Describe the advice</p> <p>Determine its form (written, audio, both)</p> <p>Determine and describe the pictures needed to highlight and best demonstrate this advice about collaboration</p>
ENDING SCENE	<p>Determine how the video will end (provide short description here)</p> <p>Group participants, use of pictures, end title</p>
Find music for your video	<p>Use own compositions (if they exist) and or use creative commons music (e.g.) https://creativecommons.org/about/program-areas/arts-culture/arts-</p>

	culture-resources/legalmusicforvideos/ What kind of music do you need for your video (short description)?
Determine ethical issues (if any)	E.g. not showing the faces of the students

Promo Video

Each group should create a promo-video for their robot or for their work as a team around their robot. Students should work on the script of their video focusing on what makes their robot special, or showing what their robot can do in a creative way i.e. instead of saying our robot can do this or that they could create an imaginative story around their robot, which demonstrates its functionalities. I.e. the story of a robot adopted by a blind person and training it to become his/her personal assistant. Another option for theme of the promo video is to focus on the collaboration of the specific students as a group. In this case the video should focus on how the group worked together, how they resolved their disagreements, the disagreements that finally promoted their work, and what is their special strength as a group. As in the advice video, an evaluation of the videos is important part of the process. Each video could be evaluated (likes - and comments) by students of the same class or other collaborating classrooms. Before embarking on evaluation ask your students to focus on the following criteria: how innovative and creative is the video; can the video draw other people's attention; why? quality of the music, the graphics and the texts used; other characteristics that make the video to capture the attention of the viewer (e.g. humor). Ask your students to provide comments along with their evaluation.

Tags: Teamwork; reflection; creative thinking; digital media literacy

Objectives: Students reflect on the special characteristics of the robot they constructed; Use creative thinking to best promote their video (i.e. integrate it in a story, a song)

Something to remember: video

This video aims at depicting the story of the construction of the group. The focus of this video can be on the collaboration of the specific students as a group. In this case the video should focus on how the group worked together, how they resolved their disagreements, what were the disagreements that finally promoted their work, and what is their special strength as a group. Before constructing the video students should first create the script following a worksheet and then embark on creating the video. As in the advice video, an evaluation of the videos is important part of the process. Each video could be evaluated (likes - and comments) by students of the same class

or other collaborating classrooms. Before embarking on evaluation ask your students to focus on the following criteria: how innovative is the video; does it tell an interesting story about the collaboration around constructing a robot; did they address only good moments of the work as a group or did they also discussed difficulties; quality of the music, the graphics and the texts used; other characteristics that make the video to capture the attention of the viewer (e.g. humor). Ask your students to provide comments along with their evaluation.

Tags: Teamwork; reflection; creative thinking; digital media literacy

Objectives: Creative reflection on student collaboration; Elaborating on meta-cognitive thinking using multiple modalities (audio, short text, pictures); Development of critical and creative thinking.

Suggestions for topics of reflective activities

- Engineer's journal
- Create - draw a postcard
- Create a poster
- Post a photo and comment on other's photo's

3.7 BEING CREATIVE

A storytelling path

Here the idea for the students is to become creative so as to build something interesting around the path their robot moves. Each group decides identifies in the path specific spots (e.g. one path might consist of 4 or five such spots which might be turning points or stops. For each spot the group can record a sound or they can narrate a short story. Then in their program they integrate a "wait command" so that the robot will wait at the specific point for as long as the sound or the narration will be heard (e.g. 3-4 min max). Each group works around the story after they finish programming their robot. So, they might search on the Internet for sounds or they might record themselves telling the story. For this there might be a need for each tutor to accompany the students in a different room so as to record their story without the extra noise of the room. There should be one sound file per stop. As soon as recordings have finished then each group stands next to their robot and they press the respective sound file so that the sound or the narration is heard. They do this until the end of the path. At the end of this activity, it is expected that students have created different stories/sounds around the path followed by their robot. This process can be done in an more "automatic way" if tutors use further equipment like Makey Makey and Scratch. The next "subblocks" present more structured examples of this activity block.

Tags: robots moving on a path or labyrinth; group work; creativity; storytelling

Objectives: Using their imagination to create a story; supporting creative thinking

Material: sound recording software; sound playing software, tablets or mobile phones; makey-makey, scratch

STRUCTURED SOUND PATH

This is a specification of the storytelling block. In this case, the tutors place "smilies" depicting different emotions; at each point of the path they place a smiley with a different emotion (e.g. sad, surprised, troubled, happy, in agony, frightened). Students have to come up with sounds they believe that can cause the specific emotion.

STRUCTURED STORY PATH I

This is a specification of the storytelling block. In this case the tutors place "smilies" depicting different emotions; at each point of the path they place a smiley with a different emotion (e.g. sad, surprised, troubled, happy, in agony, frightened). Students have to come up with incidents that can have as a result the specific emotion. Another option here is for the tutors to use a set of trigger words, which will be written in cards and will be placed in specific spots of the path like "free Mrs. Robot" (from free willy for example), "oh oh trouble!", "a friend? or not?", "time for confrontation or time to run?", "the end"

STRUCTURED STORY PATH II

In this example each group writes five phrases which are not expected to be connected. These phrases should respond to the following questions: 1) Where am I, Who am I and What I can do? (e.g. the robot) 2.) Here is a (my) problem? 3) Who is this behind me? 4) What are we going to do now? 5) Who is going to help us? These phases can be printed in a card (see the STORY CARDS worksheet below) and students write their responses there. Next, they give this card to the group next to them or to the group sitting opposite them. Then the group who took the filled card should use these phrases to create episodes of one story (using the responses in any order they want). This can become really funny)

WORKSHEET – STORY CARDS

Where I am, who am I, what can I do?	
Hmm here is a problem	
Who is this behind me?	
What are we going to do now?	

Who is going to help us?	

Find a mission for your robot

Groups discuss about a mission that their robot could accomplish. In this discussion they specify a) a mission that their robot would like to accomplish b) what their robot can do now (what are the characteristics) - c) which characteristics - functionalities should be there in order for their robot to be able to accomplish the mission they defined. For this purpose, students can use the Mission CARD where they answer these questions in the form of bullets and then each group presents their work to the classroom

Worksheet Mission Cards

What is the mission I want my robot to accomplish?

.....

What my robot can do now?

.....

.....

What else my robot should be able to do, to accomplish the mission?

.....

.....

.....

.....

4 REVISION OF ACTIVITY PLANS

In this section, we describe how the first year activity plans were revised - even if partners decided to design a completely different activity plan – based mainly on the first year evaluation of the activity plans and of their implementation in the workshops. To this end we asked from the

ER4STEM participants who draw activity plans to implement a structured reflection on the new activity plans they designed responding to a set of questions that focused mainly on addressing aspects highlighted from the first year evaluation such as supporting collaboration, creativity, multiple entry points. There was also a reference to the use of the activity blocks and two questions asking from the participants to explain what changed in their designs during the second year and which of these changes they consider as the most important. Next, we present the questions consisting the structure for reflection on the second year activity plans:

- Provide the title of your activity plan
- How is the second year activity plan different from the activity plan you designed in the first year? (Refer here to topic, level of detail, style of description, focus of activity plan, etc.)
- Highlight the most important change you made
- How do you support collaboration - argumentation in the second year activity plan?
- How do you support creativity in the second year activity plan?
- How do you support multiple entry points for the second year activity plans?
- Did you use/adapt or got inspired by the activity blocks? Which ones did you find useful? What changes should be made in the activity blocks?

Analysis of the partner responses shows that in the second year there was a progress in addressing the aspects highlighted during the evaluation of the first year i.e. collaboration, creativity and introduction of multiple entry points for the robotic activities. Furthermore, it appears that in most cases activity blocks were considered useful the partners. In the following sections, we present partner responses organized thematically.

4.1 SECOND YEAR CHANGES

Partners' reflection on the second version of activity plans showed that changes in the second year happened in different levels.

- Changes in the process of generating activity plans especially from a pedagogical perspective: Two of the partners who have mainly a commercial profile (ESI CEE and AcrossLimits) worked on their activity plans in close collaboration with the ETL research group. Specifically, ESICEE provided a working version activity plans for comments and discussion with ETL. Similarly, AcrossLimits discussed with ETL and Cardiff University aspects of collaboration and creativity. Activity blocks on the story paths were created after this discussion. Furthermore, discussion with these two partners helped to distinguish between the two types of creative tasks during engagement with educational Robotics mentioned next (i.e. creativity in the robotic construction and the other is creativity about the robot).
- Changes in the level of detail in describing the activity plans and especially the “how to section”. This change addresses one of the comments on first year activity plans made by Scientix Ambassadors, who stressed that the descriptions were not sufficient enough to indicate how the plan was going to be implemented in the classroom. This was also one of the reasons we developed the activity plans i.e. to support activity plan designers in describing the practical part of their scenario (i.e. the implementation) by providing examples they could use and demonstrating by example what was the level of detail expected for the description of the “how to” activities.

- Additions or changes in activities targeting mainly collaboration, creativity and reflection (see following sections). Modifications in activities involved mainly changes from following specific instructions to open ended tasks allowing for multiple strategies and solutions to emerge. The new activities were mainly inspired by the activity blocks.

4.2 COLLABORATION AND ARGUMENTATION

Two major changes were observed in the second year activity plans: One involved the introduction of «Edmodo» an a social networking educational tool to support argumentation between the groups of students. ETL – UoA teachers used Edmodo in their workshops (four out of the seven teachers). One teacher mentioned that the scenario envisaged the use of Edmodo but students did not have the time to use it and they did not expressed any interest to this. This comment should be seen in the light of the scenario in which Edmodo was integrated. Specifically, this teacher implemented the construction and programming of a Robotic Insect from scratch. The task was very demanding not only in terms of programming but also in terms of construction. Thus although the scenario envisaged the use of Edmodo, the scenario did not envisage enough time for its use or the use of Edmodo was not seamlessly integrated in the activity. Interestingly, the specific teacher suggested Edmodo when changes for the second year were discussed between the teachers and the ETL group. Furthermore, the teacher mentioned that she has used Edmodo extensively with her students mainly for the exchange of material (not as a discussion tool).

The other change involved the use of relevant activity blocks. One teacher stated that he used the activity block for group formulation and the activity block that involved the collaboration rules.

Other changes involved emphasis on prompting students to discuss, to reflect, to exchange opinions and ideas, to respect different opinions and diversity. All partners mentioned that their students worked in groups and there was encouragement for discussion and collaboration.

4.3 CREATIVITY

When discussing creativity in educational robotics we can identify two main foci: one is creativity in creating the robot and the other is creativity about the robot. In the first case, creativity is connected with open-ended problems that allow for multiple solutions to occur. This can involve robotic constructions and/or programmed behaviour. This is an interesting observation given that in many cases in robotic classrooms (and in many of the first year activity plans) student constructions followed specific guidelines. One of the teachers structured creative solutions by allowing the students to tinker creatively with their robotic constructions allowing certain degrees of freedom at the beginning of the task. This design choice resulted in the occurrence of different robots and required different programming solutions as the tasks progressed.

The second category of creativity activities, are those that focus around the robot and involve mainly what a robot can do. This was an approach followed during the first year by ESI CEE with the mind maps that focused on the applications of robots and was further extended with the creativity-focused activity blocks that involved mainly activities that contextualized and enriched the behaviour of a robot (e.g. story paths). ESICEE in the second year used story-paths as inspiration for enhancing the creative dimension of their activity plans.

4.4 MULTIPLE ENTRY POINTS

The concept of multiple entry points appears to be a challenging aspect for most of the partners. Thus, several of the partners did not provide an answer for this question. However, some of the teacher designers provide an interesting view on this aspect. Specifically, they recognize that mixed ability groups might support multiple entry points in the sense that students with low interest or with no experience with robotics can be supported by other students who are more enthusiastic and more familiar with the technology. Introducing authentic tasks or tasks related to real life is also considered as offering a new entry point for students to robotics activities. Another view involves identifying and making explicit to the students the different tasks involved in educational robotics: i.e. hands on activity (construction), programming, making calculations, giving names to the robot (upon which students build a sense of ownership), introducing argumentation activities where students present their work to the rest of the groups of their class. The rationale behind this concept is that students with different interests or inclinations can find an entry point to be involved with the robotics activity (e.g. make the calculations, perform the tests, take the photographs and write a short presentation of the robot to be uploaded in the online environment (e.g. Edmodo) for the rest of the class to see, etc.). This view of multiple entry points can be enhanced and extended more by including activities involving creativity, prototyping, etc.

4.5 USE OF ACTIVITY BLOCKS

Activity blocks were found useful by most of the partners. However, one of the teachers considered them useful but she believed that the activity blocks were designed to support activity plans that address elementary school activities. This teacher taught 14-15 year olds and she implemented a very demanding task from the point of view of construction and programming that of a robotic insect (see section with the activity plans). The use of activity blocks by partners varied. Thus some of them used them as inspiration for structuring and describing their activities in the “how to” section of the activity plan (two UoA) teachers. Other partners integrated one or more activity blocks in their plan and extended it to support reflection, resilience and creativity (i.e. they mentioned that they used the activity blocks: story paths, sharing ideas – resilience activity blocks, group formulation). Others found useful the introductory activity “play the robot”. One of the teachers claimed that made use of seven activity blocks (i.e. a) Play the robot, b) What a robot could do for you, c) Explaining Collaboration rules, d) Creating random groups, e) Modifying a given example, f) Tasks with gradual complexity, g) Handling failure). Last but not least, ESI CEE pinpointed that activity blocks facilitated their entrance in the school as they seemed to have a strong impact on the teachers. Overall, activity blocks appeared useful for the partners engaged in the process of designing their activity plan, and that partners found different uses for the blocks according to their expertise, characteristics of the students participating the workshop, time to revise and/or redesign the activity plan, etc.

5 ACTIVITY PLANS: OVERVIEW AND REFLECTION

In this section of the deliverable, we present an overview of the activity plans designed for the second year workshops of ER4STEM and we attempt a reflective presentation. During the second year, the project produced 18 activity plans. Twelve (12) of these activity plans are new productions and the rest (6 activity plans) are revisions of year one activity plans. Revisions took into consideration: a) partner-teacher own reflection on the first year implementation; b) first year evaluation recommendations; c) discussions with the ETL – team on the activity plan drafts; d) the activity blocks.

No	Partner	Activity Plan	Technology	Domain - emphasis
NEW ACTIVITY PLANS				
1	AL	Engaging with robots in a fun way	Dash and Dot, Scratch	Technology, Mathematics
2	ESI CEE	Visualizing mathematics with the Mathbot	Finch, Scratch	Technology, Mathematics
3	TU-Wien	ER4STEM Workshops – Robot-video (Elementary)	Thymio, Aseba VPL	Technology, Business, Engineering, Arts
4	TU-Wien	ER4STEM Workshops – Robot-video (Advanced)	Thymio, Aseba Blockly and Textual	Technology, Business, Engineering, Arts
5	UoA	Identification and avoidance (bypassing) of obstacles	LEGO NXT, Lego programming language	Technology, Engineering, Mathematics
6	UoA	Robots for sustainability	LEGO EV3	Science, Technology, Engineering
7	CU	SLurtles Introduction & Orientation	Slurtles, Scratch for Open Sim	Technology, Mathematics
8	CU	SLurtles & Geometry 1	Slurtles, Scratch for Open Sim, OneNote Reflection tool	Technology, Mathematics
9	CU	Exploring the properties of shapes with SLurtles	Slurtles, Virtual Worlds, Scratch for Open Sim	Technology, Mathematics
10	PRIA	Robotics workshop with Bee bots and Lego Mindstorms	BeeBots, LEGO Mindstorms, LEGO EV3	Technology, Engineering, Arts
11	PRIA	Robotics workshop with Lego Mindstorms	LEGO Mindstorms, LEGO EV3	Science, Technology, Engineering
12	PRIA	Robotics workshop with hedgehog	Hedgehog, Python	Science, Technology, Engineering
REVISED ACTIVITY PLANS				
13	AL	Exploring with Dash, and, programming Dash	Dash, Scratch	Science, Technology, Mathematics
14	ESI-CEE	Educational Robotics and Creativity Workshop	Arduino, Scratch	Science, Technology, Engineering
15	UoA	An introduction to robotics (exploring planet ektonis)	LEGO WeDo 2.0, Scratch	Science, Technology, Engineering
16	UoA	Building a robot and making it smart	LEGO Mindstorms NXT, LEGO programming environment	Science, Technology, Engineering, Mathematics
17	UoA	Robotic Insect	Arduino, Arduino IDE	Technology, Engineering
18	UoA	Robots in a maze	LEGO EV3 , LEGO programming environment	Technology, Engineering

Table 1: List of the operational release of activity plans, their technologies and the domains they cover per partner

With respect to the new activity plans there are three categories of partner contributions: New partner entries in designing activity plans. Here we have two such cases of activity plans, which are created for the first time in year two. Specifically, Cardiff University designed three activity plans for

ER4STEM this year for the first time. The other case comes from UoA and involves the activity plan “Identification and avoidance (bypassing) of obstacles”. This activity plan is created by a new teacher who joined the ETL –team of teachers in year two. He is a mathematics teacher, PhD student, member of the ETL research group and he is implementing the workshop for ER4STEM for the first time.

The second category of new activity plans involves partners who revised their initial activity plan and produced a new more advanced activity plan. In this category fall Across Limits and ESI-CEE. In these cases, the revised activity plan was designed to support student introduction to robotics. Their second production (new activity plan) involves more advanced and more focused activity with robotics. In the case of ESI CEE the new activity plan (“Visualizing mathematics with the Mathbot”) addresses robotics as a domain for implementation of mathematics and it is designed for older students (Grade 4) in comparison to the introductory activity plan, which is designed for 3rd grade students. Furthermore, the educational robotics activities in this activity plan are designed in alignment with the national educational curriculum in mathematics for the fourth grade of general education schools in Bulgaria. AcrossLimits has produced a new activity plan “Engaging with robots in a fun way” which introduces programming in the context of two scenarios: the robot being a security guard or a lottery drawer. The new scenario addresses secondary school students whereas the revised scenario is designed for 10 year olds (Primary School).

The third category of new activity plans involves cases where partners chose to produce a new activity plan completely different from the activity plan produced in year 1. One such case comes from UoA “Robots for sustainability”. The designer explains that the inspiration for the topic of the activity plan comes from the 2017 Olympiad for robotics and the context in which this activity plan is implemented is not the school but an “after school, at STEM Robotics Academy (non-profit organization)”. The theme of this new activity plan is more aligned with the multiple entry-points requirement of the ER4STEM project. The other case comes from the TU-Wien team who produced two new activity plans which are different from those produced in the first year. These activity plans are structured around the same idea but they are designed so that they support introductory and more advanced engagement with robotics. These two new activity plans integrate well aspects of Arts, Engineering and Business (as the video is designed to promote the robot as a business idea) and offers multiple entry points to the activity. Furthermore, the idea to connect the robotic construction with business (through a promo video) can be considered an influence of the “Crazy robots” activity plan created during the first year by TU-Wien.

5.1 MAIN OBJECTIVES

In the second year of the project the main objectives pursued with the activities primarily focused on the domain of Technology and Engineering. Secondary subjects that were involved in the robotic constructions were Mathematics, Science, and Business. In this respect there is no differentiation from the first year.

An important differentiation however, is observed in the integration of Arts in the robotics activities, which is present in the workshops designed by the two Austrian Partners: TU-Wien and PRIA. In the first year we observed that Arts was integrated only in a peripheral way. Specifically, one of the activities designed by UoA and implemented in Ionidios involved the construction of a robot painter. However, our observation was that the students did not actually focus on aspects of painting as the robot mainly drew colored geometrical shapes (like lines, squares etc.) During the second year we identified three activities which integrate Arts more centrally in the construction.

Arts related objectives: Video

Specifically, the TU-Wien activities include as a central part of their focus the creation of a video that demonstrates the main functionalities of the robot created by two different groups. This is integration of arts about the construction however, the idea for each video to include robots created by two different groups involves knowledge about robot functionalities, which have to be highlighted and presented in the video.

Arts related objectives: Storytelling

The first activity plan designed by PRIA for the introductory workshop includes storytelling as a context for students to integrate the programming skills they acquired during the previous phases of the workshop. The idea is to ask students to think of a story where their robot will be an actor and they are asked to draw the scene where their story takes place. To facilitate this process, the tutors show to the students examples of possible stories in the form of pictures. This integration of Arts is considered innovative and interesting for the following reasons:

- a) Storytelling is transformed so that it meets the specifics of robot functionalities. This means that the emphasis is not on verbal narration but instead in creating a scene where the robot can have an active role and interact with. In this sense students need to create an interactive story taking into account the functionalities of their robot (what their robot can do: i.e. drive around, push objects, make a sound?). This adaptation of storytelling can be considered as a new genre where technological characteristics (i.e. functionalities) are integrated in a story which is artistically expressed in the form of a scenery (as the scene is the locus of the story where the robot can have an active role).
- b) Storytelling provides the context where robot functionalities and programming knowledge become meaningful and are connected together in a story, which makes sense for the students.
- c) Storytelling the way it is described in this scenario requires from the students to think in a more functional and abstract way about the programs they create and the behavior of their robot. This means that students need to take a different view point and think about robots and programming in terms of a) what the robot can do – in terms of sensors and functionalities and b) how programming can transform these functionalities into behaviors. These two pieces of knowledge have to be then combined so as to be integrated in the flow of a story and to influence the design of the landscape which represents the story and allows for their robot to demonstrate its programmed behavior.

Color creation

Color creation was part of the tasks designed by ESI CEE in the new activity plan “Visualizing Mathematics with Mathbot”. ESI CEE did not state that Arts is parts of its objectives however, from our communication with Cardiff University which is responsible for the Evaluation, occurred a piece of information that involved student comments on one of the tasks consisting the activity plan and its relationship to Arts. Specifically, the task involved programming the Finch robot to emit different colors from its nose according to the turn it was taking. One of the suggested colors was purple which in order to be produced required students to mix other colors. In the mid-point reflections, introduced by the CU so as to capture student views on their learning in the workshop, one of the groups mentioned color mixing in order to produce purple, as one of their greatest achievements.

Furthermore, what is equally interesting is that students acknowledged the multidisciplinary nature of robotics by saying that *“Robots can teach you many things about art too – how to combine colors for instance!”* We mention this example here to show that the multidisciplinary nature of robotics can reveal connections with different domains of knowledge (other than engineering and programming), although these connections might not be highlighted during the design of the activity. However, for these connections to emerge, it is important that the activity focuses on the constructionist nature of robotics, which means that the idea underlying the activity plan should involve a construction with personal interest for the students instead of solely focusing on learning specific skills and acquiring specific pieces of knowledge.

ETL acknowledging the dynamic nature of constructionist activities, will develop in the third year of the project, a template that captures the practice of implementing the activity plan. This template will aim, among other things, to capture unexpected aspects of the initial design with the purpose to enrich and inform back the design of the initial activity plan.

5.2 MULTI-DISCIPLINARITY AND MULTIPLE ENTRY POINTS

In D.4.1 we have acknowledged multidisciplinary as one of the special characteristics of Robotics activities (Yiannoutsou, Nikitopoulou, Kynigos, Gueorguiev, & Fernandez, 2016). Our analysis of the first year activity plans showed that with the exception of “Mathematics” and physics laws, which were seamlessly integrated, mainly in the way robot vehicles function, other domains were superficially covered. To further support the design of activity plans towards multidisciplinary we introduced in D.4.1 two theoretical constructs that of powerful ideas and conceptual fields.

We include here the main definition of these two concepts and we explain next how these concepts were used in the design of some of the activity plans designed in the second year of the project.

Activity plans developed around powerful ideas

Powerful ideas are a central theoretical construct of constructionism and involve use of knowledge in new ways where learners can establish personal epistemological connections with various domains of knowledge (Papert 2000). Furthermore, Bers (2008) analyzing powerful ideas, describes them as domains of knowledge where many diverse topics or subjects co-exist and become explicit. An illustrative example is the idea of animals where the subject of biology and geography (and many others co-exist). Furthermore, animals can fall within children’s personal interest, which is also one of the characteristics of powerful ideas (ibid).

The most prominent example of powerful ideas is found in the “tell a story” activity of the “Robotics workshops with Bee bots and Lego Mindstorms” activity plan. This is an introductory activity for familiarization with the robots designed mainly for young children. Storytelling is an activity with personal interest for the students and offers a context where the concept of the story is captured in the drawing of the main scene where the robot will move. Furthermore, the story is on the one hand influenced by the restrictions and the functionalities of the robot and on the other hand the behavior of the robot is determined by the elements of the story. In our analysis we can see how the story elements and the robot functionalities co-exist and influence each other integrally.

Another good example of activity plan developed around the concept of powerful ideas is the “Robots for sustainability”. In this activity plan students are expected to construct robots that offer solutions to specific tasks that relate to the reduction of carbon emission. The activity plan does not

offer sufficient details on the different tasks – problems. However, it appears that an analysis of the problem –e.g. its causes, its characteristics- is important in devising a solution. Furthermore, this solution, should also take into account the functionalities and the possible behavior of the robot (i.e. what the robot can do under what conditions, what is the behavior that could help in solving the problem, what are the restrictions, etc.).

Elements of powerful ideas are also found in a rather loose way in the Robotic Insect. However, as we pointed out in D.4.1 there is connection between robotics and biology but the knowledge of biology is only peripheral here. The reason is that students do not need to do something more than recall the general knowledge about how insects look like. Furthermore, if the structure of the body of a real insect is not correctly represented this has little impact in the final result as the main point of the task is to construct a robot which will be able to walk with more than two modular feet. However there is potential in the idea to be further developed towards multidisciplinary as the legs of the robotic insect follow a metachronal pattern, which resembles insect locomotion and follows its mechanical principles which is a subject of inherent to biology and physics.

Conceptual fields in activity plans

Conceptual fields are a construct used by Vergnaud (2009) to describe understanding of mathematics. The main argument of Vergnaud is that mathematical concepts do not exist in isolation instead they exist in conceptual fields which include the situations and the examples in which a concept manifests its properties plus the symbolic representations by which this concept is mediated. Healy and Kynigos (2010) extended the idea of conceptual fields to analyze exploratory learning environments for the learning of mathematics and we attempted to transfer this concept in the domain of robotics activities.

One example of activity plans where the concept of conceptual field is demonstrated is the “Visualizing Mathematics with Mathbot” which is developed by ESI CEE. One of the tasks of the specific activity plans involves the drawing of a circle with the Finch robot, which consists of two wheels (see Fig 1.)

Fig. 1 Finch Robot drawing

In order for the students to make the robot draw a circle on paper they need to consider a) the properties of the circle (as a geometrical shape) and b) the way they can use the robot’s functionalities, i.e. tinkering with the speed of each of the two wheels in order for the robot to move so as to draw a circle. Thus, robotics offers a new situation/ context where circle is explored and connected with the concepts of motion and speed.

A similar approach of conceptual fields is encountered with the 3d Geometrical shapes investigated with SLurtles (Activity plans: “SLurtles and Geometry 1”; “Exploring the properties of Shapes with SLurtles”). In these activities the geometrical shapes are explored through the drawings of a turtle

avatar in a virtual world. In this context students investigate properties of the geometrical shapes in relation to the specifics of the avatar movement in the virtual world.

Elements of the conceptual field are also found in the integration of business in the activity plans developed by TU-Wien (ER4STEM workshops - Robot video) where the students are challenged to manage limited resources (time availability of the camera) in order to produce their video. We consider this as a new context where students explore aspects related to business in the context of a robotic construction. Thus, to produce to video and manage the limited resources students should take into account the specifics of the robotic construction (i.e. experimenting with the robot, deciding which aspects to highlight given that the video should not exceed the 1 min, etc.).

Multiple entry points

We consider that multiple entry points to educational robotics activities can be found in activity plans with a multidisciplinary dimension. An important prerequisite for an activity to offer multiple entry points is to have integrated well in its main idea concepts from other domains. Furthermore, the activity plans constructed for the project during the second year, offer multiple entry points for students who might be interested in art: including video construction, in storytelling – drawing, in mathematics, sustainability and biology.

The tasks of a “security guard” and a “lottery drawer” introduced in the activity plan of AcrossLimits can be considered as offering multiple entry points to the students in the sense that they do not focus on the concepts of programming or robotic construction. Instead, they bring in real life tasks and professions as a context to be analyzed and modeled in terms of robot behavior.

In the above examples, we showed how concepts from different domains, i.e. mathematics, arts and sciences have been effectively and seamlessly integrated in some of the activity plans of the second year. Furthermore, we showed that concepts from multiple disciplines if integrated well within the activity plan, could offer multiple entry points to the robotics activity. In this respect, we can observe a significant progress and change in comparison to activity plans of year 1.

5.3 STUDENT AGE, SETTING AND CONNECTION TO THE CURRICULUM

Student age ranged from 6 year olds to 18 year olds (for an overview of the statistics of workshops see D.2.). Same to the first year, there are activities connected to the formal curriculum of each country and activities that do not follow the curriculum (see table 2). This year only half of the designed activities are connected to the activities and in a small number of them (only the CU activities and ESI CEE’s “Visualizing Mathematics with Mathbot”) are explicitly connected to specific aspects a national educational curriculum. As we mentioned in D.4.1 the fact that the project has produced activities connected and not associated to formal curricula is a strong point. Specifically, we consider that curricula aligned activities offer an easy entry point to other interested parties to use the activity plans. Whereas activity plans that are not aligned to a specific curriculum might contribute in exploring new ways of thinking and learning around robotics.

With respect to the settings where these activities take place, again there are activities designed to take place in the context of formal education (i.e. schools) and activities, which are carried out irrespectively of the formal educational system. The activities which are taking place within the school can be divided in two subcategories: a) activities designed by school teachers (this is the case

of UoA) and they are integrated in the normal classroom schedule. In this category fall the activities designed by the CU where the researchers collaborate with the school teacher for the design and implementation of the activity; b) Activities designed by external partners like ESI CEE and AL and they are delivered in school not by the school teachers but by the external partners. In this case the teacher might collaborate with the organizers of the workshop or not and might be present during the implementation or not. It appears that these activities take place during class hours but there is no obligation for them to be fully aligned with the formal curriculum (yet, when it happens, it seems to be a good selling point for the activity).

Non-formal settings involve initiatives that might address school students but they do not happen in the physical space of school or within school hours. One such activity comes from the UoA (Robots for sustainability activity), which is organized by a non-profit after school Robotic Club. However, the activity is aligned with the national curriculum in the domains of technology and engineering. As we mentioned earlier alignment with the curriculum might be a good selling point for the students to participate. PRIA activities seem² to take place in a similar setting where students participate on voluntary basis and the school space does not seem to be involved (teachers participating, or school allowing, or all students have to participate in the activity) or influence the focus of the activity. Finally, TU-Wien activities are situated in the non-formal setting as they take place in the University during school hours. It appears here that there might be some kind of collaboration between the University and a school in terms of providing students on a voluntary basis to participate in the workshop, but other than that there seems to be no influence of the school in the organization of the workshop.

No	PARTNER	TITLE	CURRICULUM	SETTING	AGE
NEW ACTIVITY PLANS					
1	AL	Engaging with robots in a fun way	NO	Formal Education	11-13 years
2	ESI CEE	Visualizing mathematics with the Mathbot	YES	Formal Education	9-11 years
3	TU-Wien	ER4STEM Workshops – Robot-video (Elementary)	NO	Non – Formal ³	6-10 years
4	TU-Wien	ER4STEM Workshops – Robot-video (Advanced)	NO	Non – Formal ⁴	14-18 years
5	UoA	Identification and avoidance (bypassing) of obstacles	YES	Formal Education	12-15 years
6	UoA	Robots for sustainability	YES	Non-Formal: After School Robotic club	12-16 years
7	CU	SLurtles Introduction & Orientation	YES	Formal Education	11-12 years
8	CU	SLurtles & Geometry 1	NO	Formal Education	12-13 years
9	CU	Exploring the properties of shapes with SLurtles	YES	Formal Education	8-10 years

² The setting is not clearly stated.

³ Courses take place at the university during school hours

⁴ Courses take place at the university during school hours

10	PRIA	Robotics workshop with Bee bots and Lego Mindstorms	NO	Not stated – non – formal	6-10 years
11	PRIA	Robotics workshop with Lego Mindstorms	NO	Not stated – non – formal	8-13 years
12	PRIA	Robotics workshop with hedgehog	NO	Not stated – non – formal	10-19 years
REVISED ACTIVITY PLANS					
13	AL	Exploring with Dash, and, programming Dash	NO	Formal Education ⁵	10 years average
14	ESI-CEE	Educational Robotics and Creativity Workshop	NO	Computer lab - class	8-12 years
15	UoA	An introduction to robotics (exploring planet ektonis)	YES	Formal Education	10-11 years
16	UoA	Building a robot and making it smart	YES	Formal Education	13-14 years
17	UoA	Robotic Insect	YES	Formal Education	14-15 years
18	UoA	Robots in a maze	YES	Formal Education	15-16 years

Table 2. Overview of robotic activities, student age, relationship with the curriculum and setting

However, the activity plans describe situations where the robotics activity can be implemented in something like a gray zone: i.e. in the school in the context of extracurricular activities which take place after school or during school hours (if there is a slot for extracurricular activities) especially in cases of primary schools, which seem to have more freedom.

Not all the activities created are connected to a formal national curriculum especially those that are designed for non-formal settings and those implemented in the context of extracurricular school activities. Even though there are activity plans declaring connection to the curriculum, the specific concepts of the curriculum are not included in the plan. This is an issue that needs to be addressed in the next version of activity plans especially because connection to curricula in some cases is a criterion for implementing an activity in the classroom.

5.4 STUDENT COLLABORATION

Orchestration of work in the organized workshops - irrespectively of context (formal non formal)-involved group work and whole classroom discussions (assembly discussions). This means that all activity plans foresee robotic constructions and learning in a collaborative setting. ESI CEE also offers a set of suggested interventions for the tutors in order to effectively support student collaboration Activity plan “Visualizing mathematics with Mathbot”):

- Ask questions that promote understanding (i.e. if a group member makes a suggestion then they others are expected to ask why this suggestion is appropriate for what the group attempts to do);
- Ask questions that challenge suggestions (why is this a good idea?);
- Be open to trying new ideas;

⁵ The workshop can take place in the computer lab or school hall

- Respect the other's opinions and do not offend the team members if an idea is not appropriate;
- The group takes responsibility for all the choices made and responsibility is not an issue of the individual (the one who made a wrong suggestion);
- Trying to identify what each member is good at and use his/her abilities to support group work;
- Try to engage all group members in the task.

Apart from the general use of collaborative settings, there are some activity plans, which place special emphasis on collaboration through their design in the sense that they create interesting collaboration settings and put collaboration at the focus of student learning.

Division of labor – turn taking

ESI CEE: “Visualizing mathematics with the Mathbot”. In this activity plan the designers have foreseen specific roles for the students and they have identified points of switching these roles. Specifically, the roles identified are:

- Role 1: writing the code;
- Role 2: holding the cable and helping with the program;
- Role 3: Reading the task and making sure that everything is correct;
- Role 4: Making sure that the rules are followed.

Before we proceed we need to explain Role 2 and Role 4. Holding the cable means that one of the students should hold the USB cable that connects the Finch robot to the computer in order for it to be able to move, especially important for the games that require measuring and thus one student was responsible for that. In both activity plans designed by ESI CEE students are presented with a set of rules that involves their interaction with the robot (especially when young children are involved – like keeping the robot safe, tidy up the working space after every game, safety rules, etc.) but also teamwork and rules of conduct with the tutors (see respective activity plan). Students are expected to change roles after each subtask and the activity plan foresees that the tutors would remind students to change roles during the first session but not in the second session in order to leave the responsibility with them. In a discussion with CU about the results of this arrangement it appeared that students faced these roles as domains of responsibility and not as tasks that they should perform individually. This means that the person who was responsible for writing the program was not the only one contributing to this task (i.e programming the robot – which was also the main task) instead the whole group was expected to participate in it. However, there was one instance recorded, where a student used the division of labor as an opportunity to not take risks but still contribute in the team as he chose the rather “soft” role of reading the task to the others and he did not want to switch roles with the rest of the team.

Groups of special focus and intra-group collaboration

TU-Wien: “ER4STEM Workshops – Robot video (Elementary – Advanced)”. These activity plans have introduced a collaboration scheme, which can be loosely connected with jigsaw and involves mainly inter-group and intra group collaboration. The workshop is divided in two main parts. The first part involves robot construction and programming which has the form of separate tasks. The second part involves the construction of a video, based on a given storyline which requires the understanding of the tasks performed in part one. This video is expected to focus on two robots,

which are programmed by different subgroups. The idea behind this intra-group collaboration is to exchange ideas and discuss what are the specifics of each robot in order to highlight them in the video construction.

Another characteristic of this collaboration scheme is that the class is split up into two groups who are again split up into at least four subgroups with different responsibilities: two subgroups are responsible for the technical part (i.e., programming the robots), one subgroup is responsible for the design (robot and image background) and one subgroup is responsible for maintaining collaboration. In the activity plan it is mentioned that the groups responsible for the design and the video construction should be able to understand the programming and engineering tasks well in order to proceed with the construction of the video. To ensure the latter the tutors provide a specific storyline for the video, which however is not provided with the activity plan. Furthermore, this setup is very interesting and has a lot of potential, however the designers do not explain how the groups responsible for collaboration or for video production are engaged with the robots during the first part. Are they just observers or they work as non-specialized groups during the first part of the workshop? This is an aspect to be considered when groups with specific focus are created: how they engage with the task and how they are not left with nothing to do during parts of the workshop.

Collaboration Rules and reflection on collaboration

AL in the activity plan “Engaging with Robots in a Fun way” have introduced to the students specific collaboration rules and asked them to explicitly reflect on the way they collaborated among them. CU has also introduced the concept of “creating class rules for communication in the virtual space” (See activity plan “SLurtles and Geometry 1”).

AL introduced in the workshop discussion on collaboration and before the activity students were asked to describe what were the elements on good teamwork. After the end of the first phase of the workshop students were asked to reflect on their teamwork. To this end the designers had created a worksheet, which required from the students to work individually and included the following questions:

In a list share with us 3 top tips about collaboration and working with each other. The first tip must be the one, which is most important to you.

Write one more tip about collaboration and working with each other, which you know from your personal experience. (If possible this should be a tip which, hasn't been mentioned in today's session).

At the end of the workshop the students were expected to reflect on a diary entry the most important parts of the workshop experiences. Reflection was done at the level of individuals and included challenging moments and memorable learning experiences:

I worked in a team. The most challenging moment in working as a team was:

I learned from my team members that:

Apart from that, AL included aspects of resilience related to group work:

An idea I hesitated to share with my team was:

This idea could be useful: ...

The last part of reflection on collaboration aims to bring into the foreground situations where students do not participate as much in group work because of fear of failure, fear of mistakes and rejection. This reflection aims at helping students to reflect on these hesitations, see them in the light of completed group work and bring into the foreground that their contribution might have been also valuable for the group.

To sum up, the concept of introducing or helping students to shape collaboration rules is a step towards teaching students basic principles of collaborative work. Moreover, teaching and learning about collaboration can be further elaborated with student reflections on the way they worked and the rules they used to regulate their collaboration especially in challenging tasks such as robotics.

5.5 ARGUMENTATION

Argumentation is part of the collaboration process as students were expected to discuss, negotiate and elaborate on their ideas with their peers, other groups and the classroom. In the new version of the activity plan template the designers were asked to identify the forms of student dialogue that were expecting to take place during the different activities (see “section how to in the classroom”). A closer look into the relevant section in the activity plans of the second year revealed not only forms of dialogue but also topics of discussion:

Topics of discussion:

- Arguing on which are the right parts of the robot to use and how to put the sensor on the robot.
- Argumentation about possible changes in the program, after testing the robot behavior on the floor.
- Discussion on the way that the loops must be used, in order to make the program work.
- Discussion about assumptions (i.e. on the program and/or the robot behavior).
- Communicate plans and ideas about how to construct the body of the robot; to correctly connect the root electronics and to program the robot.
- Technical vocabulary. This is included here as it indicates that the discussion between the students should involve terminology related to the robots and the programming language

The topics of discussion presented above are drawn from activity plans generated by teachers collaborating with UoA. Furthermore, the focus of these activity plans is mainly on the technology and engineering domains, which is also apparent in the discussion topics listed above. Discussion topics is an interesting issue to consider when designing an activity plan because it makes clear what are the designed learning challenges which are expected to be negotiated and explored in a social setting (group or classroom).

Forms of student dialogue:

- Communication with other makers
- Helping each other in the team
- Discussing ideas in the team
- Clearly communicate plans and ideas between the team members
- Discussion through sharing and commenting on ideas.

- Idea generation and discussion (team level – classroom level)
- Student presentation of their work, solutions and ideas to the classroom
- Communicating ideas which are not fully developed
- Communicate with others in a virtual world.
- Between group discussions for understanding and towards a common goal (video creation on the robots of two groups)
- Contribute to group discussion and help everyone take part; help a group to reach agreement, e.g. considering reasons or consequences, keeping focus on the topic
- Contribute to group discussion, taking some responsibility for completing the task well, e.g. introducing relevant ideas, summing up; build on and develop the ideas of others in group discussions, e.g. by asking questions to explore further, offering more ideas.

The forms of student dialogue are listed above from more general towards more specific contributions. Thus on the top of the list we can see a contribution mentioning communication with other makers without specifying the focus of communication (i.e. asking for help, seeking new ideas? Discussing an idea?). Towards the end of the list we observe a very clear focus of student dialogue on considering reasons or consequences when an idea is offered, asking questions for clarification, offering alternatives, etc.

In an attempt to provide an overview of the forms of dialogue described in the activity plans we can say that dialogue includes: a) contributing with – sharing ideas. This can happen at group level or at the classroom level in the form of brainstorming; b) presenting solutions and final work. This is different from the generation of ideas in that presentation of a solution or of the final output means that the group has explored the topic and shows the result of its exploration. Idea generation on the other hand is situated at the beginning of the exploration process thus the idea can be a contribution towards a task or a solution and not the solution or the final output of group work in terms of status; c) Discussing, commenting and challenging ideas: this includes asking questions for further understanding, considering results and consequences, comparing with other solutions, offering alternatives, summing up; d) asking and providing help to others; e) intra-group communication with the aim to understand the solutions of each group in order to use this understanding for a common construct (i.e. video).

Most of the dialogue processes recorded here are also encountered in other settings and learning situations. However, the reference to “communicating ideas which are not fully developed” has a special interest and can be connected to the nature of robotics in specific and the constructionist learning environments in general. When students are encountered with a challenging construction like that of a robot, quite often they might come up with ideas that seem right or worth exploring but students are not able to provide a sufficient explanation or argumentation of why the specific idea is worth pursuing. This is something that happens in constructionist and exploratory environments because in these cases, students learn with the tool and their knowledge evolves along with their construction. This situation can become very challenging in a group discussion because the ways of convincing the others cannot be grounded on arguments that prove that the specific idea is the most appropriate. In these cases students are expected to suggesting testing an idea, to ground their suggestion on previous feedback, to make a disclaimer that this is not a fully developed concept so that the others know how to address it etc.

5.6 LEARNING PROCESS AND REFLECTION

The learning process pursued with the designed activities involved robotic constructions some of which emphasized the programming part of the robot (e.g. visualizing mathematics with the Mathbot, the three activities introduced by CU etc) others emphasized the construction of the robot (e.g. Educational robotics and creativity workshop;) and others introduced a combination of both activities (e.g. The robotic insect, “Building a robot and making it smart”, etc). All activities involve exploration of concepts regarding use of sensors, algorithms, loops, etc. through construction, experimentation analysis of feedback and refinement of initial constructions. The evaluation of the first year workshops showed that a challenging dimension in the learning process was student reflection thus the inclusion of reflective activities was part of the recommendations for the activity design of the second year.

An analysis of the activity plans showed that reflective activities took different forms and made use of different media/tools

- Capturing the problem solving process with OneNote Recordings: Activity plan “SLutrlles & Geometry 1”. In this activity plan, the designers have created a structure (in the form of main questions) that aimed to support students to reflect on the problem solving process they followed in order to create geometrical shapes in the virtual world. In the final phase of the activity, groups were expected to collaborate in order to create a shared reflection on exploring mathematical concepts with a robot on a virtual world.
- Comments in blog posts: Teachers in several cases prompted their students to use the blog of the teacher or Edmodo⁶ to respond to reflective questions regarding the focus of their activity, their biggest challenges and the means to solve their problems, or to describe their construct. Such examples are encountered in several of the UoA activity plans: In “An Introduction to Robotics: Exploring planet Ektonis” the teacher has created a blog where the worksheets and digital material for the workshop is made available for the students along with some reflective questions at different phases of the construction (at the beginning to capture student ideas about robots, in the middle of the construction and at the end of the construction)
- Postcards and diaries: AL introduced the concept of postcards where students reflected on their learning experience with text and sketches (Activity plan: “Exploring with Dash and Programming with Dot”). The concept of a postcard as a reflection instrument is interesting because it is an artifact and has a specific purpose which gives reflection a meaning. The second AL activity plan “Engaging with robots in a fun way” introduced the concept of a structured diary entry which involved a more enriched reflection process as it did not only focus on the construction and the problem solving process but also on aspects of teamwork and resilience (see worksheet 2 and 3). Furthermore, students worked individually on their diaries the confidential form of which, allowed for students to feel free recording aspects of resilience.
- Assembly discussions. Another form of reflection takes place as a final phase of the activity only where students are expected to share with other students the difficulties, the different solutions, the limitations that may have found in every step of the construction process (see for example the activity plans “Building a robot and making it smart”; “Robots in a maze”; “Robotic Insect”). In the activity “Robots for sustainability” reflective discussions are encountered in two phases of the workshop: one reflective discussion is

⁶ <https://www.edmodo.com/home>

done in the middle of the workshop when students have devised several solutions to carbon emission problems and they share with the other groups their ideas with the purpose for the groups to revise their initial solutions combining the different ideas presented. Another reflective discussion is conducted at the end of the process where groups present their robots and reflect on the learning process.

After reviewing of all the above forms and activities through which activity plans supported reflection we can make the following remarks: a) Activity plans following the first year recommendations included in their majority reflective activities which took different forms and had a more prominent or peripheral role in the construction process b) The reflection process had a rather narrow focus as it involved mainly the construction and the problem solving process. There was one very important exception found on the AL activity “Engaging with Robots in a fun way” which focused on other important aspects of the learning process like teamwork and resilience c) the majority of activity plans situated reflection towards the end of the process. Yet a considerable number of activity plans, situated reflection after the completion of a crucial phase of the construction. This latter approach is considered more efficient as it allows for students to make use of the results of the reflective process in the next phase of their construction.

6 CONCLUDING REMARKS AND CONSIDERATIONS FOR THE FINAL VERSION OF ACTIVITY PLANS

6.1 PROGRESS SINCE YEAR 1

In the second year of the project, WP4 had the following outputs:

- A revised version of the activity plan template
- 16 activity blocks distributed in seven different categories of activities that were designed to support teachers in enriching their activity plans so that they support more explicitly and effectively collaboration, reflection and creativity.
- 12 new activity plans
- 6 revised activity plans (produced in year 1)

In terms of methods and activities in order to support the design of activity plans, ETL undertook the following actions:

- In collaboration with CU discussed with the partners the focus of the design on aspects of the learning process regarding collaboration, creativity, reflection, multidisciplinary and multiple entry points.
- Produced the activity blocks as a means to support with concrete examples the requirements for the 2nd year activity plans.
- Offered support to the partners (specifically to commercial partners like ESI CEE and AcrossLimits) during the design of their activity plans. Discussing possibilities and revising the drafts of the activity plans.
- Organized a teacher workshop for the Greek teachers where they met and discussed with the project partners implementing workshops and exchanged experiences from the first year implementation. In this workshop the roadmap for the second year activity plans was presented and discussed
- Developed a structured reflection form in order to capture partners’ views on the changes in the design of the activity plans between the second and the first year.

These activities, methodologies and design instruments developed during the second year seem to have supported the activity plans of the second year to become more aligned with the recommendations of the first year evaluation, as we will show next.

6.2 REFLECTION AND ALIGNMENT WITH THE FIRST YEAR CONSIDERATIONS - RECOMMENDATIONS

One of the observations on the first year activity plans involved the aspect of multidisciplinary. Specifically, it was highlighted that mathematics and sciences were the best integrated subjects in the activity plans and only one activity plan had integrated in a very good way aspects from humanities and business (“Crazy robots”). In the second year activity plans we observed a progress with respect to multidisciplinary. Specifically, as we showed in section 5.2 at least seven out of the 18 activity plans had integrated well in their design other disciplines following the theoretical constructs of powerful ideas and conceptual fields. In these activity plans three of them integrated in a very interesting and innovative way concepts from arts which included a) color production b) storytelling and c) video construction. Furthermore, these activity plans can offer multiple entry points to robotics because as we showed in section 5.2, multidisciplinary can be considered as one dimension of multiple entry points to educational robotics.

With respect to the evaluation recommendations that emerged from the first year evaluation: i.e. collaboration, creativity and reflection the analysis of the activity plans showed that:

- Similar to the activity plans of the first year all activity plans situated the robotics activity in the context of collaborative learning
- The activity plans developed for SLurtles include communication and collaboration in the virtual world which is a new form of collaboration in the domain of educational robotics
- There were activity plans which included in their learning design collaboration i.e. division of labor and turn taking; intra-group collaboration; establishing collaboration and communication rules; structured reflection on collaboration
- Argumentation and student dialogue, which is integrally connected to collaboration – as language is considered as an instrument that regulates collaboration, was explicitly addressed in the revised template for activity plans. Our analysis of activity plans showed that the activity plans designed for different forms of student dialogue which included a) generating ideas b) presenting solutions and final work to the class c) commenting and challenging ideas d) asking and providing help e) intra-group communication.

Creativity was not explicitly addressed or analyzed in the activity plans with the exception of ESI CEE’s revised activity plan “Educational robotics and Creativity workshop”. However, partners in their structured reflection on the second year changes, they stressed that they addressed creativity by constructing more open-ended tasks, which allowed for different solutions to occur. Furthermore, the activity plans that included arts in their objectives integrate in their design creative expression.

Reflection was also included in the majority of the activity plans and in most cases it was part of the final phase of the activity plan (how to section). However, we observed activity plans that introduced reflection in the middle of the process in order for the students to use their reflection in the second phase of their work. Reflection was supported by different media and instruments. Specifically, it took the form of OneNote Recordings, of blog posts in Edmodo or in the teacher’s blog, of diary entries or postcards, or it took the form whole classroom discussions.

Thus, our analysis of the second year activity plans shows that their design was aligned to the first year evaluation of the workshop implementation and activity plan analysis.

6.3 CONSIDERATIONS FOR THE FINAL VERSION OF ACTIVITY PLANS

The final version of activity plans will take into consideration the evaluation results of the implementation of activity plans in the second year workshops, which will provide feedback on the effectiveness of the designed activity plans to the main aspects of interest in the project i.e. collaboration, creativity, meaning generation, multiple entry points and reflection.

Apart from the evaluation of the activity plans in the field, and based on the analysis of the second year activity plans we foresee the following actions for better alignment of the activity plans to the project objectives

- Enrichment of activity blocks.
- Development of an “activity plan in practice” design instrument, which will be aiming to capture teacher practice in the classroom while implementing the activity plan. This document will be designed so that teachers can refine their initial design based on the specifics of the implementation and can enrich it with unexpected moments occurring in dynamic learning situations like the one mentioned in section 5.1
- Supporting further the multiple entry points and the multidisciplinary approach to robotics. ETL will investigate methodologies and will organize events (half-day seminars) for the partners to revise and extend their activity plans so as to include other domains following the approach of conceptual fields and powerful ideas.
- Encouraging further the process of sharing between students, classes and teachers – activity plan designers
- Encouraging further the focus on engaging with real world projects.

During the third year of the project, we will also investigate ways to address some of the first year considerations derived from the evaluation of the Scientix ambassadors:

- Employ digital design solutions in the presentation of the activity plans like websites, YouTube channels, e-library with examples and solutions, use of pictures and videos, and refine language so as to be less academic and more appealing to teachers. During the third year we will use the activity design instrument implemented in the repository of the project
- Strengthen the maker culture among teachers by producing videos and walkthroughs with the technology that maybe useful for other teachers. This material will function as a teacher guide to the use of the robotic kit, will provide “tips and tricks” for other teachers on how to experiment with the specific technology, how they can construct the robot – which programming languages they can use, advice on how to program the robot behavior.
- Investigate how we can address issues of alignment with national curricula across Europe. We already mentioned that the second version of the activity plans will be aligned with the skills tree developed in the framework (W.P.1) and we will also investigate crowdsourcing practices (introducing the activity plans to communities of STEM teachers and asking them to align selected activity plans to their national curriculum)

- Record observations, tips and ideas on how to support students with special needs (like ADD) when engaged with Robotics activity.

The above list will be examined in relation to other project activities (i.e. Framework, evaluation, technologies) and will be prioritized and refined during the final year of the project. Furthermore, this list is not exhaustive, as the considerations included, will be informed by the second year evaluation of the project and will be taken into account in the final version of activity plans (D.4.3 Operational Release of activity plans Due in m 35)

7 OPERATIONAL RELEASE OF ACTIVITY PLANS

In this section, we present the actual activity plans designed according to the activity template presented in section 2. In order for workshop organizers to use the activity plan template to design their activity plans, UoA discussed, explained and refined the dimensions of the template a) in project meetings with ER4STEM partners and b) in a one-day workshop with teachers (in UoA-ETL). To further illustrate and clarify each aspect of the template, UoA – ETL provided to the ERW organizers an example of activity plan designed with the specific template.

7.1 NEW ACTIVITY PLANS

Engaging with robots in a fun way

AUTHOR:

Pullicino Joanna, Duca Annalise

SHORT DESCRIPTION OF THE ACTIVITY (SUMMARY)

These were workshops run with students whose age was between 11 - 13 years, and, at secondary level. The robots used were Dash and Dot although the practical aspects were explored with Dash. Dash is a pre-constructed robot and activities focused around programming Dash through commands and loop statements. Another objective was explaining to students that when searching for a solution programming gives you the advantage of finding multiple answers to activities, and, that some solutions are simpler and more straightforward than others.

These sessions were run between March and May 2017 and during each workshop the tutors reflected with the students about group work and collaboration; a worksheet (Annex 2) was also assigned to students to gather feedback about this. STEM careers and gender in science were topics discussed during workshops.

Another topic discussed with students was about success, failure and resilience. These factors were presented to students in an employment context where perseverance, personal initiative and drive are key factors. The students recounted their experience of how successful/unsuccessful they were during the workshop activities by describing this in a diary post (Annex 3).

FOCUS, SET UP AND REQUIREMENTS OF THE ACTIVITY

CURRICULUM

Select NO if the scenario is not aligned with the curriculum of your country and YES if it is. Please mention the relevant subject matter.

NO X YES Subject:

CONTENT

Choose categories and give a rating of the level of emphasis on concepts from each of the following domains

<input type="checkbox"/> Science	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Technology	<input type="checkbox"/> Business	<input type="checkbox"/> Engineering	<input type="checkbox"/> Arts	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Mathematics
(0-10)	(0-10)	(0-10)	(0-10)	(0-10)	(0-10)
0	8	0	0	0	6

OBJECTIVES

<i>Subject related</i>	Specific tasks according to set instructions related to, technology, programming and mathematical concepts including probability and random numbers.
<i>Technology use related</i>	Drag and drop visuals
<i>Social and action related</i>	Allowed students to collaborate and share ideas with each other, and, to learn that decision making processes are enhanced when being teams/groups.
<i>Argumentation and fostering of maker culture:</i>	Finding multiple solutions to activities, allowing the robot to respond to external stimuli/obstacles

TIME

Duration: 2 days

Schedule: 4 hours per day

MATERIALS AND ARTIFACTS

<i>Digital artifact</i>	Drag and Drop visuals
<i>Robotic artifact</i>	Not applicable
<i>Student's workbook and manual</i>	Using worksheets containing graded activities whose difficulty increased from one task to another
<i>Teacher's instruction book and manual:</i>	Power point presentation, and, hard copy of programme for time management

STUDENTS AND SPACE

STUDENTS (TARGET AUDIENCE)

<i>Sex and Age:</i>	boys & girls, 11 - 13 years old. Some classes were same gender, girls only.
<i>Prior knowledge:</i>	Knowledge of Scratch language for a few of the students which helped with programming of Dash; very few others had attended Lego Mindstorm classes. Other students had no previous knowledge in programming or robotics.
<i>Nationality and cultural background</i>	The majority Maltese; around 10% came from European or non-European countries
<i>Social status and social environment</i>	Church schools and private schools. In church schools the population is of a diverse social status. In private schools the majority come from a high social background and there are more foreigners attending versus church schools.
<i>Special needs and abilities</i>	Some degree of autism, dyslexia, dyscalculia, Down's syndrome

SPACE INFO

Organizational and cultural context: computer lab or school hall or school gymnasium

Physical characteristics: indoors

SOCIAL ORCHESTRATION**POPULATION**

Students: e.g: groups ranged between 15 and 26

Tutors: e.g. 2

GROUPING:

Grouping criteria	e.g. mixed ability, mixed gender or single gender
<i>Setting:</i>	e.g. Students seated on the floor, indoors, in groups of 2 or 3 sharing a tablet and a robot per group.

INTERACTION DURING THE ACTIVITY (EMPHASIS)

Actions	e.g. Exchange ideas and dialogue
<i>Relationships</i>	e.g. Collaborative and competitive (during races)
<i>Roles in the group</i>	e.g. role exchange in the group
<i>Support by the tutor(s)</i>	e.g. Intervene, monitor, facilitate

LEARNING PROCEDURES**EXPECTED STUDENT ACTIVITY**

Students during the activity are expected to engage in the following actions: construct, observe, communicate, create, present their work in a blog, exchange ideas, etc.

STUDENT LEARNING PROCESSES

<i>Designed Conflicts and</i>	Not applicable to activities prepared
-------------------------------	---------------------------------------

<i>misconceptions</i>	
<i>Learning processes emphasized:</i>	1. multiple programming solutions to the activities 2. communicate and discuss tasks set and decide on the way forward 3. write up about your experience, learn about collaborative issues).
<i>Expected relevance of alternative knowledge</i>	None

“HOW TO” IN THE CLASSROOM

In this section of the activity plan we describe how we expect the teaching and the learning process to evolve. We might use phases or activities for this description. The phases or activities should support the objectives stated and make use of the materials, tools and teaching and learning processes mentioned earlier in the activity plan. Next we provide an example of phase description

PHASE 1: INTRODUCTION AND EXPERIMENTATION

Duration: 2 hours

Orchestration: Presentation, experimentation and group work.

Description: The pre-questionnaire was first carried out. This was followed by an introduction to what are robots and what isn't a robot. Advantages and disadvantages of robots in everyday life, and, how or why humans use them.

Collaboration, communication and teamwork are discussed and students are asked to talk about the requisites for good teamwork (Annex 2). Examples of science careers and employments were presented to them to sustain the applicability of STEM subjects and nurture STEM in their thinking and possibly future choice of subjects. Gender in career uptake and employment is discussed to explain that any STEM career can be equally taken up by males or females and hence to break down any stereotype images that the students might have had.

A demonstration of Dash and its functions, sensors and actions was explained to the children. The robot was then handed out and they were allowed firstly to experiment and explore freely.

Indicate which of the stated objectives are supported by this phase: Subject related, Technology use and action related

Expected student constructions: Not applicable

Expected forms of student dialogue: communication and taking turns

Teaching method: Instruction, demonstration by example, discussion with the students and experimentation by the students themselves.

PHASE 2: SEQUENTIAL PROGRAMMING AND LOOPS

Duration: 2 hours

Orchestration: Group work (groups of 2 or 3) and individual

Description: Students implement their first programs as per the puzzle sheet (Annex 1). Loops, If-else, repeat-until were included in the programs constructed by the students. A key factor in these

puzzles was to make students aware that a number of options and answers are possible in programming which range from a simple to a more complex solution.

Puzzle 5, as shown in Annex 1 allowed the students to come up with an activity themselves for a peer. We emphasized on creativity and to come up with an exciting task; this task was based on bringing in knowledge from the previous activities of the day but it had to be different.

At the end of this workshop, students were given a worksheet to point out characteristics relating to collaboration and group work.

Indicate which of the stated objectives are supported by this phase: Subject related, Technology use and action related

Expected student constructions: Not applicable

Expected forms of student dialogue: discussion, communication, taking turns, taking decisions

Teaching method: Instruction, demonstration by example, discussion, experimentation

PHASE 3: USING LOOPS AND ANALYSIS

Duration: 3 hours

Orchestration: group work

Description: Two scenarios are presented to students where the robot assumes two personalities: as a security guard (puzzle 6) and a lottery drawer (puzzle 7). In the former situation the robot must realise where its boundaries are and walk accordingly from one end to another. As a lottery drawer the robot presents a fair and transparent scenario by drawing random numbers. In both instances there are multiple ways how to arrive to your answer and the loops came into the picture again.

Two commonly used mathematical and analytical topics were part of these activities and explained. These are the use of graphs to interpret data collected (Puzzle 6) and hence the importance of statistics, and, probability (Puzzle 7). With regards to probability students recorded the number generated by their robot. The tutors generated a random number and then listed all the numbers on the board. Later the tutor revealed the number the robot generated. The question “What is the probability that your robot generates the same number as mine?” was asked to the students.

Indicate which of the stated objectives are supported by this phase

Expected student constructions - not applicable

Expected forms of student dialogue: brainstorming, interpretation

Teaching method: instruction, demonstration by example, discussion, experimentation

PHASE 4: REFLECTION AND POST FEEDBACK

Duration: 1 hour

Orchestration: Individual work

Description: These 2 day workshops focused on the students' abilities to come up with more than one answer to a task, and, therefore their resilience to achieve or give up. They were asked to describe and talk about their experience with being successful, unsuccessful and resilient in a diary post.

At the end of this exercise, the students were asked to give their feedback about the two day workshops which they had participated to.

An interview was carried out to 2 - 3 students who had acted as the focus group to get deeper insight of their experiences.

Indicate which of the stated objectives are supported by this phase

Expected student constructions: not applicable

Expected forms of student dialogue: personal reflection, evaluation

Teaching method: Explanation

ASSESSMENT PROCEDURES

In this section we include the worksheets they were used during the implementation of the activity both as an instrument to support the teaching and learning process and as means to assess students

ANNEX 1 – WORKSHEET 1

Puzzle 1

Make Dash drive in a square.

There are 2 correct answers for this puzzle, can you find them both?

Puzzle 2

Make Dash look left and right for 5 times.

There are 2 correct answers for this puzzle, can you find them both?

Puzzle 3

Make Dash work like a traffic light. Each colour should be active for 10 seconds. Once the light turns green, Dash should move forward 1 meter.

There are 2 correct answers for this puzzle, can you find them both?

Puzzle 4

Make dash drive forward until he finds an obstacle.

There are 2 (or more) correct answers for this puzzle, can you find them?

Puzzle 5

Based on what you have learned in Puzzles 1 to 4 above, use this knowledge to come up with a puzzle for a friend your age in another class. Try it out to find out whether it works; ensure that your puzzle is solvable. Provide the answer as though you will act yourselves as the tutor.

Turn Dash into a Security Guard

Puzzle 6

Part A

Your robot has a task. He is a soldier in a war zone and everyday and at all times he has to patrol a marked territory walking from end to another without stopping and without walking into the set boundaries marked by sacks.

Make Dash walk from one end to the other of the marked territory without bumping into the sacks.

Use cardboard boxes as sacks.

There are over 4 correct answers, how many can you find? (Use your tablet to keep a record of your results and ask the tutors to check these).

Part B

After a month, the rebels lost some of their territory. This meant that Dash had less area to patrol and the sacks were brought closer. The new distance Dash walks from one side to another has decreased. Dash's task remained the same: the robot had to persist on a daily basis to patrol the boundaries and walk from one end to another.

Think: a) The distance has changed; does your programme from Part A to Part B change too?

b) The tutors will inform you of the different solutions obtained within the class; interpret this information and present it as a bar graph

Grand Lottery

Puzzle 7

Dash is able to generate random numbers. He finds himself at the Lottery Department and Dash is involved in the draw so that it is fair. His role is to generate 5 numbers to create a 5-digit number. This 5-digit number is the winning ticket and its owner is the winner of EUR 1,000,000!!

Get Dash to make this draw of five numbers; as a team you have to give the tutors your 5-digit number.

ANNEX 2 – WORKSHEET 2

In a list share with us 3 top tips about collaboration and working with each other. The first tip must be the one which is most important to you.

1. _____
2. _____
3. _____

Write one more tip about collaboration and working with each other which you know from your personal experience. (If possible this should be a tip which hasn't been mentioned in today's session).

ANNEX 3 – WORKSHEET 3

You were asked to find solutions to make Dash behave as a soldier and as a Lottery drawer. In arriving to these solutions you may have been successful or you may have failed (completely or partially) and we wish you to write about how this went by creating a diary post. Imagine you own a diary and you are going to share your feelings with it. Fill in the below as best as you can.

Dear Diary,

Today, at school, I was involved in workshops using Dash. This robot played two roles: being a soldier in a war zone and a Lottery Drawer at the Lottery Department.

I worked in a team. The most challenging moment in working as a team was

I learned from my team members that:

An idea I hesitated to share with my team was

This idea could be useful:

I (succeeded/failed) _____

to solve (one/both/none) _____ of these puzzles. _____

_____ (Mention the names of the puzzles if any).

When I (failed/succeeded) to find an answer or answers I felt: _____

As the friend with whom I share all my secrets, I wish to tell you that my feelings and attitude today following this workshop are:

And, (write anything else which you wish to tell your diary):

Thanks for taking care of my feelings and secrets,

Your dearest friend,

_____ (write your code number here)

Visualizing mathematics with the Mathbot

AUTHORS

ESI CEE Team: Christina Todorova and Petar Sharkov with the support and direct contribution of Ivaylo Gueorguiev, Pavel Varbanov, Dr. George Sharkov, Prof. Galina Momcheva and Prof. Mariya Nisheva

SHORT DESCRIPTION OF THE ACTIVITY (SUMMARY)

The goal of this workshop is to introduce and exercise mathematical concepts, which are covered in the national school curriculum for mathematics for the fourth grade in Bulgarian schools, using programming and robotics.

Participants play 5 different games with the robot. Every game builds on the previous one and is broken down into quests, through which they exercise their knowledge on mathematics and adopt new concepts while exercising them. Children program to make the robot move and they make the robot move to solve a mathematical problem.

In addition, and of equal importance to the subject of mathematics, this workshop is specifically designed to support and encourage the development of the following skills:

1. Problem solving skills are stimulated by encouraging students to solve different kind of problems in conventional ways, but also to seek innovative ways to find solutions. Children are stimulated to identify and ask significant questions that clarify various points of views and lead to better solutions.
2. Communication is important for the successful outcome of the games. This includes the ability to articulate thoughts and ideas effectively in a group. Groups consist of student of diverse points of view, knowledge and abilities, which requires a certain ability to communicate complex ideas clearly, effectively and patiently.
3. Flexibility and adaptability is a skill which is greatly incorporated on many levels. Students have to be flexible in order to incorporate feedback from other team members and tutors effectively, and furthermore to understand, negotiate and balance diverse views and beliefs to reach workable solutions.

Within the sessions, students are required to shift roles within their group, which consist of different responsibilities, aiming to ensure that flexibility and adaptability skills are fostered. During the second session, students are not reminded to shift roles, which encourages communication, as well as provides students the chance to fall back into the most comfortable role within their team.

Robotics is intriguing and fun, which is why we believe it makes a wonderful tool, in addition to the general school curriculum, for learning mathematics. We know that learning by doing makes children fall in love with mathematics and robotics is the way we visualize mathematics.

FOCUS, SET UP AND REQUIREMENTS OF THE ACTIVITY

CURRICULUM

NO YES Subject: Mathematics

This workshop is aligned to and specifically designed to support the Bulgarian national curriculum on Mathematics for the fourth grade.

CONTENT

Choose categories and give a rating of the level of emphasis on concepts from each of the following domains

<input type="checkbox"/> Science	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Technology	<input type="checkbox"/> Business	<input type="checkbox"/> Engineering	<input type="checkbox"/> Arts	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Mathematics
(0-10)	(0-10)	(0-10)	(0-10)	(0-10)	(0-10)
0	5	0	0	0	10

OBJECTIVES

<i>Subject related</i>	<p>Mathematics:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Learn more and exercise knowledge on angles and how to measure them using protractors; Engage students in brief discussions about different types of triangles by length of sides (scalene, isosceles, equilateral) and by width of angles (acute, right, obtuse) to enable them to learn from one another; Engage students in brief discussions about circles and the elements of a circle (radius and diameter only). Exercise knowledge about circles through games with the robot. Exercise arithmetical functions - multiplication addition, subtraction and division by including them as part of the games; Exercise the use of measuring tools such as ruler and protractor; Showcase the difference between positive and negative numbers without going into theory; Showcase the difference between whole numbers and decimal numbers without going into theory; <p>Technology:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Students gain understanding of what a robot is and know some common robotic parts; Students understand that robots are programmable; Students apply sequences of actions to program their robot. Students gain knowledge on sensors and some different types of sensors; Students understand that different sensors serve different purpose; Students understand that sensors are controllable;
<i>Technology use related</i>	Programming The Finch robot developed by Birdbrain Technologies with the visual programming software Scratch .
<i>Social and action related</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Develop problem solving skills; Exercise effective communication skills; Encourage flexibility and adaptability;

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Foster collaboration skills;
<i>Argumentation and fostering of maker culture:</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Practicing communication skills in terms of formulating and expressing ideas. • Encourage curiosity; • Encourage tinkering and experimentation; • The games require the decision-making process within a team; • Identifying and solving problems; • Stimulate proportional thinking and proportional reasoning by thinking in proportion to solve the mathematical tasks while visualizing the solution both on the screen by programming, as well as on a physical level with the robot. • Exercise logical thinking;

TIME

Duration: 1-2 weeks (8 hours in total)

Schedule: 2 sessions, 4 hours per session

MATERIALS AND ARTIFACTS

<i>Digital artifact</i>	<p>Desktop version of Scratch visual programming software.</p> <p>A digital artifact of learning will be Scratch project files from teams. Students work only with the desktop version of Scratch in order to avoid connectivity issues.</p>
<i>Robotic artifact</i>	<p>The Finch robot by Birdbrain Technologies programmable using Scratch visual programming language.</p> <p>Children program a pre-constructed robot with USB cable and do not build one themselves.</p>
<i>Student's workbook and manual</i>	<p>Handouts with the game tasks of gradual complexity, featuring example code for in case of trouble getting started. Sheet with answers and bonus games.</p> <p>Additional materials necessary: markers, color pens, pencils, plain paper of different sizes (A4, A3, A1), protractors, rulers.</p>
<i>Teacher's instruction book and manual:</i>	<p>Activity plan, workshop checklists, copy of student handouts, source code, evaluation protocol.</p>

STUDENTS AND SPACE

STUDENTS (TARGET AUDIENCE)

<i>Sex and Age:</i>	boys & girls, 9-11 years old (fourth grade students)
<i>Prior knowledge:</i>	The workshop is developed as continuation of the "Educational Robotics and Creativity Workshop" for students, so it is expected or recommended for the students to know the very basics of Scratch

	programming and robotics elements. The workshop is developed taking into account the national curriculum for mathematics for the fourth grade. Students should be familiar with third grade mathematics.
<i>Nationality and cultural background</i>	Bulgarian and Bulgaria-based minorities;
<i>Social status and social environment</i>	Mainstream public schools;
<i>Special needs and abilities</i>	Fluency in Bulgarian language as game tasks are written in Bulgarian. Children with physical disabilities or mental disorders might need additional help from specialized personnel according to their special education needs and obstructions, if any.

SPACE INFO

Organizational and cultural context: In school or at a club, equipped with a spacious hall, with one computer and empty table per team, enough chairs, projector or smart TV screen.

Useful but not required are whiteboard & internet access.

Physical characteristics: Indoors

SOCIAL ORCHESTRATION

POPULATION

Students: up to 28

Tutors: e.g. 2-3; **Assistants:** 1 (school teacher)

GROUPING

Grouping criteria	No specific criteria – students or school teachers decide how to form the groups
<i>Setting:</i>	3-4 students in a group, indoors, at a school or club. Every group is seated around one table, with a computer and enough chairs. Every group works with one robot.

INTERACTION DURING THE ACTIVITY (EMPHASIS)

Actions	Exchange ideas, engage in dialogues, negotiations, debates; Program, calculate, measure; Test out concepts and ideas; Learning by experiencing;
<i>Relationships</i>	Collaborative;
<i>Roles in the group</i>	Role exchange in the group ;
<i>Support by the tutor(s)</i>	Intervene, monitor, facilitate, encourage;

LEARNING PROCEDURES

EXPECTED STUDENT ACTIVITY

Students during the activity are expected to engage in effective communication within the team, with other teams and tutors in order to successfully complete their quests. A problem solving attitude is expected in order to experiment with new ideas to solve problems and observe results in order to improve or change strategy. Students are expected to be flexible and adapt to different roles in terms of responsibility within a team, and to be tolerant and patient with their classmates and the tutors.

Students are supposed to verbally and visually present their solutions to tutors and optionally other teams, which requires them to communicate their learning curve and solution in an understandable and clear manner.

STUDENT LEARNING PROCESSES

<i>Designed Conflicts and misconceptions</i>	The only designed conflict is to put students in a situation which contradicts their probable attitude that some roles are more important in a team than others. By promoting flexibility and adaptability within a team, children are encouraged to find a way to show their abilities and be useful for the team in different context in terms of role.
<i>Learning processes emphasized:</i>	Emphasis on experimenting with different values and approaches to reach a goal, as well as on analyzing robot results in order to refine and reflect on the code that defines this result.
<i>Expected relevance of alternative knowledge</i>	Alternative knowledge will be encouraged as the activity requires logical thinking, interpretation and creativity. Children might apply knowledge from other domains apart from mathematics, such as Mind Mapping and ICT.

“HOW TO” IN THE CLASSROOM

The workshop is divided into 2 sessions of 4 hours each. In each session, students have to complete a given number of games with gradual complexity.

The ultimate goal of the games with gradual complexity is to introduce students in a complex concept or construct. The idea is to start with simple procedures or physical constructions and in consecutive steps add new and new elements in the process.

PHASE 1: INTRODUCTION & PRE-WORKSHOP EVALUATION

Duration: 70 minutes

Orchestration: Individual and group work. Groups consist of 3-4 members, if necessary 5.

Description: The tutors introduce themselves, explain what they do and why they came to the school. They also explain what is the task for the specific day and how this is going to build on the Educational Robotics and Creativity Workshop, in case children have went through it. Next, they ask from the students what they remember from the Educational Robotics and Creativity Workshop and if they have had any robotics and/or programming experience since then in order to break the ice and put children in the mood for sharing and thinking about robotics, but also to refresh their memory. Children are also asked about their **attitude on mathematics**, whether they like it and whether they think robots are useful for teaching mathematics. The purpose is to become familiar with the audience and vice versa and to explore their existing attitudes.

The researchers introduce themselves as **robot enthusiasts and math-lovers** and explain that in this workshop they will play and work together with the student teams in order to solve several mathematical games using the Finch robot. Tutors explain again the importance of feedback and student contributions which will be used to design even more interesting educational workshops.

Following this, children fill out the **Pre-Workshop Questionnaire** evaluation activity. In case this is the first acquaintance with these students, they are asked to complete the Draw a Scientist evaluation activity. Children are provided with instructions on how to fill out the questionnaires.

After the evaluation, the tutors continue the discussion about robots and ask questions about the parts of the robot. They introduce the Finch robot and ask children to fill out the **“Parts of my Robot handout”** together as a team.

Afterwards, students are ready to refresh their memory on **Mind Maps**, by having to complete a group Mind Map on the **abilities of their robot**, based on what they know about the robot's sensors.

Following that, they are presented with the **workshop rules**. Every group is handed out a Mind Map with the workshop rules.

The rules are explained and a focus is put on the importance of recording results, on protecting the robot and on switching roles within the team. Tutors try and emphasize to the students that in order to complete the task they need to collaborate with other students. The work of one person, no matter how good it is, is not going to be better than the collective work. Switching roles is of utmost experience to the success of the group and that everyone has to gain experience.

Please note that this is a translation of the Mind Map with the Workshop rules, not the original handout!

Children are encouraged by tutors to find a way to work past possible differences and disagreement within a team, by supporting them on occasions with advice to:

- ask questions that promote understanding (i.e. if a group member makes a suggestion then they others are expected to ask why this suggestion is appropriate for what the group attempts to do);
- ask questions that challenge suggestions (why is this a good idea?);
- be open to trying new ideas;
- respect the other's opinions and do not offend the team members if an idea is not appropriate;
- the group takes responsibility for all the choices made and responsibility is not an issue of the individual (the one who made a wrong suggestion);
- trying to identify what each member is good at and use his/her abilities to support group work;
- try to engage all group members in the task.

Workshop objectives supported: Students gain understanding of what a robot is and know some common robotic parts; They understand that robots are programmable and gain knowledge on sensors and some different types of sensors; Students are aware that different sensors serve different purpose; Foster communication and collaboration skills; practicing communication skills in terms of formulating and expressing ideas; decision-making within a team;

Expected student constructions: Completed pre-workshop evaluation forms, completed introduction handouts.

Expected forms of student dialogue: Collaboration;

Teaching method: Evaluation activities – Instruction; Introduction activities – Discussion;

PHASE 2: MOVING OUR ROBOT

Duration: 70 minutes

Orchestration: Group work. Groups consist of 3-4 members, if necessary 5.

Description: Students implement their first programs that have programming blocks in a row. No loops or selection structures are needed. The first program should move the robot forwards. The

robot is pre-assembled so students have to focus on programming and debugging their own programs. After a successful first program, they are asked to write additional code, so as to program their robots to move backwards, left, right, around its center (left and right) and create a stop button. Bonus games include making LED lights shine at a push of a button and change colors after another button is pressed.

Workshop objectives supported: Students are programming the Finch robot developed by Birdbrain Technologies with the visual programming software Scratch. They are further showcased the difference between positive and negative numbers without going into theory, as programming the Finch to move backwards requires a negative value for the motors. Students understand that robots are programmable;

This game develops problem solving skills, exercises effective communication and collaboration skills, encourages flexibility and adaptability. Students are formulating and expressing ideas. They are encouraged to experiment and test out ideas;

This game requires the decision-making process within a team, while stimulating proportional thinking and proportional reasoning by thinking in proportion to solve the mathematical tasks while visualizing the solution both on the screen by programming, as well as on a physical level with the robot.

Students also exercise logical thinking as solutions to this game are interconnected.

Expected student constructions: Code

Expected forms of student dialogue: Collaboration

Teaching method: Instruction, demonstration by example, discussion, experimentation

PHASE 3: WAIT! AND DO A SEQUENCE OF ACTIONS

Duration: 40 minutes

Orchestration: Group work. Groups consist of 3-4 members, if necessary 5.

Description: Students build on the knowledge, gained during the previous game to make a sequence of actions with the use of “wait”, to gain a smarter command of the robot. In this game, the robot has to complete a series of tasks on the push of a given button.

Workshop objectives supported: Students apply sequences of actions to program their robot. Students are applying the skills and principles related to the argumentation and fostering of maker culture objectives, as well as the targeted skills from the social and action related objectives, similarly to Phase 2.

This game develops problem solving skills, exercises effective communication and collaboration skills, encourages flexibility and adaptability. Students are formulating and expressing ideas. They are encouraged to experiment and test out ideas;

This game requires the decision-making process within a team, while stimulating proportional thinking and proportional reasoning by thinking in proportion to solve the mathematical tasks while visualizing the solution both on the screen by programming, as well as on a physical level with the robot.

Students also exercise logical thinking as solutions to this game are interconnected.

Expected student constructions: Code

Expected forms of student dialogue: Collaboration

Teaching method: Demonstration by example, discussion, experimentation. Teachers refrain from instructions at this point, leaving students at a position where they have to experiment with different ideas and observe results to achieve the desired result.

PHASE 4: MATHEMATICAL GAMES – MEASURING LINES

Duration: 60 minutes

Orchestration: Group work. Groups consist of 3-4 members, if necessary 5.

Description: Students attach a pencil to their robots using sticky papers. With a pencil they have to draw, by pressing only one button, lines with different values. They have to work with a ruler to make the measurements and have to do some precise coding to achieve their goal. This game requires students to discover fractions to achieve precise results.

This game exercises proportional thinking and encourages experimentation.

The second part of the game is devoted to applying arithmetical functions to achieve lines of a certain length. Students have to use fractions again, and learn or exercise their knowledge of calculating fractions.

Workshop objectives supported: Students apply sequences of actions to program their robot and exercise arithmetical functions - multiplication addition, subtraction and division by including them as part of the games. They use measuring tools to complete the game (ruler) and test out in practice work with whole numbers and decimal numbers (without going into theory) by having to program the “wait time” to achieve precision with their results;

Students are applying the skills and principles related to the argumentation and fostering of maker culture objectives, as well as the targeted skills from the social and action related objectives.

Expected student constructions: Code

Expected forms of student dialogue: Collaboration

Teaching method: Experimentation, discussion. Teachers refrain from instructions at this point, leaving students at a position where they have to experiment with different ideas and observe results to achieve the desired result.

PHASE 5: MATHEMATICAL GAMES – MEASURING ANGLES

Duration: 80 minutes

Orchestration: Group work. Groups consist of 3-4 members, if necessary 5.

Description: As usually this game is conducted during the second session, students are given a simple task to perform within 10-15 minutes to refresh their knowledge on Scratch programming from the previous session.

When they've done that, tutors engage the students in brief discussions about different types of triangles by length of sides (scalene, isosceles, equilateral) and by width of angles (acute, right, obtuse) to enable them to learn from one another.

Building on their knowledge about angles, children are briefed on how to measure angles by the tutors. This is explained by one of the tutors and to reinforce the knowledge of the students, a handout with various figures is given out to the children to complete in groups.

After making sure that each group feels comfortable measuring angles, we continue with a game, aiming to make children exercise what they know about angles.

This game is adapted from the www.finchrobot.com and could be viewed [here](#).

For this activity, children are given paper, pencils, colored markers and a protractor. They have to make the Finch turn around one wheel at speed 30. Students measure how far the Finch turns for different wait times, and they use this information to figure out how to calculate the wait time for a particular angle, which is included in the bonus games.

Workshop objectives supported: Students learn more and exercise knowledge on angles and how to measure them using protractors. They are also discussing the different types of triangles by length of sides (scalene, isosceles, equilateral) and by width of angles (acute, right, obtuse) to enable them to learn from one another;

They use measuring tools to complete the game (protractor and ruler) and test out in practice work with whole numbers and decimal numbers (without going into theory) by having to program the “wait time” to align with the requirements of the game task;

Students are applying the skills and principles related to the argumentation and fostering of maker culture objectives, as well as the targeted skills from the social and action related objectives.

Expected student constructions: Code

Expected forms of student dialogue: Collaboration

Teaching method: Instruction, demonstration by example, discussion, experimentation.

PHASE 6: MATHEMATICAL GAMES - CIRCLES

Duration: 80 minutes

Orchestration: Group work. Groups consist of 3-4 members, if necessary 5.

Description: Students are engaged in a discussion about their knowledge on circles. Students come up with definitions about a circle and its elements. By doing this, children are encouraged to learn from one another and exercises their ability to express themselves and articulate complex concepts verbally.

Afterwards, a game exercising knowledge on circles is explained. Students have to program the robot to draw a perfect circle by making it turn around one of its wheels for certain time. They have to experiment to find the precise value and have to collaborate with one another in order to test out various ideas.

At this point of the workshop, they are no longer reminded to shift roles in order to observe if groups created a habit of social and team flexibility or team members naturally fall into a role that feels most comfortable.

Following the first quest of this game, students have to program a robot to make a series of circles, a series of semi-circles. They are encouraged to draw out different elements of the circles, such as radius and diameter and measure them.

This last game ends with a quest, aiming to exercise everything learnt by this moment – a complex sequence of tasks, including measuring lines and angles, drawing circles, making LED lights shine with different color every time the robot changes its direction of movement.

Workshop objectives supported: Students are engaged in brief discussions about circles and the elements of a circle (radius and diameter only). Together in groups, they exercise their knowledge about circles through games with the robot.

The final quest of this game combines everything learnt so far and answers to all of the subject related objectives.

Phase 5 fosters skills related to the argumentation and fostering of maker culture objectives, as well as the targeted skills from the social and action related objectives, similarly to all previous phases.

Expected student constructions: Code

Expected forms of student dialogue: Collaboration

Teaching method: Experimentation. Teachers refrain from instructions at this point, leaving students at a position where they have to experiment with different ideas and observe results to achieve the desired result.

PHASE 7: FEEDBACK AND EVALUATION, FINAL GAMES AND CONCLUSIONS

Duration: 80 minutes

Orchestration: Individual and group work. Groups consist of 3-4 members, if necessary 5.

Description: In addition to the activity sheets that students complete during activity phases, finally they discuss in classroom the difficulties, the different solutions, the limitations that may have found in every step. They also fill in an evaluation questionnaire and teacher gets short informal open interviews from students that want to share their experience. Children are asked about their recommendations and their favorite games from both sessions.

Tutors give instructions on how to complete the evaluation papers and thanks children for participating in the workshop.

Students have time for their final experiments. They are left with the opportunity to ask questions, test out different speeds and play Finch football.

Finch football is a game, in which children are provided with a ball that the Finch has to “kick” into a gate, created by the team (with their hands or using anything they could find in the classroom). For this purpose, students have to write a sequence of action, executable with the press of one button.

They can also play Finch pong, using the robot’s accelerometer and a pre-made program. A video of the game from another workshop, not conducted by ESI CEE or ER4STEM partner, could be found [here](#).

Workshop objectives supported: Ultimately, students gain understanding of what a robot is and know some common robotic parts; They understand that robots are programmable and gain knowledge on sensors and some different types of sensors; Students are aware that different sensors serve different purpose; They have already worked on the subjects of mathematics and informatics and have covered a lot of subject related material.

The final games are informal and serve as a conclusion to the workshop. They support the objectives related to fostering curiosity, experimentation and collaboration.

Expected student constructions: Code, Post-Workshop Questionnaire, Focus group interview

Teaching method: Evaluation activities – Instruction;
Other activities – Discussion, Experimentation;

ASSESSMENT PROCEDURES

REGARDING DIRECT WORKSHOP OBJECTIVES

Objective	Activities to achieve the objective	Assessment (evaluation) procedures
<p><i>Subject related – technology, engineering, science</i></p>	<p>Mathematics:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Learn more and exercise knowledge on angles and how to measure them using protractors; • Engage students in brief discussions about different types of triangles by length of sides (scalene, isosceles, equilateral) and by width of angles (acute, right, obtuse) to enable them to learn from one another; • Engage students in brief discussions about circles and the elements of a circle (radius and diameter only). • Exercise knowledge about circles through games with the robot. • Exercise arithmetical functions - multiplication addition, subtraction and division by including them as part of the games; • Exercise the use of measuring tools such as ruler and protractor; • Showcase the difference between positive and negative numbers without going into theory; • Showcase the difference between whole numbers and decimal numbers without going into theory; <p>Technology:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Students gain understanding of what a robot is and know some common robotic parts; • Students understand that robots are programmable; • Students apply sequences of actions to program their robot. • Students gain knowledge on sensors and some different types of sensors; • Students understand that different sensors serve different purpose; <p>Students understand that sensors are controllable;</p>	<p>Opinions about STEM as well as preconceptions about scientists, scientists and robotics are measured by the pre and post workshop questionnaires as well as visualized through the draw a scientist exercise, if applicable.</p> <p>Mind Maps are used as tools to boost creativity and remember rules. Group interviews assess and record concepts regarding collaboration and digital fluency. Tutor reflections and observations support the assessment of this objective.</p>
<p><i>Technology use related</i></p>	<p>Programming The Finch robot developed by Birdbrain Technologies with the visual programming software Scratch.</p>	<p>Photos and videos of successfully performed tasks. Tutor reflections and observations support the assessment of this objective.</p>

<p><i>Social and action related</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop problem solving skills; • Exercise effective communication skills; • Encourage flexibility and adaptability; <p>Foster collaboration skills;</p>	<p>Group discussions/interviews and focus group interviews are used as a tool to record students' progress, opinions and changing attitudes, along the with questionnaires. Attitudes towards team work are recorded and measured with the questionnaires as well. Tutor reflections and observations support the assessment of this objective.</p>
<p><i>Argumentation and fostering of maker culture:</i></p>	<p>Practicing communication skills in terms of formulating and expressing ideas. We encourage curiosity, tinkering and desire to test ideas. The games requires the decision-making process within a team. Identifying and solving problems skills. Proportional reasoning is also stimulated as children have to think in proportion to solve the mathematical tasks while visualizing the solution both on the screen by programing, as well as on a physical level with the robot.</p>	<p>Group discussions and interviews, alongside with photos and videos are used to record children's attitude and productions. All forms of evaluation, applied within the ER4STEM projects are further relevant for measuring this objective. Tutor reflections and observations support the assessment of this objective.</p>

REGARDING RESEARCH QUESTIONS AND TOOL FOR ASSESSMENT

<p>Research Question</p>	<p>Assessment Method or Tool</p>
<p>Are popular gender stereotypes about STEM held?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Draw a scientist (if applicable) • Pre-Questionnaire • Post-Questionnaire • Interviews • Team Reflections • Tutor Observations & Reflections
<p>Past experience and existing attitudes to STEM subjects and careers</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pre-questionnaire • Interviews • Team Reflections
<p>Past experience and existing attitudes to STEM subjects and careers</p> <p>Includes questions about the activities to help understand learners' experiences of the workshop as a whole, what participants feel they have learned and what their future</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pre-Questionnaire • Post-Questionnaire • Interviews • Team Reflections

intentions are	
Understand the experience of participants and their reasons for particular actions	<ul style="list-style-type: none">● Post-Questionnaire● Interviews● Team Reflections● Tutor Observations & Reflections

ER4STEM Workshops – Robot-video (Elementary)

AUTHORS:

Patrik Harner, Julian Angel-Fernandez, Johannes Pagitsch (TUWien)

SHORT DESCRIPTION OF THE ACTIVITY (SUMMARY)

As a result of the workshop the children should have made a video where robots function as actors. The video should have been developed by working on the following steps: Develop a screenplay to a given story and make a video (arts) in the given time and with the available resources (business). Design the robot and the image background in an appropriate way (arts). Program the robot's behaviour (engineering) and use as many of the robot's functions as possible (technology).

FOCUS, SET UP AND REQUIREMENTS OF THE ACTIVITY

CURRICULUM

Select NO if the scenario is not aligned with the curriculum of your country and YES if it is. Please mention the relevant subject matter.

NO YES Subject:

CONTENT

Choose categories and give a rating of the level of emphasis on concepts from each of the following domains

<input type="checkbox"/> Science	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Technology	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Business	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Engineering	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Arts	<input type="checkbox"/> Mathematics
(0-10)	(0-10)	(0-10)	(0-10)	(0-10)	(0-10)
0	10	5	6	4	0

OBJECTIVES

<i>Technology related</i>	Use of Thymio robot, proper employment of its functions, use of a camera
Business related	Making the video with a given amount of time and resources (e.g., number of cameras, robots, time when camera is available).
Engineering related	Solving several problems given through specific constraints concerning the video. Problems might be solved by programming the robot(s) in an appropriate way. Example: Little human interaction (hands etc.) should be visible in the video. The robot has to act on its own after for instance pushing button.
Arts related	Telling a story in a video, developing a design for the robot with respect to the story

Further: Social skills	School classes are split up into groups. Each group has its own area of responsibility (design, programming etc.). The children are told to collaborate and organize the necessary exchange of information on their own.
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TIME

Duration: 6 hours

Schedule: 2 workshop parts with a duration of 3 hours each

MATERIALS AND ARTIFACTS

<i>Digital artifact</i>	Source code, videos, presentations
<i>Student's workbook and manual</i>	Videos to describe the task (part 1), story and constraints (part 2), template for presentation

STUDENTS AND SPACE

STUDENTS (TARGET AUDIENCE)

<i>Sex and Age:</i>	boys & girls, 6-10 years old
<i>Prior knowledge:</i>	No prior knowledge required
<i>Nationality and cultural background</i>	Mostly Austrian, cultural background diverse, capital city and surrounding
<i>Social status and social environment</i>	mainstream public elementary school
<i>Special needs and abilities</i>	Some students are deaf

SPACE INFO

Organizational and cultural context: Workshops take place at the university. During regular school time.

Physical characteristics: indoors

SOCIAL ORCHESTRATION

POPULATION

Students: 10-27

Tutors: 2 (+teacher and parents)

GROUPING:

Grouping criteria	preference of subject (engineering and technology, arts and design, organization and leadership)
<i>Setting:</i>	Class is split up into two groups who are again split up into at least four subgroups with different responsibilities: two subgroups are responsible for the technical part (i.e., programming the robots), one subgroup is responsible for the design (robot and image background)

	and one subgroup is responsible for maintaining collaboration.
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INTERACTION DURING THE ACTIVITY (EMPHASIS)

Actions	Result oriented, solution oriented
<i>Relationships</i>	Collaborative
<i>Roles in the group</i>	emergent roles
<i>Support by the tutor(s)</i>	facilitate

LEARNING PROCEDURES

EXPECTED STUDENT ACTIVITY

In general the workshop consist of two parts:

In the first part the children are taught the basic concepts needed to make the robot-video. In this part we concentrate on technical skills as these also require some time to practice which is not available in the video development process. Furthermore, it is important that all children (not only those who belong to the engineer-groups in part 2) know the robot's functions and possibilities. Otherwise it would never be possible to come to a result. The teaching method is rather instructive in this part: The groups get exercises that have to be solved. Collaboration is not very important here, the focus lies on 21st century skills as creativity and critical thinking.

In the second part we concentrate on the video itself. The focus lies on the teaching of creative skills and the children should develop the necessary design concepts on their own (learning by doing). As in the first part the acquisition of knowledge has the highest priority, in the second part the usage of this knowledge is the most important thing. In contrast to part 1, the teaching method itself is rather constructive in this part. This allows us to evaluate the influence of different pedagogic strategies on the effect of learning. The groups get a story and some constraints (e.g., time- and resource related) and have to develop a concept to make a video on their own. As at least four groups work together to make one video, 21st century skills as collaboration, teamwork and communication are demanded. Without these skills it will not be possible to come to a result.

STUDENT LEARNING PROCESSES

<i>Designed Conflicts and misconceptions</i>	No, the activity is well documented
<i>Learning processes emphasized:</i>	Emphasis on robot behavior and small exercises
<i>Expected relevance of alternative knowledge</i>	No alternative knowledge used/needed

"HOW TO" IN THE CLASSROOM

Exercise Tasks can be started individually from the groups, as soon as the previous task has been solved.

PHASE 1: KNOWLEDGE/SKILLS ACQUISITION

Duration: 180 min

Anonymization, group-building, pre-questionnaire (duration: app. 30 min)

Exercise 1: Push buttons (app. 25 min)

In this exercise the children should learn how to use the robot's push buttons. A program should be written to let Thymio react on specific push-button events.

Exercise 2: Horizontal sensors (app. 25 min)

This exercise should give the children a feeling for the use of the horizontal sensors. The robot should drive forwards if there was an obstacle behind it and backwards if there was an obstacle in front of it.

Exercise 3: See a line (app. 15 min)

This exercise focuses on the use of the ground sensors. The sensors should detect a black line on the ground and the robot should react to it.

Exercise 4: Tap me (app. 15 min)

The robot should move and if he is tapped he should take some action like driving in the opposite direction or stop etc.

Exercise 5: Timer (app. 10 min)

The robot should move for a given time and then take some action like changing direction or stopping.

Exercise 6: Accident (app. 15 min)

In this exercise, the children are introduced to the G-sensor. The robot therefore is going to drive up a cardboard ramp. When the programmed angle of the robot is reached, the robot should stop.

Exercise 7: Open challenge (app. 20 min)

This exercise is a direct preparation for part 2. Thymio should execute different sequences of actions after different buttons are pushed. The sequences of actions are not predefined – the children can choose them on their own.

Note: As we work with 6-10 year old children, we will also make 2-3 breaks of about 10-15 minutes during workshop part 1.

PHASE 2: MAKING A VIDEO

Duration: 180 min

Group splitting, handing out the stories for the videos (duration app. 10 min)

We are going to hand out the task descriptions (these are the stories and the constraints) in two different ways: For some groups, every subgroup gets the task description, for other groups, only the director-subgroup gets the task description. In the second case, teamwork and collaboration is really forced as only one group has the necessary information. In the first case it is more or less a free decision. The goal is to see which method provides a better learning effect.

Self-initiated preparation of the video (duration app. 105 min)

The stories are written in a way that it is necessary to use the knowledge gained in exercises 1-7 for the implementation of the video. The following constraints are additionally given:

- The video may not last longer than one minute and it has to last at least 40 seconds. This constraint requires a big amount of organizational and business-related skills. There are several important issues that have to be regarded to fulfill the constraint (e.g., how fast the robots may drive, how many actions generally may be done)
- The camera is only available in a certain time interval of 15 minutes. This requires a thorough preparation of the robots and of the environment where the video takes place. Furthermore the constraint makes it necessary to do some test runs of the video beforehand. Again, organizational skills are required.
- The video has to include two robots that are programmed by different subgroups. This usually requires collaboration and teamwork.
- There may be as little human intervention as possible visible in the video (e.g., hands). Especially exercises 3, 5 and 7 and some creativity are required here.

Shooting (duration at most 15 min)

Preparation of a presentation (duration app. 20 min)

The children should prepare a short presentation where they reflect about their experiences and point out the problems they had. Therefore, they will get a template for a slideshow. The template will include some with questions to be answered. This should help us to find out some things about the children's attitudes to STEM (e.g., if they changed or sustained during the workshop) and to collect some evidence of learning.

Presentation (duration app. 2x5 min)

The children present their video and the presentation they made in the previous point.

Post-Questionnaire (duration app. 15 min)

ASSESSMENT PROCEDURES

Making a video in the second part of the workshop is kind of an assessment to see what the kids have learned and if they understood how to combine the skills of the robot.

ER4STEM Workshops – Robot-video (Advanced)

AUTHORS:

Patrik Harner, Julian Angel-Fernandez, Johannes Pagitsch (TUWien)

SHORT DESCRIPTION OF THE ACTIVITY (SUMMARY)

As a result of the workshop the children should have made a video where robots function as actors. The video should have been developed by working on the following steps: Develop a screenplay to a given story and make a video (arts) in the given time and with the available resources (business). Design the robot and the image background in an appropriate way (arts). Program the robot's behaviour (engineering) and use as many of the robot's functions as possible (technology).

FOCUS, SET UP AND REQUIREMENTS OF THE ACTIVITY

CURRICULUM

Select NO if the scenario is not aligned with the curriculum of your country and YES if it is. Please mention the relevant subject matter.

NO YES Subject:

CONTENT

Choose categories and give a rating of the level of emphasis on concepts from each of the following domains

<input type="checkbox"/> Science	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Technology	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Business	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Engineering	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Arts	<input type="checkbox"/> Mathematics
(0-10)	(0-10)	(0-10)	(0-10)	(0-10)	(0-10)
0	10	5	6	4	0

OBJECTIVES

Technology related	Use of Thymio robot, proper employment of its functions, use of a camera
Business related	Making the video with a given amount of time and resources (e.g., number of cameras, robots, time when camera is available).
Engineering related	Solving several problems given through specific constraints concerning the video. Problems might be solved by programming the robot(s) in an appropriate way. Example: no human interaction (hands etc.) should be visible in the video. ; a possible solution would be to use and program some robots as remote controllers.
Arts related	Telling a story in a video, developing a design for the robot with respect to the story

Further: Social skills	School classes are split up into groups. Each group has its own area of responsibility (design, programming etc.). The children are told to collaborate and organize the necessary exchange of information on their own.
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TIME

Duration: 6 hours

Schedule: 2 workshop parts with a duration of 3 hours each

MATERIALS AND ARTIFACTS

<i>Digital artifact</i>	Source code, videos, presentations
<i>Student's workbook and manual</i>	Textual description of the tasks (part 1), story and constraints (part 2), template for presentation

STUDENTS AND SPACE

STUDENTS (TARGET AUDIENCE)

<i>Sex and Age:</i>	boys & girls, 14-18 years old
<i>Prior knowledge:</i>	Fundamentals of how to program Thymio robot are required
<i>Nationality and cultural background</i>	Mostly Austrian, cultural background diverse, capital city and surrounding
<i>Social status and social environment</i>	mainstream public school
<i>Special needs and abilities</i>	-

SPACE INFO

Organizational and cultural context: Workshops take place at the university. During regular school time.

Physical characteristics: indoors

SOCIAL ORCHESTRATION

POPULATION

Students: 10-27

Tutors: 2 (+teacher and parents)

GROUPING:

Grouping criteria	preference of subject (engineering and technology, arts and design, organization and leadership)
<i>Setting:</i>	Class is split up into two groups who are again split up into at least four subgroups with different responsibilities: two subgroups are responsible for the technical part (i.e., programming the robots), one

	subgroup is responsible for the design (robot and image background) and one subgroup is responsible for maintaining collaboration.
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INTERACTION DURING THE ACTIVITY (EMPHASIS)

Actions	Result oriented, solution oriented
Relationships	Collaborative
Roles in the group	emergent roles
Support by the tutor(s)	facilitate

LEARNING PROCEDURES

EXPECTED STUDENT ACTIVITY

In general the workshop consist of two parts:

In the first part the children are taught the basic concepts needed to make the robot-video. In this part we concentrate on technical skills as these also require some time to practice which is not available in the video development process. Furthermore, it is important that all children (not only those who belong to the engineer-groups in part 2) know the robot's functions and possibilities. Otherwise it would never be possible to come to a result. The teaching method is rather instructive in this part: The groups get exercises that have to be solved. Collaboration is not very important here, the focus lies on 21st century skills as creativity and critical thinking.

In the second part we concentrate on the video itself. The focus lies on the teaching of creative skills and the children should develop the necessary design concepts on their own (learning by doing). As in the first part the acquisition of knowledge has the highest priority, in the second part the usage of this knowledge is the most important thing. In contrast to part 1, the teaching method itself is rather constructive in this part. This allows us to evaluate the influence of different pedagogic strategies on the effect of learning. The groups get a story and some constraints (e.g., time- and resource related) and have to develop a concept to make a video on their own. As at least four groups work together to make one video, 21st century skills as collaboration, teamwork and communication are demanded. Without these skills it will not be possible to come to a result.

STUDENT LEARNING PROCESSES

<i>Designed Conflicts and misconceptions</i>	No, the activity is well documented
<i>Learning processes emphasized:</i>	Emphasis on robot behavior and small exercises
<i>Expected relevance of alternative knowledge</i>	No alternative knowledge used/needed

"HOW TO" IN THE CLASSROOM

Exercise Tasks can be started individually from the groups, as soon as the previous task has been solved.

PHASE 1: KNOWLEDGE/SKILLS ACQUISITION

Duration: 180 min

Anonymization, group-building, pre-questionnaire (duration: app. 30 min)**Exercise 1 – Measurements with Thymio** (duration: app. 30 min)

In this exercise the children get to know the very basics of robotic: They learn that a robot can perceive its environment only through sensors that deliver a numeric value. A robot cannot interpret its environment on its own. The interpretation of the values is the programmer's issue. To get a feeling for this matter, the children should use some of the robot's sensors to do some measurements.

Exercise 2 – Drive through maze(duration: app. 20 min)

In this exercise, the children are taught one basic concept of programming, namely sequential programming. Therefore they have to lead the robot through a maze step by step. A program framework which contains the basic steps is delivered to them.

Exercise 3 – Start stop event (duration: app. 20 min)

In this exercise, the second important concept of programming robots should be learned, namely event-based programming. I.e., the robot reacts autonomously on a special event which is triggered by one of its internal functions (e.g., timer) or by one of its sensors. The children should use the five push buttons to trigger an event. The push buttons should be used to move the robot in all directions.

Break (duration: 20 min)

Exercise 4 – Stop at table edge (duration: app. 15 min)

This exercise deepens the knowledge that was gained in the previous exercise. Again, the robot should act autonomously. Its sensors should be used to detect the edge of a table – the robot must not fall down.

Exercise 5 – Avoid obstacles(duration: app. 30 min)

This exercise requires a combination of the different functions of the robot the children had to deal with in the previous exercises. The robot should detect any obstacle in front of it and must not crash into it. As a second step, some groups should try to extend their program in a way that it even works with more than one robot. Therefore the dynamics of the programming have to be enlarged

Exercise 6 – Reach point (duration: app. 15 min)

One of the robot's internal functions is a timer. This exercise explains how a timer works and what it can be used for. By writing an appropriate program, the children can experience the use of a timer on their own.

Extra Exercise (not mandatory; in the case the children perform well and finish to early):

An exercise from the workshop for children with prior knowledge can be used as extra exercise.

PHASE 2: MAKING A VIDEO

Duration: 180 min

Group splitting, handing out the stories for the videos (duration app. 5 min)

We are going to hand out the task descriptions (these are the stories and the constraints) in two different ways: For some groups, every subgroup gets the task description, for other groups, only the director-subgroup gets the task description. In the second case, **teamwork and collaboration** is

really forced as only one group has the necessary information. In the first case it is more or less a free decision. The goal is to see which method provides a better learning effect.

Self-initiated preparation of the video (duration app. 110 min)

The stories are written in a way that it is advisable to use the knowledge gained in exercises 1, 2, 3, 4, 5 and 6 for the implementation of the video. The following constraints are additionally given:

- The video may not last longer than one minute and it has to last at least 40 seconds. This constraint requires a big amount of **organizational and business-related skills**. There are several important issues that have to be regarded to fulfill the constraint (e.g., how fast the robots may drive, how many actions generally may be done)
- The camera is only available in a certain time interval of 10 minutes. This requires a thorough preparation of the robots and of the environment where the video takes place. Furthermore the constraint makes it necessary to do some test runs of the video beforehand. Again, **organizational skills** are required.
- The video has to include two robots that are programmed by different subgroups. This usually requires **collaboration and teamwork**.
- There must not be too much human intervention be visible in the video (e.g., hands). Especially exercises 4,5 and 6 and some **creativity** are required here.

Shooting (duration at most 10 min)

Preparation of a presentation (duration app. 30 min)

The children should prepare a short presentation where they reflect about their experiences and point out the problems they had. Therefore, they will get a template for a slideshow. The template will include some with questions to be answered. This should help us to find out some things about the children's **attitudes to STEM** (if they changed or sustained during the workshop) and to collect some **evidence of learning**.

Presentation (duration app. 2x5 min)

The children present their video and the presentation they made in the previous point.

Post-Questionnaire (duration app. 15 min)

ASSESSMENT PROCEDURES

Making a video in the second part of the workshop is kind of an assessment to see what the kids have learned and if they understood how to combine the skills of the robot.

Identification and avoidance (bypassing) of obstacles

AUTHOR:

Dimitris Diamantidis (UoA)

SHORT DESCRIPTION OF THE ACTIVITY (SUMMARY)

Students firstly make their own LEGO NXT robots. They will work in groups of three. They shall built the robot, with three wheels, following specific steps. Then they have to put on an ultrasonic sensor, taking initiative in the design of the robot, without having any instructions to follow.

The next step is to make the robot ho straight ahead and then turn right. This is an introductory activity to the main challenge which is to make the robot recognize the empty space between two obstacles. Then the robot shall move between the obstacles, simulating a “parking” procedure.

FOCUS, SET UP AND REQUIREMENTS OF THE ACTIVITY

CURRICULUM

NO YES Subject: Mathematics\Proportional amounts, Circle characteristics and circumference, algorithmic thinking.

CONTENT

Choose categories and give a rating of the level of emphasis on concepts from each of the following domains

<input type="checkbox"/> Science	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Technology	<input type="checkbox"/> Business	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Engineering	<input type="checkbox"/> Arts	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Mathematics
(0-10)	(0-10)	(0-10)	(0-10)	(0-10)	(0-10)
0	10	0	5	0	7

OBJECTIVES

<i>Subject related</i>	Study a turn of a robot based on time, or on rotations of the wheel. Choose the best measure to achieve the goal. Program the ultrasonic sensor.
<i>Technology use related</i>	Programming with LEGO NXT in LEGO programming environment
<i>Social and action related</i>	Develop collaborative skills, take roles within groups, communicate with other groups to exchange ideas and tips, compare strategies and artefacts
<i>Argumentation and fostering of maker culture:</i>	Students make and test hypotheses in practice about the robot actions based on their own program, make assumptions, test possible solutions, trying to develop their strategy in

	order to achieve the best solution.
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TIME

Duration: e.g. 2 weeks

Schedule: e.g. 4 hours per week

MATERIALS AND ARTIFACTS

<i>Digital artifact</i>	Lego EV3 programming environment
<i>Robotic artifact</i>	LEGO NXT – ‘a simple vehicle’
<i>Student’s workbook and manual</i>	Manual with step-by-step instructions for building the robot.
<i>Teacher’s instruction book and manual:</i>	Five stages.

STUDENTS AND SPACE

STUDENTS (TARGET AUDIENCE)

<i>Sex and Age:</i>	boys & girls, 12-15 years old
<i>Prior knowledge:</i>	Not any knowledge on robotics & programming
<i>Nationality and cultural background</i>	All pupils are from Greece
<i>Social status and social environment</i>	public experimental school
<i>Special needs and abilities</i>	Lego programming environment is in English. English is not native language for participants

SPACE INFO

Organizational and cultural context: After school activity, during the courses of the Mathematics Club – in the school PC Lab.

Physical characteristics: indoors

SOCIAL ORCHESTRATION

POPULATION

Students: 15

Tutors: 2 Assistants: 0

GROUPING:

Grouping criteria	Students that have worked together as a team during Math Club’s activities this year – students preferences.
<i>Setting:</i>	Students in groups of three (3), around tables with a desktop and a robot available for them in each group.

INTERACTION DURING THE ACTIVITY (EMPHASIS)

Actions	Exchange ideas, dialogue, negotiation
Relationships	Collaborative
Roles in the group	emergent roles
Support by the tutor(s)	Facilitate – participant observer

LEARNING PROCEDURES

EXPECTED STUDENT ACTIVITY

Students during the activity are expected to engage in the following actions: construct, observe, collaborate, experiment with their constructions, reflect on and elaborate their artefacts, communicate, exchange ideas.

STUDENT LEARNING PROCESSES

<i>Designed Conflicts and misconceptions</i>	Do the activity designers do not wish to bring students in conflict with mistaken conceptions documented in educational research or their teaching practice.
<i>Learning processes emphasized:</i>	Emphasis on analyzing robot behavior using related measurements and experimentation in order to refine and reflect on the code that defines this behavior
<i>Expected relevance of alternative knowledge</i>	Students are expected to investigate the structure of mechanisms that use contemporary technological achievements, like auto-parking of a car, or distance-sensors.

“HOW TO” IN THE CLASSROOM

In this section of the activity plan we describe how we expect the teaching and the learning process to evolve. We might use phases or activities for this description. The phases or activities should support the objectives stated and make use of the materials, tools and teaching and learning processes mentioned earlier in the activity plan. Next we provide an example of phase description

PHASE 1: INTRODUCTION AND EXPERIMENTATION

Duration: 2 teaching hours

Orchestration: group work in groups of 3

Description: The groups are assembling their robots, following instructions, clearly described on an online manual. The final stage of the construction (placing the ultrasonic sensor) is totally open for the pupils to decide which way to do it. After that, we demonstrate to them which way to program the robot.

Expected student constructions: A Lego NXT simple vehicle

Expected forms of student dialogue: Arguing on which are the right parts of the robot to use and how to put the sensor on the robot.

Teaching method: Demonstration by example, discussion, experimentation.

PHASE 2: SEQUENTIAL PROGRAMMING

Duration: 2 hours

Orchestration: group work

Description: Students implement their first programs that have programming blocks in a row. No loops or selection structures are needed. The first program should move the robot on a predefined path on the floor. The path contains a turn at the end of it. Students use the robots they have just assembled.

Indicate which of the stated objectives are supported by this phase

Expected student constructions: A simple program by each group

Expected forms of student dialogue: Argumentation of possible of their program, after testing it on the floor.

Teaching method: Demonstration by example, discussion, experimentation

PHASE 3: USING LOOPS

Duration: 2 hours

Orchestration: group work

Description: The main goal for the students is to create a new program in order to make the robot recognize obstacles. Then it should change its path, avoiding them. With teacher assistance, students recognize the usage, the conditions and the characteristics of the new programming structure (loop) and also the role of the sensors in executing a loop block.

Indicate which of the stated objectives are supported by this phase

Expected student constructions: A new program using loops.

Expected forms of student dialogue: Discussion on the way that the loops must be used, in order to make the program work

Teaching method: Demonstration by example, discussion, experimentation.

PHASE 4: GIVING “SMART” BEHAVIOR: THE USAGE OF SELECTION/SWITCH BLOCKS

Duration: 2 hours

Orchestration: group work

Description: A most difficult and challenging task for the students is to make the robot park automatically between two obstacles. In this case, the robot should not only avoid the obstacle, but follow a more specific track, after avoiding it. After that the robot has to stop. This makes the program even more challenging.

Indicate which of the stated objectives are supported by this phase

Expected student constructions: A more sophisticated way of using the loops.

Expected forms of student dialogue: Discussion on the way that the loops must be used, in order to make the program work

Teaching method: Demonstration by example, discussion, experimentation

PHASE 5: FEEDBACK AND EVALUATION

Duration: 30 minutes

Orchestration: individual and class work

Description: In addition with the activity sheets that students complete during activity phases, finally they discuss in classroom the difficulties, the different solutions, the limitations that may have found in every step. They also fill in an evaluation questionnaire and teacher gets short informal open interviews from students that want to share their experience.

Indicate which of the stated objectives are supported by this phase

Expected student constructions

Expected forms of student dialogue:

Teaching method: (Instruction, demonstration by example, discussion, experimentation)

Robots for sustainability

AUTHOR:

Giannis Baras (Teacher – UoA)

SHORT DESCRIPTION OF THE ACTIVITY (SUMMARY)

The challenge we have chosen is the construction of robots which will help in sustainable development. This issue is inspired from the contest of World Robot Olympiad 2017. Students must build a robot that solves various missions. All missions are aimed at reducing carbon emissions. The robot has three missions. Students will be divided into 5 groups. Groups 1-2, and 2-3 will take joint missions to be resolved, whereas group 5 (case study group) will take one mission itself. In each group there will be a student - link with other groups. The role of the the studentl - link is to communicate with the other groups. The solutions which the groups will develop, should be a solution that can easily be adapted to the solutions of other teams for different mission.

In order to achieve this, there should be at appropriate times discussion and exchange between all groups. Students should work within the team, but teams should work together.

At the end the groups will decide which will be the combination of the solutions for the robot construction to solve different missions. As a result we get a robot which solves as much more mission can. The robot will be a synthesis solutions of all five groups (through cooperation between groups).

FOCUS, SET UP AND REQUIREMENTS OF THE ACTIVITY

CURRICULUM

Select NO if the scenario is not aligned with the curriculum of your country and YES if it is. Please mention the relevant subject matter.

NO YES Subject: Programming, Technology, Science

CONTENT

Choose categories and give a rating of the level of emphasis on concepts from each of the following domains

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Science	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Technology	<input type="checkbox"/> Business	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Engineering	<input type="checkbox"/> Arts	<input type="checkbox"/> Mathematics
(0-10)	(0-10)	(0-10)	(0-10)	(0-10)	(0-10)
4	8	0	10	0	0

OBJECTIVES

<i>Subject related</i>	Construction of a robot in order to solve different tasks (specially use of grabber)
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	mechanism and line follow techniques)
<i>Technology use related</i>	LEGO EV3 programming environment
<i>Social and action related</i>	Develop collaborative skills, take roles within groups, communicate with other groups to exchange ideas and tips, advice, analysis and synthesis of solutions
<i>Argumentation and fostering of maker culture:</i>	test possible solutions, choose the best solution, communicate with other “makers”, collaborate with others “makers”, decision taking, brainstorming

TIME

Duration: 6 hours (total to take place in two 2 Days)

Schedule: 3 hours per day

MATERIALS AND ARTIFACTS

<i>Digital artifact</i>	programming language (Lego EV3 programming environment)
<i>Robotic artifact</i>	Basic EV3 construction
<i>Student’s workbook and manual</i>	Step by step direction to build a simple (but not suitable) grabber
<i>Teacher’s instruction book and manual:</i>	Presentation of the missions (ppt), notes

STUDENTS AND SPACE

STUDENTS (TARGET AUDIENCE)

<i>Sex and Age:</i>	14 boys, 1 girl, 12-16 year old
<i>Prior knowledge:</i>	3 experts (participated in robotic Olympiads, 11 medium knowledge, 1 amateur
<i>Nationality and cultural background</i>	All from Greece
<i>Social status and social environment</i>	mainstream public school
<i>Special needs and abilities</i>	-

SPACE INFO

Organizational and cultural context: After school, at STEM Robotics Academy (non profit organization)

Physical characteristics: indoors

SOCIAL ORCHESTRATION

POPULATION

Students: 15

Tutors: 1; **Assistants:-**

GROUPING:

Grouping criteria	mixed ability (one programmer, one constructor, one leader)
Setting:	students in front of computers with one lego EV3 kit available for each group

INTERACTION DURING THE ACTIVITY (EMPHASIS)

Actions	Exchange ideas, dialogue, negotiation, debate, Brainstorming, decision making
Relationships	Collaborative
Roles in the group	pre-defined roles
Support by the tutor(s)	mentor

LEARNING PROCEDURES**EXPECTED STUDENT ACTIVITY**

Students during the activity are expected to engage in the following actions: construct, communicate, create, exchange ideas, collaborate, take decisions

STUDENT LEARNING PROCESSES

<i>Designed Conflicts and misconceptions</i>	Develop a solution as part of a bigger mission
<i>Learning processes emphasized:</i>	emphasis on designing sub-systems that can be part of a greater system. In order to do that, the group must collaborate and synthesis solutions
<i>Expected relevance of alternative knowledge</i>	Students should understand the importance of sustainable development (science)

“HOW TO” IN THE CLASSROOM

In this section of the activity plan we describe how we expect the teaching and the learning process to evolve. We might use phases or activities for this description. The phases or activities should support the objectives stated and make use of the materials, tools and teaching and learning processes mentioned earlier in the activity plan. Next we provide an example of phase description

PHASE 1: INTRODUCTION

Duration: 10 minute

Orchestration: presentation

Description: The theme is presented to the students

Teaching method: presentation

PHASE 2: BRAINSTORMING

Duration:20 minute

Orchestration: group work

Description: Students are trying all together to find solution to the problem. The leaders of each group must agree to additional development solutions to each other.

Indicate which of the stated objectives are supported by this phase: Brainstorming, Collaboration

Expected forms of student dialogue: exchange ideas, present thinkings, decision making

Teaching method: monitor,

PHASE 3: CONSTRUCTING

Duration: 2 hours

Orchestration: group work

Description: The groups are trying to find solutions to the problem undertaken. The leader students then communicate with other groups to report progress and to see if the final solutions can be combined.

Indicate which of the stated objectives are supported by this phase: Collaboration, creativity

Expected student constructions : Primary construction of a vehicle in capable of solving one missions of the task, but also it can combine other solution from other teams.

Teaching method: monitor, answering questions

PHASE 4: ANALYSIS, EVALUATION, EXCHANGE OF VIEWS

Duration: 15 minutes

Orchestration: all groups work

Description: All groups present their work so far. Become valuation of construction so far, reported problems, cautions, checking whether the solutions can be combined. Solutions by teams who have encountered problems are reported, strategic decisions are taking for the next stage of construction.

Indicate which of the stated objectives are supported by this phase : Collaboration, decision making, creative thinking, analysis of a problem, problem solving

Expected forms of student dialogue: reporting, argument

Teaching method: guiding, mentoring

PHASE 5: SECOND PHASE OF CONSTRUCTION

Duration: 2 HOURS

Orchestration: group work

Description: After evaluation of the work so far, the exchange of ideas and decision-making, starts the second phase of construction according to the new data.

Now must cooperate in order to modify their solution and try to construct a vehicle to solve as many mission is possible.

Indicate which of the stated objectives are supported by this phase: Collaboration, creativity

Expected student constructions : Finally construction of a vehicle in capable of solving the missions of the task.

Expected forms of student dialogue:

Teaching method: (Instruction, demonstration by example, discussion, experimentation)

PHASE 6: TESTING THE FINAL ROBOTIC VEHICLES AND TAKING FEEDBACK

Duration: 30 minutes

Orchestration: group work

Description: The structures tested so that students check that there are problems and try to improve structures. We have feedback of the initial thoughts and decisions of brainstorming phase, understanding Conflicts and misconceptions in initial plans. Students try to understand what succeeded and what failed and why.

Expected forms of student dialogue: exchange ideas, valuation

Teaching method: mentor

ASSESSMENT PROCEDURES

- Presentation of the theme (pdf)
- Brainstorming (using an inspiring video)
- Construction
- meeting and exchanging new ideas
- 2nd phase of construction
- Feedback and evaluation

SLurtles Introduction & Orientation

AUTHOR:

Dr Carina Girvan (Cardiff University) in collaboration with Mr Adam Speight (Mary Immaculate High School, Cardiff. Wales)

SHORT DESCRIPTION OF THE ACTIVITY (SUMMARY)

This activity introduces students to SLurtles (robot), Scratch for OpenSim (programming tool) and the virtual world (Slurtle World), familiarising them with the technology through guided discovery. Following open exploration of the virtual world and SLurtles to familiarise students with basic controls, students engage in a series of short directed tasks which progressively develop into more open ended activities to develop their familiarity with using and controlling SLurtles by programming them. These activities are based on existing mathematical knowledge (properties of shapes) and provide an opportunity to explore the programming environment.

FOCUS, SET UP AND REQUIREMENTS OF THE ACTIVITY

CURRICULUM

Subject: Computer Science & ICT

Curriculum:

CONTENT

Choose categories and give a rating of the level of emphasis on concepts from each of the following domains

<input type="checkbox"/> Science	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Technology	<input type="checkbox"/> Business	<input type="checkbox"/> Engineering	<input type="checkbox"/> Arts	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Mathematics
(0-10)	(0-10)	(0-10)	(0-10)	(0-10)	(0-10)
0	10	0	0	0	3

OBJECTIVES

<i>Subject related</i>	Moving between multiple applications Demonstrate knowledge of the properties of shapes.
<i>Technology use related</i>	Develop an understanding of what a virtual world is, how to move and interact within it. Programming with a graphical environment

	(Scratch for OpenSim) Reflection tool
<i>Social and action related</i>	Develop an awareness of how to communicate with others in a virtual world. Develop written communication skills. Communicating with others.
<i>Argumentation and fostering of maker culture:</i>	Application of mathematical knowledge to solve problems. Awareness that there are multiple ways to solve a given problem. Reflection for learning.

TIME

Duration: 3 weeks

Schedule: 2 hours per week

MATERIALS AND ARTIFACTS

<i>Digital artefact</i>	Programming interface - Scratch for OpenSim. Virtual world – Slurtle World (internal access only) Robot – Slurtles (cuboids) Reflection tool
<i>Robotic artefact</i>	SLurtles: Programmable turtle in a virtual world which creates cuboids
<i>Student’s workbook and manual</i>	Virtual world orientation guide and scavenger hunt.
<i>Teacher’s instruction book and manual:</i>	This activity plan

STUDENTS AND SPACE

STUDENTS (TARGET AUDIENCE)

<i>Sex and Age:</i>	Boys and girls; 11-12 years old
<i>Prior knowledge:</i>	No relevant prior programming knowledge expected. Knowledge of angles and 2D shapes.
<i>Nationality and cultural background</i>	Welsh
<i>Social status and social environment</i>	Lower-socio economic group
<i>Special needs and abilities</i>	Higher ability group within year. English as a Second Language

SPACE INFO

Organizational and cultural context: In school computer lab, part of scheduled lessons.

Physical characteristics: Desktop computers on fixed desks with an internal and external horseshoe arrangement.

Virtual World: Shared orientation island with directed tasks and spaces to explore. From this island the class island can be accessed.

Class island: The class island has a standard structured space as an arrival point and a large construction space for learners to use. The construction space is unstructured, allowing learners to use any part of that space.

SOCIAL ORCHESTRATION

POPULATION

Students: 22

Tutors: 2 teachers: Class teacher and researcher

GROUPING:

Grouping criteria	Working individually at start. In matched ability pairs for problem solving with more able and talented leading learning.
<i>Setting:</i>	Students in classroom, as above.

INTERACTION DURING THE ACTIVITY (EMPHASIS)

<i>Actions</i>	Exchange ideas and share solutions.
<i>Relationships</i>	Independent and collaborative.
<i>Roles in the group</i>	Equal/emerging roles in pairs. Some more able and talented learners will be expected to lead the learning for the whole class (e.g. demonstrations).
<i>Support by the tutor(s)</i>	Facilitate, monitor and mentor.

LEARNING PROCEDURES

EXPECTED STUDENT ACTIVITY

Students during the activity are expected to engage in the following actions:

In world: explore, communicate, programme and create.

In classroom: communicate, present work and exchange ideas.

STUDENT LEARNING PROCESSES

<i>Designed Conflicts and misconceptions</i>	None planned as this is an introduction to the technology. Maths: Assumptions that the SLurtle turns through the internal angle.
<i>Learning processes emphasised:</i>	Emphasis on exploring the technology and potential of robots.
<i>Expected relevance of alternative knowledge</i>	Students are expected to know the properties of squares and triangles, and to apply this knowledge. If there are knowledge gaps the activity can be modified to provide an opportunity for individual students to discover the properties of these shapes through programming their robot.

“HOW TO” IN THE CLASSROOM

In this section of the activity plan we describe how we expect the teaching and the learning process to evolve. We might use phases or activities for this description. The phases or activities should support the objectives stated and make use of the materials, tools and teaching and learning processes mentioned earlier in the activity plan. Next we provide an example of phase description

PHASE 1: INTRODUCTION TO THE VIRTUAL WORLD

Duration: 1 hour in world (+ pre-inworld class to prepare)

Orchestration: Before the main lesson, the whole class is introduced to the virtual world before individually deciding on the name on their avatar's name. In the main lesson, students explore the virtual world individually.

Description: Children are introduced to the virtual world and provided with an opportunity to identify the type of avatar they would like to create, name the avatar and password. Between this pre-lesson activity and the main lesson, the teacher creates each of the avatars on the server, ready for the main lesson.

During the main lesson students log into the virtual world for the first time and are given the opportunity to freely explore or following a path around the island with guided orientation activities. To support this, students are given a physical guide to refer to and scavenger hunt activities to practice targeted skills (communication, flying, inventory use, camera tools).

Supported objectives: Develop an understanding of what a virtual world is, how to move and interact within it.

Expected student constructions: Avatar customisation

Expected forms of student dialogue: In class sharing and instruction.

Teaching method: Guided discovery and peer-teaching.

PHASE 2: INTRODUCTION TO SLURTLES – SANDBOXING AND SQUARES

Duration: 1 hour

Orchestration: Individual activities and peer teaching.

Description: Students are introduced to SLurtles and Scratch for OpenSim (S4OS) and given a series of simple directed tasks to gain familiarity with the tools and switching between programmes – programme the SLurtle to move, draw a line, draw a multi-coloured line.

Following this, students are given the challenge to programme the SLurtle to draw a square. Extension problems: 1) Explain why there is a gap at each of the external corners of the square. 2) Programme the SLurtle to draw a square without these gaps. 3) What's the minimum number of lines that this your programme could be written in?

Supported objectives: Moving between multiple applications; programming with a graphical environment (Scratch for OpenSim); demonstrate knowledge of the properties of shapes; communicating with others.

Expected student constructions: SLurtle constructed lines and squares.

Expected forms of student dialogue: In class sharing and instruction.

Teaching method: Demonstration, exploration, structured tasks and peer-teaching.

PHASE 3: COLLABORATING IN WORLD

Duration: 1 hour

Orchestration: Paired work

Description: Students are reminded about how to use the communication tools and how to communicate effectively in world. Students work in pairs to create different types of triangles before completing an individual reflection on what they have learnt so far.

Supported objectives: Moving between multiple applications; programming with a graphical environment (Scratch for OpenSim); demonstrate knowledge of the properties of shapes; communicating with others; develop an awareness of how to communicate with others in a virtual world; develop written communication skills; awareness that there are multiple ways to solve a given problem; reflection for learning.

Expected student constructions: Various triangles and individual reflections.

Expected forms of student dialogue: Cooperative

Teaching method: Demonstration, exploration and reflection.

PHASE 4: OPEN 2D CHALLENGE

Duration: 1.5 hours

Orchestration: Paired work

Description: As before but this time they move into the 3D to create a cube.

Supported objectives: Moving between multiple applications; programming with a graphical environment (Scratch for OpenSim); demonstrate knowledge of the properties of shapes; communicating with others; develop an awareness of how to communicate with others in a virtual world; develop written communication skills; awareness that there are multiple ways to solve a given problem; reflection for learning.

Expected student constructions: SLurtles that can create 3D cubes

Expected forms of student dialogue: Cooperative, discussion, argumentation

Teaching method: Exploration

PHASE 5: REFLECTION

Duration: 30 minutes

Orchestration: Individual and paired work

Description: This session focuses on reflecting on the experience, what has been learnt and planning for future. Students will have the opportunity to think and share ideas about how they could use SLurtles to create their own island. These ideas will be fed into the next workshop.

Supported objectives: communicating with others; develop written communication skills; awareness that there are multiple ways to solve a given problem; reflection for learning,

Expected student constructions: Reflection documents

Expected forms of student dialogue: Discussion through sharing and commenting on ideas.

Teaching method: Dialogic

ASSESSMENT PROCEDURES

Student record the code and construction as part of their reflections to demonstrate what they were able to programme the SLurtles to do.

SLurtles & Geometry 1

AUTHOR:

Dr Carina Girvan (Cardiff University, UK) in collaboration with Mr Neil Butler (North Wicklow Educate Together Secondary School, Ireland)

SHORT DESCRIPTION OF THE ACTIVITY (SUMMARY)

This activity introduces students to SLurtles (robot), Scratch for OpenSim (programming tool) and the virtual world (Slurtle World), familiarising them with the technology through guided discovery. Following open exploration of the virtual world and SLurtles to familiarise students with basic controls, students engage in a series of short directed tasks which progressively develop into more open ended activities as they develop their familiarity with using and controlling SLurtles by programming them. These activities begin by allowing students to apply existing knowledge of the properties of 2D and 3D shapes as they learn to control SLurtles and move on to students programming SLurtles to develop new knowledge about geometry and shapes.

FOCUS, SET UP AND REQUIREMENTS OF THE ACTIVITY

CURRICULUM

Subject: Mathematics

Curriculum:

CONTENT

Choose categories and give a rating of the level of emphasis on concepts from each of the following domains

<input type="checkbox"/> Science	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Technology	<input type="checkbox"/> Business	<input type="checkbox"/> Engineering	<input type="checkbox"/> Arts	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Mathematics
(0-10)	(0-10)	(0-10)	(0-10)	(0-10)	(0-10)
0	7	0	0	0	7

OBJECTIVES

<i>Subject related</i>	Apply knowledge of the properties of 2D and 3D shapes to new problems.
<i>Technology use related</i>	Develop an understanding of what a virtual world is, how to move and interact within it. Programming with a graphical environment (Scratch for OpenSim)

	<p>Moving between multiple applications.</p> <p>Recording and reflecting on learning with screen capture and OneNote.</p>
<i>Social and action related</i>	<p>Develop written communication skills.</p> <p>Working with others in small groups to solve a problem.</p> <p>Presenting incomplete solutions to others.</p>
<i>Argumentation and fostering of maker culture:</i>	<p>Application of mathematical knowledge to solve problems.</p> <p>Awareness that there are multiple ways to solve a given problem.</p> <p>Reflection for learning.</p>

TIME

Duration: 5 weeks

Schedule: 1 hour per week

MATERIALS AND ARTIFACTS

<i>Digital artefact</i>	<p>Programming interface - Scratch for OpenSim.</p> <p>Virtual world – SLurtle World (internal access only)</p> <p>Robot – SLurtles (cuboids)</p> <p>Reflection tool – OneNote</p>
<i>Robotic artefact</i>	<p>SLurtles: Programmable turtle in a virtual world which creates cuboids</p>
<i>Student’s workbook and manual</i>	<p>Virtual world orientation guide and scavenger hunt.</p> <p>Activity recording template for OneNote.</p> <p>Reflection template for OneNote.</p>
<i>Teacher’s instruction book and manual:</i>	<p>This activity plan</p>

STUDENTS AND SPACE

STUDENTS (TARGET AUDIENCE)

<i>Sex and Age:</i>	Boys and girls; 12-13 years old
<i>Prior knowledge:</i>	Properties of 2D and 3D shapes; programming in Scratch;
<i>Nationality and cultural background</i>	Irish
<i>Social status and social environment</i>	Roughly middle-class
<i>Special needs and abilities</i>	Dyslexia, deaf & autistic spectrum

SPACE INFO

Organizational and cultural context: In school mathematics lessons, part of scheduled lessons.

Physical characteristics: Flexible learning environment. Laptop computers, 1 per student. Movable individual desks allowing students to create shared working spaces.

Virtual World: Shared orientation island with directed tasks and spaces to explore. From this island the class island can be accessed.

Class island: The class island has a standard structured space as an arrival point and a large construction space for learners to use. The construction space is unstructured, allowing learners to use any part of that space.

SOCIAL ORCHESTRATION

POPULATION

Students: 20

Tutors: 2 teachers: Class teacher and researcher

GROUPING:

Grouping criteria	Working individually at start. In matched ability pairs for problem solving
<i>Setting:</i>	Students in classroom, as above.

INTERACTION DURING THE ACTIVITY (EMPHASIS)

Actions	Exchange ideas, discuss possible solutions to problems.
<i>Relationships</i>	Independent and collaborative.
<i>Roles in the group</i>	Equal/emerging roles in pairs.
<i>Support by the tutor(s)</i>	Facilitate, monitor and mentor.

LEARNING PROCEDURES

EXPECTED STUDENT ACTIVITY

Students during the activity are expected to engage in the following actions:

In world: explore, communicate, present work, programme and create.

In classroom: communicate, present work and exchange ideas.

STUDENT LEARNING PROCESSES

<i>Designed Conflicts and misconceptions</i>	That the SLurtle turns through the internal angle.
<i>Learning processes emphasised:</i>	Emphasis on discovering mathematical ideas through purposeful exploration.
<i>Expected relevance of alternative knowledge</i>	<p>Students are expected to know the properties of squares and cubes, and to apply this knowledge. If there are knowledge gaps the activity can be modified to provide an opportunity for individual students to discover the properties of these shapes through programming their robot.</p> <p>Students are expected to be familiar with drag-and-drop graphical programming environments.</p>

“HOW TO” IN THE CLASSROOM

In this section of the activity plan we describe how we expect the teaching and the learning process to evolve. We might use phases or activities for this description. The phases or activities should support the objectives stated and make use of the materials, tools and teaching and learning processes mentioned earlier in the activity plan. Next we provide an example of phase description

PHASE 1: INTRODUCTION TO THE VIRTUAL WORLD

Duration: 1 hour in world (+ pre-inworld class to prepare)

Orchestration: Before the main lesson, the whole class is introduced to the virtual world before individually deciding on the name on their avatar’s name. In the main lesson, students explore the virtual world individually.

Description: Children are introduced to the virtual world and provided with an opportunity to identify the type of avatar they would like to create, name the avatar and password. Between this pre-lesson activity and the main lesson, the teacher creates each of the avatars on the server, ready for the main lesson.

During the main lesson students log into the virtual world for the first time and are given the opportunity to freely explore or follow a path around the island with guided orientation activities. To support this, students are given a physical guide to refer to and scavenger hunt activities to practice targeted skills (communication, flying, inventory use, camera tools). They will also have a OneNote space to record their activities.

Supported objectives: Develop an understanding of what a virtual world is, how to move and interact within it; moving between multiple applications.

Expected student constructions: Avatar customisation; OneNote recording of activities.

Expected forms of student dialogue: In class sharing and instruction.

Teaching method: Guided discovery and peer-teaching.

PHASE 2: INTRODUCTION TO SLURTTLES – SANDBOXING AND SQUARES

Duration: 1 hour

Orchestration: Individual activities.

Description: Students are introduced to SLurttles and Scratch for OpenSim (S4OS) and given a series of simple directed tasks to gain familiarity with the tools and switching between programmes – programme the SLurttle to move, draw a line, draw a multi-coloured line.

Following this, students are given the challenge to programme the SLurttle to draw a square. Extension problems: 1) Explain why there is a gap at each of the external corners of the square. 2) Programme the SLurttle to draw a square without these gaps. 3) What’s the minimum number of lines that this programme could be written in? What does this tell us about squares?

As students complete tasks they complete the OneNote reporting template.

Supported objectives: Moving between multiple applications; programming with a graphical environment (Scratch for OpenSim); demonstrate knowledge of the properties of 2D shapes; communicating with others.

Expected student constructions: SLurtle constructed lines and squares; OneNote recording of outcomes.

Expected forms of student dialogue: In class sharing and instruction.

Teaching method: Demonstration, exploration, structured tasks and peer-teaching.

PHASE 3: DISCOVERING THE PROPERTIES OF SHAPES

Duration: 1 hour

Orchestration: Paired work

Description: In pairs, students are given the challenge to programme the SLurtle to draw the outline of a cube. There are several solutions to this problem and each provide an opportunity for students to develop their expression of mathematical ideas. Having completed this task, they use the OneNote recording and reflection tool to explain how they solved the problem, what knowledge they used to solve the problem and what they have learnt.

Extension: Programme the SLurtle to draw a parallelogram. This is a completely exploratory task after which students will report back to the class on what they did. Again they will use the OneNote recording and reflection tool to capture their problem solving process to share it with others.

Supported objectives: Apply knowledge of the properties of 2D and 3D shapes to new problems; Programming with a graphical environment (Scratch for OpenSim); moving between multiple applications; recording and reflecting on learning with screen capture and OneNote; develop written communication skills; working with others in small groups to solve a problem; presenting incomplete solutions; application of mathematical knowledge to solve problems; awareness that there are multiple ways to solve a given problem; reflection for learning.

Expected student constructions: Cubes and parallelograms; OneNote recording of and reflection on activities.

Expected forms of student dialogue: Idea generation, discussion, cooperative.

Teaching method: Exploration and collaborative learning

PHASE 4: APPLYING AND EXPLORING CONCEPTS OF SYMMETRY

Duration: 1.5 hours

Orchestration: Paired work

Description: In pairs students are given two tasks: 1) Programme the SLurtle to create the mirror image of a shape. The programme for the SLurtle to create one half of the shape and the line of symmetry will be given to students (as a half-baked solution). Students will be tasked with completing the programme so that the SLurtle draws the full shape. 2) Using the avatar as the

centre of symmetry, create a symmetrical shape. This second task is open and exploratory and allows students to engage in some creative exploration of the idea.

As students complete tasks they complete the OneNote reporting template.

Supported objectives: Maths - symmetry;

Expected student constructions: OneNote recordings.

Expected forms of student dialogue: Idea generation, discussion, collaboration.

Teaching method: Exploration and mentoring.

PHASE 5: REFLECTION

Duration: 15 minutes

Orchestration: In pairs.

Description: Discussion and completion of a shared reflection on exploring mathematical concepts with a robot in a virtual world.

Supported objectives: Reflecting on learning

Expected student constructions: OneNote reflection

Expected forms of student dialogue: Discussion

Teaching method: Mentoring.

ASSESSMENT PROCEDURES

Student record the outcomes of their learning activities (code, constructions and expression of understanding) through the OneNote recording and reflection templates.

Exploring the properties of shapes with SLurtles

AUTHOR:

Dr Carina Girvan (Cardiff University, UK) in collaboration with Ms Kelly Bladon (Oak Field Primary School, Barry, UK)

SHORT DESCRIPTION OF THE ACTIVITY (SUMMARY)

Following open exploration of the virtual world and SLurtles to familiarise students with basic controls, students engage in a series of short directed tasks which progressively develop into mathematically and computationally more complex problems. These activities begin by allowing students to apply existing knowledge of the properties of squares as they learn to control SLurtles and move on to students programming SLurtles to develop new knowledge about the properties of different types of triangles and 3D shapes. Along with applying and developing mathematical knowledge, students develop computational and programming knowledge and skills. Using an internally accessible only virtual world (within the school) also provides students a secured environment to begin exploring digital citizenship, interacting and collaborating skills.

FOCUS, SET UP AND REQUIREMENTS OF THE ACTIVITY

CURRICULUM

Subject: Mathematics and Digital Competency

Curriculum: Mathematics for KS2 and Digital Competency Framework

CONTENT

Choose categories and give a rating of the level of emphasis on concepts from each of the following domains

<input type="checkbox"/> Science	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Technology	<input type="checkbox"/> Business	<input type="checkbox"/> Engineering	<input type="checkbox"/> Arts	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Mathematics
(0-10)	(0-10)	(0-10)	(0-10)	(0-10)	(0-10)
0	7	0	0	0	5

OBJECTIVES

<i>Subject related</i>	<p>Mathematics: Y4 – Using geometry skills strand: recognise, classify and sketch polygons with up to eight sides, including irregular shapes;</p> <p>- Using geometry skills strand: recognise and classify 3D shapes, using their own criteria</p> <p>Y5 – Using measuring skills strand: recognise</p>
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	<p>acute and obtuse angles</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">- Using geometry skills strand: recognise and classify triangles, using their own criteria; identify congruent shapes and justify whether two or more shapes are congruent <p>DCF: Y4 – Citizenship strand: be aware that information put online leaves a digital footprint or trail; identify appropriate behaviour when participating or contributing to collaborative online projects for learning</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">- Interacting and collaborating strand: exchange online communication with other learners in one or more languages, making use of a growing range of available features- Data and computational thinking strand: demonstrate how part of a solution might need repetition; represent a simple solution in a flowchart that contains a looping element <p>DCF: Y5 – Citizenship strand: talk about the impact that the digital content created can have; create and use secure passwords</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">- Interacting and collaborating strand: exchange online communication with other learners in one or more languages, making use of a growing range of available features- Data and computational thinking strand: design simple sequences of instructions (algorithms). <p>LNF: Literacy: Y4 – Collaboration and discussion: contribute to group discussion and help everyone take part; help a group to reach agreement, e.g. considering reasons or consequences, keeping focus on the topic.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">- Meaning, purposes and readers: explain main idea(s) with supporting details, including observations and explanations where relevant <p>LNF: Literacy: Y5 – Collaboration and discussion: contribute to group discussion, taking some</p>
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	responsibility for completing the task well, e.g. introducing relevant ideas, summing up; build on and develop the ideas of others in group discussions, e.g. by asking questions to explore further, offering more ideas.
<i>Technology use related</i>	Develop an understanding of what a virtual world is, how to move and interact within it. Programming with a graphical environment (Scratch for OpenSim) Moving between multiple applications.
<i>Social and action related</i>	Develop written communication skills. Develop an awareness of how to communicate with others in a virtual world. Working with others in small groups to solve a problem. Presenting incomplete solutions to others.
<i>Argumentation and fostering of maker culture:</i>	Application of mathematical knowledge to solve problems. Awareness that there are multiple ways to solve a given problem. Reflection for learning.

TIME

Duration: 2 weeks

Schedule: 2 hours, twice per week

MATERIALS AND ARTIFACTS

<i>Digital artefact</i>	Programming interface - Scratch for OpenSim. Virtual world – Slurtle World (internal access only) Robot – SLurtles (cuboids)
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<i>Robotic artefact</i>	SLurtles: Programmable turtle in a virtual world which creates cuboids
<i>Student's workbook and manual</i>	Virtual world orientation guide and scavenger hunt. Worksheets
<i>Teacher's instruction book and manual:</i>	This activity plan

STUDENTS AND SPACE

STUDENTS (TARGET AUDIENCE)

<i>Sex and Age:</i>	Boys and girls; Years 4 and 5; Ages 8-10
<i>Prior knowledge:</i>	Assumed knowledge: Y3 Mathematics: identify right angles; recognise that two right angles make a half turn, and that four right angles make a full turn; describe an angle as more or less than a right angle; recognise and classify triangles, squares, rectangles, pentagons and hexagons, including irregular cases; identify congruent shapes; recognise 3D shapes, including prisms; DCF: Recursion in Scratch. Literacy: Reading and writing instructions; creating flow diagrams.
<i>Nationality and cultural background</i>	Welsh
<i>Social status and social environment</i>	Lower-socio economic status
<i>Special needs and abilities</i>	Dyslexia, English as a Second Language, behavioural support

SPACE INFO

Organizational and cultural context: In school, part of scheduled lessons.

Physical characteristics: Flexible learning environment. Laptop computers, 1 per pair. Movable shared desks. Carpet area. Reading area. Teacher's area.

Virtual World: Shared orientation island with directed tasks and spaces to explore. From this island the class island can be accessed.

Class island: The class island has a standard structured space as an arrival point and a large construction space for learners to use. The construction space is unstructured, allowing learners to use any part of that space.

SOCIAL ORCHESTRATION

POPULATION

Students: 19 children; two year groups (Y4 and Y5)

Tutors: 2 teachers: Class teacher and researcher

GROUPING:

Grouping criteria	Mixed ability pairs; boys with girls
<i>Setting:</i>	Students in classroom, as above.

INTERACTION DURING THE ACTIVITY (EMPHASIS)

Actions	Exchange ideas, discuss possible solutions to problems.
<i>Relationships</i>	Collaborative
<i>Roles in the group</i>	Equal/emerging roles in pairs.
<i>Support by the tutor(s)</i>	Facilitate, monitor and mentor.

LEARNING PROCEDURES

EXPECTED STUDENT ACTIVITY

Students during the activity are expected to engage in the following actions:

In world: explore, communicate, present work, programme and create.

In classroom: communicate, present work and exchange ideas.

STUDENT LEARNING PROCESSES

<i>Designed Conflicts and misconceptions</i>	Assumption that the turtle must turn by the internal angle.
<i>Learning processes emphasised:</i>	Emphasis on discovering mathematical ideas through purposeful exploration and computational thinking.
<i>Expected relevance of</i>	Students are expected to know the properties of squares and cubes, and to apply this knowledge. If there are knowledge gaps the activity

<i>alternative knowledge</i>	can be modified to provide an opportunity for individual students to discover the properties of these shapes through programming their robot. Students are expected to be familiar with drag-and-drop graphical programming environments.
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“HOW TO” IN THE CLASSROOM

In this section of the activity plan we describe how we expect the teaching and the learning process to evolve. We might use phases or activities for this description. The phases or activities should support the objectives stated and make use of the materials, tools and teaching and learning processes mentioned earlier in the activity plan. Next we provide an example of phase description

PHASE 1: INTRODUCTION TO THE VIRTUAL WORLD

Duration: 1.5 hours in world and in class.

Orchestration: Preparation: The whole class is introduced to the virtual world before being placed in pairs. In pairs, students decide on the name on their avatar. All avatars have the same surname to support class cohesion. Names and password are given to the teacher to create in the virtual world.

In the main lesson, students explore the virtual world individually.

Description: Children are introduced to the virtual world and told they will have a chance to identify the type of avatar they would like to create, name the avatar and create a password. Whole discussion on the types of information that are recorded in the virtual world and how this becomes part of our digital footprint. Highlight that this is a safe space that only the class can get access to but everything that is done is still recorded. Pupil led discussion on what makes a good password. Students then decide on the type of avatar they would like to create, choose a name and agree a password which is given to the teacher to create in-world whilst students complete another task.

Demonstration of communication tools. Create class rules for communicating in the virtual space.

Once all avatars are ready, students are shown the software that they will be using and how to log into the virtual world. Once in world, they are given the opportunity to freely explore or follow a path around the island with guided orientation activities. To support this, students are given a physical guide to refer to and scavenger hunt activities to practice targeted skills (communication, flying, inventory use, camera tools).

For the plenary, pupils complete in pairs a structured reflection writing about what they have done today, how they are working in a pair and drawing a picture of their avatar.

Supported objectives: Develop an understanding of what a virtual world is, how to move and interact within it; moving between multiple applications; be aware that information put online leaves a digital footprint or trail; identify appropriate behaviour when participating or contributing to collaborative online projects for learning; talk about the impact that the digital content created can have; create and use secure passwords

Expected student constructions: Avatar customisation, completed worksheet and reflection.

Expected forms of student dialogue: In class sharing and cooperative

Teaching method: Demonstration, whole class discussion, instruction, guided discovery and peer-teaching.

PHASE 2: INTRODUCTION TO SLURTLES – SANDBOXING

Duration: 2 hours

Orchestration: Paired activities.

Description: Students are introduced to SLurtles and Scratch for OpenSim (S4OS) and given a series of simple directed tasks to gain familiarity with the tools and switching between programmes – programme the SLurtle to move, draw a line, draw a multi-coloured line.

Whole class discussion to recap existing knowledge - what do we know about the properties of a square? Four sides, all equal length, four 90 degree angles. Following this, students are given the challenge to programme the SLurtle to draw a square. Further problems: What's the minimum number of lines that this programme could be written in? Extension: What does this tell us about squares? 3) Create a flow diagram to show what's happening in your code.

Plenary: In pairs complete the reflection template.

Supported objectives: Moving between multiple applications; programming with a graphical environment (Scratch for OpenSim); demonstrate knowledge of the properties of 2D shapes; demonstrate how part of a solution might need repetition; represent a simple solution in a flowchart that contains a looping element; design simple sequences of instructions (algorithms).

Expected student constructions: SLurtle constructed lines and squares; completed worksheets and reflection.

Expected forms of student dialogue: Discussion, sharing and instruction.

Teaching method: Demonstration, exploration, structured tasks and peer-teaching.

PHASE 3: DISCOVERING THE PROPERTIES OF TRIANGLES

Duration: 2 hours

Orchestration: Paired work

Description: Introduction: Recap what we already know about triangles. What are the different types of triangles? Which can we name and what are their properties? Explain what a congruent shape is. Can we find any in the classroom?

Discussion about how to solve a problem: Try, watch what happens, try to explain what went wrong, revise the plan.

In pairs, students are given the challenge to programme the SLurtle to draw a right-angled triangle. Students begin by engaging in free exploration. To support weaker pairs, a picture of a right-angled triangle could be given with the length of each side given.

Through trial and error and discussion with each other and the teacher, students should realise that the SLurtle does not turn through the internal angle of the triangle. The worksheet asks them to record the internal angles of the triangles that they create which may require support from the teacher and input on the number of degrees in half a circle. This provides an opportunity to introduce acute and obtuse angles.

Extension: Draw another type of triangle. Draw it, name it and explain its properties on the worksheet.

Plenary: Whole class: What is a congruent shape? Find two triangles in the virtual world that are congruent and explain why they are congruent. Reflection.

Supported objectives: Programming with a graphical environment (Scratch for OpenSim); moving between multiple applications; working with others in small groups to solve a problem; recognise, classify and sketch polygons with up to eight sides, including irregular shapes; recognise acute and obtuse angles; recognise and classify triangles, using their own criteria; identify congruent shapes and justify whether two or more shapes are congruent; design simple sequences of instructions (algorithms).

Expected student constructions: SLurtle constructed triangles; completed worksheets and reflection.

Expected forms of student dialogue: Discussion, sharing and instruction.

Teaching method: Demonstration, exploration, structured tasks and peer-teaching.

PHASE 4: EXPLORING 3D SHAPES, COLLABORATING AND DISCUSSING

Duration: 1.5 hours

Orchestration: Paired work

Description: Introduction: Recap what we have learnt so far. Introduce today's challenge and note that there are different ways to solve the problem. Highlight that collaboration and discussion will be important to get the best solution – class discussion: What do we need to do to work together well? Ensure everyone takes part, take responsibility for different parts of the task, contribute ideas, asking questions, build on and develop ideas of others, offer more ideas, reach agreement.

Revise how to solve problems: Try, watch what happens, try to explain what went wrong, revise the plan. This time will be recorded on worksheets.

Through trial and error and discussion with each other and the teacher, students should realise that the SLurtle does not draw up and must be rotated. The worksheet asks them to record each idea and what went wrong.

Plenary: Reflection in pairs.

Supported objectives: Programming with a graphical environment (Scratch for OpenSim); moving between multiple applications; working with others in small groups to solve a problem; recognise and classify 3D shapes, using their own criteria; contribute to group discussion and help everyone take part; help a group to reach agreement, e.g. considering reasons or consequences, keeping focus on the topic; contribute to group discussion, taking some responsibility for completing the

task well, e.g. introducing relevant ideas, summing up; build on and develop the ideas of others in group discussions, e.g. by asking questions to explore further, offering more ideas; explain main idea(s) with supporting details, including observations and explanations where relevant.

Expected student constructions: Cube frames, worksheets and reflections.

Expected forms of student dialogue: Discussion, sharing, checking and instruction.

Teaching method: Exploration, structured tasks and peer-teaching.

ASSESSMENT PROCEDURES

Students record outcomes on worksheets and through reflections. Teacher captures images of constructions. Dialogue with students.

Robotics workshop with Bee bots and Lego Mindstorms

AUTHOR:

Lisamarie Schuster, PRIA Robotics

SHORT DESCRIPTION OF THE ACTIVITY (SUMMARY)

This activity is designed for children who have never been in touch with robotics and/or programming. There is no prior knowledge required and it is suitable for children aged 6 and up.

At first, the students get an introduction to robotics in general: What kinds of robots are there in today’s world, what do they think about when they hear the word “robot”? Next, they learn what programming an autonomous robot is like by using Beebots: that you have to think of the program first and then execute it, that it is different from remote controlling a robot. With several different activities, they learn to plan their program ahead using Beebots.

In the next session, they get introduced to Lego Mindstorms and its programming environment. Trying out the Standard Movement block is important for the Tell a Story phase which is introduced to the children in the end of the second session.

The third session is used for the Tell a Story phase completely. In the “Tell a Story” phase they can be creative. The children should think of a story that they would like to tell, with their robot as a main character. Then, they should modify the robot to look like their desired main character by building a claw and attaching it to the base robot and decorating their robot. After having programmed the robot in a way that it suitable for the story and gathering utensils, the children should have a finished story.

FOCUS, SET UP AND REQUIREMENTS OF THE ACTIVITY

CURRICULUM

Select NO if the scenario is not aligned with the curriculum of your country and YES if it is. Please mention the relevant subject matter.

NO YES Subject:

CONTENT

Choose categories and give a rating of the level of emphasis on concepts from each of the following domains

<input type="checkbox"/> Science (0-10) 0	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Technology (0-10) 10	<input type="checkbox"/> Business (0-10) 0	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Engineering (0-10) 10	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Arts (0-10) 0	<input type="checkbox"/> Mathematics (0-10) 0
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OBJECTIVES

<i>Subject related</i>	No subject <i>e.g. Study the angle and position of all materials (servo motors, circuits, sensors), as well as the construction of the legs in order for the robot - insect to be autonomous and move correctly</i>
<i>Technology use related</i>	Programming with Lego Mindstorms programming environment/with Hedgehog <i>e.g. Programming with Arduino, or with in LEGO EV3 programming environment</i>
<i>Social and action related</i>	Fostering of presentation skills <i>e.g. Develop collaborative skills, take roles within groups, communicate with other groups to exchange ideas and tips, advice</i>
<i>Argumentation and fostering of maker culture:</i>	define an authentic problem, make assumptions, test possible solutions, choose the best solution <i>e.g. practice making conjectures about how the robot will react to external stimuli based on the program given or formulate and define an authentic problem, make assumptions, test possible solutions, choose the best solution, communicate with other “makers”.</i>

TIME

Duration: 3h on block (e.g. 4 weeks)

Schedule: 3h on block (e.g. 2 hours per week)

MATERIALS AND ARTIFACTS

<i>Digital artifact</i>	Lego EV3 Programming environment, C, Python <i>e.g. programming language (Lego EV3 programming environment), visual interface, robot simulation</i>
<i>Robotic artifact</i>	Beebots: an insect; Lego Mindstorms: a simple vehicle <i>i.e. The technology and the robot form: LEGO WEDO – form: 'an insect', 'a car' ... 'a simple vehicle'</i>
<i>Student's workbook and manual</i>	no manual <i>e.g. Manual with step-by-step instructions for the electronic part and programming part too, activity sheets, Lego electronic manual, evaluation sheet</i>
<i>Teacher's instruction book and manual:</i>	no manual <i>e.g. Teacher's notes with a template of e.g. three incisive stages and five steps for the first two stages.</i>

STUDENTS AND SPACE

STUDENTS (TARGET AUDIENCE)

Sex and Age:	, 6 – 10 years old <i>e.g. boys & girls, 12-15 years old</i>
Prior knowledge:	Basic English understanding required for Python programming <i>e.g. little if any knowledge of Arduino but experts on electronics; basic knowledge of programming concepts (like if-then concepts)</i>
Nationality and cultural background	not relevant <i>e.g. 5 pupils are from Albania and 10 from Greece</i>
Social status and social environment	not relevant <i>e.g. underprivileged area OR mainstream public school OR elite private school</i>
Special needs and abilities	not relevant <i>e.g. ADD, dyslexia, Soc. Em. Behavior Disorders, gifted, other OR Lego programming environment is in English. English is not native language for participants</i>

SPACE INFO

Organizational and cultural context: Open space for driving robots, notebooks, wifi (For example: in school at the technology laboratory; OR during project time in/after school; OR established voluntary club activity; OR after school activity at Computer Lab.)

Physical characteristics: indoors outdoors

SOCIAL ORCHESTRATION

POPULATION

Students	Tutors	Assistants
Up to 12	1	0
Up to 16	1	1
Up to 20	2	0
Up to 25	2	1

GROUPING:

Grouping criteria	No criteria <i>e.g. mixed ability, mixed gender OR mixed specialties (for Vocational Schools)</i>
Setting:	Two children per group with view of the blackboard (projector) <i>e.g. Students in a normal classroom OR around light mobile tables OR looking at the blackboard or in small groups OR students in front of computers with one lego EV3 kit available for each group</i>

INTERACTION DURING THE ACTIVITY (EMPHASIS)

<i>Actions</i>	exchange ideas, dialogue <i>e.g. Exchange ideas, dialogue, negotiation, debate</i>
<i>Relationships</i>	collaborative <i>e.g. Collaborative, competitive</i>
<i>Roles in the group</i>	emergent roles <i>e.g. pre-defined roles; emergent roles; role exchange in the group</i>
<i>Support by the tutor(s)</i>	monitor, facilitate <i>e.g. Intervene, monitor, facilitate</i>

LEARNING PROCEDURES

EXPECTED STUDENT ACTIVITY

Students during the activity are expected to engage in the following actions:

construct, observe, communicate, present their work (mindmap, code, robot)

e.g. construct, observe, communicate, create, present their work in a blog, exchange ideas, etc.

STUDENT LEARNING PROCESSES

<i>Designed Conflicts and misconceptions</i>	no designed conflicts <i>Do the activity designers wish to bring students in conflict with mistaken conceptions documented in educational research or their teaching practice?</i>
<i>Learning processes emphasized:</i>	trying out their code and adapting it to the task <i>e.g. emphasis on analyzing robot behavior in order to refine and reflect on the code that defines this behavior</i>
<i>Expected relevance of alternative knowledge</i>	not relevant <i>e.g. students are expected to investigate the structure of an insect's body (biology) in order to construct their robot</i>

“HOW TO” IN THE CLASSROOM

In this section of the activity plan we describe how we expect the teaching and the learning process to evolve. We might use phases or activities for this description. The phases or activities should support the objectives stated and make use of the materials, tools and teaching and learning processes mentioned earlier in the activity plan. Next we provide an example of phase description

PHASE 1.: INTRODUCTION, BRAINSTORMING, MINDMAP

Duration: 35 min

Orchestration: whole class discussion

Description: Children are asked to introduce their selves by saying their name and describing what they think about when they hear the word “robot”. Afterwards, a brainstorming is conducted about the question: “What are robots?” What do they look like? What materials are they made of? What are they used for today? What can they be used for in the future? A short explanation is given about what a mindmap is, what it could look like (give an example, a picture) and what it could look like in relation to the given task (robots). The tutor draws a mindmap on the blackboard by asking the students about their thoughts about robots. The children are then asked to draw their own mindmap about their thoughts about robots.

Indicate which of the stated objectives are supported by this phase

Expected student constructions: mindmap

Expected forms of student dialogue: discussion

Teaching method: discussion (*Instruction, demonstration by example, discussion, experimentation*)

PHASE 2.: PRESENTATION ABOUT TYPES OF ROBOTS

Duration: 15 min

Orchestration: presentation

Description: The tutor talks about what kinds of robots there are already in today’s world, shows students pictures and asks them what they think these robots are used for.

Indicate which of the stated objectives are supported by this phase

Expected student constructions: none

Expected forms of student dialogue: discussion

Teaching method: presentation

PHASE 3.: BEEBOTS: INTRODUCTION

Duration: 15 min

Orchestration: presentation

Description: The students form two big groups. Each group is given a Beebot and every child can have a look at it. The tutor asks the students what they think each button does. Afterwards, the tutor shows them what each button does by presenting it on the Beebot square map.

Indicate which of the stated objectives are supported by this phase

Expected student constructions: none

Expected forms of student dialogue: discussion

Teaching method: presentation, demonstration by example

PHASE 4.: BEEBOTS: DRIVING TO A CERTAIN SQUARE

Duration: 45 min

Orchestration: group work

Description: The tutor and the assistant each supervise one group. Each group gets one Beebot and one Beebot square map. The tutor/assistant shows them how to drive to a certain square. Then, some of the students can try it out their selves. Each child gets a different square from the previous one so that it cannot just copy which buttons the previous child had pressed.

Indicate which of the stated objectives are supported by this phase

Expected student constructions: none

Expected forms of student dialogue: discussion, helping each other in the group

Teaching method: demonstration by example, experimentation

PHASE 5.: BEEBOTS: DRIVING TO A CERTAIN SQUARE WITH OBSTACLES

Duration: 20 min

Orchestration: group work

Description: After some of the students have already tried out driving to a certain square and the tutor/assistant think that everyone has understood the way the Beebots work, obstacles like foam cubes can be introduced to the square map.

Indicate which of the stated objectives are supported by this phase

Expected student constructions: none

Expected forms of student dialogue: discussion, helping each other in the group

Teaching method: demonstration by example, experimentation

PHASE 6.: BEEBOTS: USING THE BEEBOT MATS

Duration: 50 min

Orchestration: group work

Description: Once everyone has understood how Beebots work and how you can navigate around obstacles with them, the children form groups of two to three people. Each group then gets a Beebot mat and has to take turns in completing the task on the mat: finding a treasure or driving a go-kart race. As soon as everyone has had their turn on the mat and has successfully completed the task, the groups can switch mats (e.g. that the group who has had the go-kart mat at first now gets the treasure mat).

Indicate which of the stated objectives are supported by this phase

Expected student constructions: code

Expected forms of student dialogue: helping each other in the group

Teaching method: experimentation

PHASE 7.: LEGO MINDSTORMS: PRINTING THEIR NAME

Duration: 30 min

Orchestration: group work

Description: The tutor shows the students which blocks are used for printing text on the controller's screen. Afterwards, the students experiment on how to make the robot greet one of the group members and then all of the group members.

Indicate which of the stated objectives are supported by this phase

Expected student constructions: code

Expected forms of student dialogue: helping each other in the group

Teaching method: demonstration by example, experimentation

PHASE 8.: LEGO MINDSTORMS: INTRODUCTION TO DRIVING

Duration: 20 min

Orchestration: team work, whole class discussion

Description: Explanation of the Standard Movement block and the buttons and sliders on it which influence the factors of the movement: direction, speed and driving a curve. Afterwards, the students can try modifying these factors and see what they do: driving forward, driving a curve, driving backwards.

Indicate which of the stated objectives are supported by this phase

Expected student constructions: code

Expected forms of student dialogue: helping each other in the group

Teaching method: Instruction, demonstration by example, discussion, experimentation

PHASE 9.: LEGO MINDSTORMS: DRIVE A SQUARE

Duration: 40 minutes

Orchestration: team work

Description: Students should use their knowledge from the previous phases to drive along a square shape with the robot. In order to be able to do that, they have to be able to drive a quite accurate 90° curve at first. They have to try out modifying the different factors for doing that. The 90° do not have to be perfectly accurate, though, since children of this age get bored quite easily.

Indicate which of the stated objectives are supported by this phase

Expected student constructions: code

Expected forms of student dialogue: helping each other in the team

Teaching method: experimentation

PHASE 10.: LEGO MINDSTORMS: TELL A STORY: INTRODUCTION

Duration: 20 min

Orchestration: team work

Description: The tutor introduces the phase “Tell a Story” to the students. They should think of a story that they could tell, with their robot as a main character. The tutor shows them several examples of possible stories (pictures).

Indicate which of the stated objectives are supported by this phase

Expected student constructions: none

Expected forms of student dialogue: discuss their ideas with their group

Teaching method: Instruction, discussion

PHASE 11.: LEGO MINDSTORMS: TELL A STORY: SKETCH

Duration: 40 min

Orchestration: team work

Description: The students should think about what their robot should look like in order to be able to be the main character of their story. They should draw a sketch of their robot to describe it.

Indicate which of the stated objectives are supported by this phase

Expected student constructions: Sketch of their finished robot (including claw/decorations)

Expected forms of student dialogue: discuss their ideas with their group

Teaching method: discussion

PHASE 12.: LEGO MINDSTORMS: TELL A STORY: BUILDING AND PROGRAMMING THE ROBOT

Duration: 210 min

Orchestration: team work

Description: The students should now try to build and program the robot to be the main character of the story that they have chosen. They can use paper and pencils to set up a simulated environment in which their robot performs the story. As a minimum requirement, the students should build a static claw and program their robot in a way that simulates the story that they have chosen.

Indicate which of the stated objectives are supported by this phase

Expected student constructions: A claw for pushing items around and a program which simulates the story

Expected forms of student dialogue: helping each other in the group, discussing their ideas with their group

Teaching method: discussion, experimentation

ASSESSMENT PROCEDURES

Suggestions for procedures, methods and tools that can facilitate the achievement of the teaching objectives stated at the beginning of the activity plan. (e.g. post activity tests, reflective videos etc)

Presentation of the task to the teacher

Robotics workshop with Lego Mindstorms

AUTHOR:

Lisamarie Schuster, PRIA Robotics

SHORT DESCRIPTION OF THE ACTIVITY (SUMMARY)

This activity is designed for children who have never been in touch with robotics and/or programming. There is no prior knowledge required and it is suitable for children aged 8 and up.

At first, the students get an introduction to robotics in general: What kinds of robots are there in today's world, what do they think about when they hear the word "robot"? Next, they learn how to drive the robot in different directions: forwards, backwards, curves.

In the following part, they can be creative. In an activity called "Save the World", the children are encouraged to think about problems in today's world and how robots could solve them. Then, they simulate this task with their own robot by building a claw and attaching it to the base robot. After the robot is programmed, utensils are gathered and maybe the robot is even decorated using paper and pencils, each group presents which problem they chose, explains the simulation and shows it to all the others by executing their program.

In the end, the students get a final task in which they have to program the robot to drive accurately along a given path. Depending on the students' mood, this can be executed in a competition way or just as a normal task.

FOCUS, SET UP AND REQUIREMENTS OF THE ACTIVITY

CURRICULUM

Select NO if the scenario is not aligned with the curriculum of your country and YES if it is. Please mention the relevant subject matter.

NO YES Subject:

CONTENT

Choose categories and give a rating of the level of emphasis on concepts from each of the following domains

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Science (0-10)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Technology (0-10)	<input type="checkbox"/> Business (0-10)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Engineering (0-10)	<input type="checkbox"/> Arts (0-10)	<input type="checkbox"/> Mathematics (0-10)
0	10	0	10	0	0

OBJECTIVES

<i>Subject related</i>	No subject <i>e.g. Study the angle and position of all materials (servo motors, circuits, sensors), as well as the construction of the legs in order for the robot - insect to be autonomous and move correctly</i>
<i>Technology use related</i>	Programming with Lego Mindstorms programming environment/with Hedgehog <i>e.g. Programming with Arduino, or with in LEGO EV3 programming environment</i>
<i>Social and action related</i>	Fostering of presentation skills <i>e.g. Develop collaborative skills, take roles within groups, communicate with other groups to exchange ideas and tips, advice</i>
<i>Argumentation and fostering of maker culture:</i>	define an authentic problem, make assumptions, test possible solutions, choose the best solution <i>e.g. practice making conjectures about how the robot will react to external stimuli based on the program given or formulate and define an authentic problem, make assumptions, test possible solutions, choose the best solution, communicate with other “makers”.</i>

TIME

Duration: 3h on block (e.g. 4 weeks)

Schedule: 3h on block (e.g. 2 hours per week)

MATERIALS AND ARTIFACTS

<i>Digital artifact</i>	Lego EV3 Programming environment, C, Python <i>e.g. programming language (Lego EV3 programming environment), visual interface, robot simulation</i>
<i>Robotic artifact</i>	a simple vehicle <i>i.e. The technology and the robot form: LEGO WEDO – form: 'an insect', 'a car' ... 'a simple vehicle'</i>
<i>Student's workbook and manual</i>	no manual <i>e.g. Manual with step-by-step instructions for the electronic part and programming part too, activity sheets, Lego electronic manual, evaluation sheet</i>
<i>Teacher's instruction book and manual:</i>	no manual <i>e.g. Teacher's notes with a template of e.g. three incisive stages and five steps for the first two stages.</i>

STUDENTS AND SPACE

STUDENTS (TARGET AUDIENCE)

Sex and Age:	, 8 – 13 years old <i>e.g. boys & girls, 12-15 years old</i>
Prior knowledge:	Basic English understanding required for Python programming <i>e.g. little if any knowledge of Arduino but experts on electronics; basic knowledge of programming concepts (like if-then concepts)</i>
Nationality and cultural background	not relevant <i>e.g. 5 pupils are from Albania and 10 from Greece</i>
Social status and social environment	not relevant <i>e.g. underprivileged area OR mainstream public school OR elite private school</i>
Special needs and abilities	not relevant <i>e.g. ADD, dyslexia, Soc. Em. Behavior Disorders, gifted, other OR Lego programming environment is in English. English is not native language for participants</i>

SPACE INFO

Organizational and cultural context: Open space for driving robots, notebooks, wifi (For example: in school at the technology laboratory; OR during project time in/after school; OR established voluntary club activity; OR after school activity at Computer Lab.)

Physical characteristics: indoors outdoors

SOCIAL ORCHESTRATION

POPULATION

Students	Tutors	Assistants
Up to 12	1	0
Up to 16	1	1
Up to 20	2	0
Up to 25	2	1

GROUPING:

Grouping criteria	No criteria <i>e.g. mixed ability, mixed gender OR mixed specialties (for Vocational Schools)</i>
Setting:	Two children per group with view of the blackboard (projector) <i>e.g. Students in a normal classroom OR around light mobile tables OR looking at the blackboard or in small groups OR students in front of computers with one lego EV3 kit available for each group</i>

INTERACTION DURING THE ACTIVITY (EMPHASIS)

<i>Actions</i>	exchange ideas, dialogue <i>e.g. Exchange ideas, dialogue, negotiation, debate</i>
<i>Relationships</i>	collaborative <i>e.g. Collaborative, competitive</i>
<i>Roles in the group</i>	emergent roles <i>e.g. pre-defined roles; emergent roles; role exchange in the group</i>
<i>Support by the tutor(s)</i>	monitor, facilitate <i>e.g. Intervene, monitor, facilitate</i>

LEARNING PROCEDURES

EXPECTED STUDENT ACTIVITY

Students during the activity are expected to engage in the following actions:

construct, observe, communicate, present their work (mindmap, code, robot), present their work in front of their colleagues

e.g. construct, observe, communicate, create, present their work in a blog, exchange ideas, etc.

STUDENT LEARNING PROCESSES

<i>Designed Conflicts and misconceptions</i>	no designed conflicts <i>Do the activity designers wish to bring students in conflict with mistaken conceptions documented in educational research or their teaching practice?</i>
<i>Learning processes emphasized:</i>	trying out their code and adapting it to the task <i>e.g. emphasis on analyzing robot behavior in order to refine and reflect on the code that defines this behavior</i>
<i>Expected relevance of alternative knowledge</i>	not relevant <i>e.g. students are expected to investigate the structure of an insect's body (biology) in order to construct their robot</i>

“HOW TO” IN THE CLASSROOM

In this section of the activity plan we describe how we expect the teaching and the learning process to evolve. We might use phases or activities for this description. The phases or activities should support the objectives stated and make use of the materials, tools and teaching and learning processes mentioned earlier in the activity plan. Next we provide an example of phase description

PHASE 1: INTRODUCTION, BRAINSTORMING, MINDMAP

Duration: 35 min

Orchestration: whole class discussion

Description: Children are asked to introduce their selves by saying their name and describing what they think about when they hear the word “robot”. Afterwards, a brainstorming is conducted about the question: “What are robots?” What do they look like? What are they used for today? What can they be used for in the future? The children are then asked to draw a mindmap about their thoughts about robots.

Indicate which of the stated objectives are supported by this phase

Expected student constructions: mindmap

Expected forms of student dialogue: discussion

Teaching method: discussion (*Instruction, demonstration by example, discussion, experimentation*)

PHASE 2: PRESENTATION ABOUT TYPES OF ROBOTS

Duration: 15 min

Orchestration: presentation

Description: The tutor talks about what kinds of robots there are already in today’s world, shows students pictures and asks them what they think these robots are used for.

Indicate which of the stated objectives are supported by this phase

Expected student constructions: none

Expected forms of student dialogue: discussion

Teaching method: presentation

PHASE 3: PRINTING THEIR NAME

Duration: 20 min

Orchestration: group work

Description: The tutor shows the students which blocks are used for printing text on the controller's screen. Afterwards, the students experiment on how to make the robot greet one of the group members and then all of the group members.

Indicate which of the stated objectives are supported by this phase

Expected student constructions: code

Expected forms of student dialogue: helping each other in the group

Teaching method: demonstration by example

PHASE 4: INTRODUCTION TO DRIVING

Duration: 20 min

Orchestration: team work, whole class discussion

Description: Explanation of the Standard Movement block. Discussion about what the different buttons could be and how changing them (the factors) could influence direction of the movement, speed and how to drive a curve. Afterwards, the students can try modifying these factors and see what they do: driving forward, driving a curve, driving backwards.

Indicate which of the stated objectives are supported by this phase

Expected student constructions: code

Expected forms of student dialogue: helping each other in the group

Teaching method: Instruction, demonstration by example, discussion, experimentation

PHASE 5: DRIVE A SQUARE

Duration: 40 minutes

Orchestration: team work

Description: Students should use their knowledge from the previous phases to drive along a square shape with the robot. In order to be able to do that, they have to be able to drive a perfect 90° curve at first. They have to try out modifying the different factors for doing that.

Indicate which of the stated objectives are supported by this phase

Expected student constructions: code

Expected forms of student dialogue: helping each other in the team

Teaching method: experimentation

PHASE 6: SAVE THE WORLD: INTRODUCTION

Duration: 10 min

Orchestration: team work, whole class discussion

Description: A brainstorming is conducted about which problems there are in today's world and how robots could help solve them/make the world a better place.

Indicate which of the stated objectives are supported by this phase

Expected student constructions: -

Expected forms of student dialogue: -

Teaching method: Instruction, discussion

PHASE 7: SAVE THE WORLD: SKETCH

Duration: 30 min

Orchestration: team work

Description: The students should think about how to design their robot to complete a task which could save the world. They should draw a sketch of their robot to describe it.

Indicate which of the stated objectives are supported by this phase

Expected student constructions: Sketch of their finished robot (including claw/decorations)

Expected forms of student dialogue: discuss their ideas with their group

Teaching method: discussion

PHASE 8: SAVE THE WORLD: BUILDING AND PROGRAMING THE ROBOT

Duration: 110 min

Orchestration: team work

Description: The students should now try to build and program a simulation of the task that they have chosen. They can use paper and pencils to set up a simulated environment in which their robot performs the task. As a minimum requirement, the students should build a static claw and program their robot in a way that simulates the task that they have chosen.

Indicate which of the stated objectives are supported by this phase

Expected student constructions: A claw for pushing items around and a program which simulates the Save the World task

Expected forms of student dialogue: helping each other in the group, discussing their ideas with their group

Teaching method: discussion, experimentation

PHASE 9: SAVE THE WORLD: PRESENTATION OF THE ROBOT

Duration: 20 min

Orchestration: team work, presentation

Description: One member of each group should now present the group's robot and explain the task the robot is going to simulate, what the utensils they used should simulate (foam cubes, ...) and then execute the program.

Indicate which of the stated objectives are supported by this phase

Expected student constructions: -

Expected forms of student dialogue: Presentation of their work

Teaching method: discussion

PHASE 10: DRIVING ACCURATELY

Duration: 60 min

Orchestration: team work

Description: A path is taped to the floor. The students should program their robot in a way that it follows this path. The path should contain a lot of different curves, straightforward parts of the same length, only multiplied (for example: line no. 1 is x seconds long, line no. 2 is 3*x seconds long) and could contain a foam cube or something similar that the robot is supposed to push somewhere.

Indicate which of the stated objectives are supported by this phase

Expected student constructions: code

Expected forms of student dialogue: discussion

Teaching method: (Instruction, demonstration by example, discussion)

ASSESSMENT PROCEDURES

Suggestions for procedures, methods and tools that can facilitate the achievement of the teaching objectives stated at the beginning of the activity plan. (e.g. post activity tests, reflective videos etc)

Presentation of the task to the teacher

Presentation of their robot and their program to the whole class in Phase 9: Save the world:

Presentation of the robot

Robotics workshop with hedgehog

AUTHOR:

Christoph Hackenberger, PRIA Robotics

SHORT DESCRIPTION OF THE ACTIVITY (SUMMARY)

This activity is designed for children who have never been in touch with robotics and/or programming. There is no prior knowledge required and it is suitable for children aged 12 and up.

At first, the students get an introduction to robotics in general: What kinds of robots are there in today's world, what do they think about when they hear the word "robot"? Next, they learn how to drive the robot in different directions: forwards, backwards, curves.

In the following part, they can be creative. In an activity called "Save the World", the children are encouraged to think about problems in today's world and how robots could solve them. Then, they simulate this task with their own robot by building a claw and attaching it to the base robot. After the robot is programmed, utensils are gathered and maybe the robot is even decorated using paper and pencils, each group presents which problem they chose, explain the simulation and show it to all the others by executing their program.

In the end, sensors and loops are explained for usage

FOCUS, SET UP AND REQUIREMENTS OF THE ACTIVITY

CURRICULUM

Select NO if the scenario is not aligned with the curriculum of your country and YES if it is. Please mention the relevant subject matter.

NO YES Subject:

CONTENT

Choose categories and give a rating of the level of emphasis on concepts from each of the following domains

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Science (0-10)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Technology (0-10)	<input type="checkbox"/> Business (0-10)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Engineering (0-10)	<input type="checkbox"/> Arts (0-10)	<input type="checkbox"/> Mathematics (0-10)
0	10	0	10	0	0

OBJECTIVES

<i>Subject related</i>	No subject <i>e.g. Study the angle and position of all materials (servo motors, circuits, sensors), as well as the construction of the legs in order for the robot - insect to be autonomous and move correctly</i>
<i>Technology use related</i>	Programming with Lego Mindstorms programming environment/with Hedgehog <i>e.g. Programming with Arduino, or with in LEGO EV3 programming environment</i>
<i>Social and action related</i>	Fostering of presentation skills <i>e.g. Develop collaborative skills, take roles within groups, communicate with other groups to exchange ideas and tips, advice</i>
<i>Argumentation and fostering of maker culture:</i>	define an authentic problem, make assumptions, test possible solutions, choose the best solution <i>e.g. practice making conjectures about how the robot will react to external stimuli based on the program given or formulate and define an authentic problem, make assumptions, test possible solutions, choose the best solution, communicate with other “makers”.</i>

TIME

Duration: 3h on block (e.g. 4 weeks)

Schedule: 3h on block (e.g. 2 hours per week)

MATERIALS AND ARTIFACTS

<i>Digital artifact</i>	Lego EV3 Programming environment, C, Python <i>e.g. programming language (Lego EV3 programming environment), visual interface, robot simulation</i>
<i>Robotic artifact</i>	a simple vehicle <i>i.e. The technology and the robot form: LEGO WEDO – form: 'an insect', 'a car' ... 'a simple vehicle'</i>
<i>Student's workbook and manual</i>	no manual <i>e.g. Manual with step-by-step instructions for the electronic part and programming part too, activity sheets, Lego electronic manual, evaluation sheet</i>
<i>Teacher's instruction book and manual:</i>	no manual <i>e.g. Teacher's notes with a template of e.g. three incisive stages and five steps for the first two stages.</i>

STUDENTS AND SPACE

STUDENTS (TARGET AUDIENCE)

Sex and Age:	, 10 – 19 years old <i>e.g. boys & girls, 12-15 years old</i>
Prior knowledge:	Basic English understanding required for Python programming <i>e.g. little if any knowledge of Arduino but experts on electronics; basic knowledge of programming concepts (like if-then concepts)</i>
Nationality and cultural background	not relevant <i>e.g. 5 pupils are from Albania and 10 from Greece</i>
Social status and social environment	not relevant <i>e.g. underprivileged area OR mainstream public school OR elite private school</i>
Special needs and abilities	not relevant <i>e.g. ADD, dyslexia, Soc. Em. Behavior Disorders, gifted, other OR Lego programming environment is in English. English is not native language for participants</i>

SPACE INFO

Organizational and cultural context: Open space for driving robots, notebooks, wifi (For example: in school at the technology laboratory; OR during project time in/after school; OR established voluntary club activity; OR after school activity at Computer Lab.)

Physical characteristics: indoors outdoors

SOCIAL ORCHESTRATION

POPULATION

Students	Tutors	Assistants
Up to 12	1	0
Up to 16	1	1
Up to 20	2	0
Up to 25	2	1

GROUPING:

Grouping criteria	No criteria <i>e.g. mixed ability, mixed gender OR mixed specialties (for Vocational Schools)</i>
Setting:	Two children per group with view of the blackboard (projector) <i>e.g. Students in a normal classroom OR around light mobile tables OR looking at the blackboard or in small groups OR students in front of computers with one lego EV3 kit available for each group</i>

INTERACTION DURING THE ACTIVITY (EMPHASIS)

<i>Actions</i>	exchange ideas, dialogue <i>e.g. Exchange ideas, dialogue, negotiation, debate</i>
<i>Relationships</i>	collaborative <i>e.g. Collaborative, competitive</i>
<i>Roles in the group</i>	emergent roles <i>e.g. pre-defined roles; emergent roles; role exchange in the group</i>
<i>Support by the tutor(s)</i>	monitor, facilitate <i>e.g. Intervene, monitor, facilitate</i>

LEARNING PROCEDURES

EXPECTED STUDENT ACTIVITY

Students during the activity are expected to engage in the following actions:

construct, observe, communicate, present their work (mindmap, code, robot), present their work in front of their colleagues

e.g. construct, observe, communicate, create, present their work in a blog, exchange ideas, etc.

STUDENT LEARNING PROCESSES

<i>Designed Conflicts and misconceptions</i>	no designed conflicts <i>Do the activity designers wish to bring students in conflict with mistaken conceptions documented in educational research or their teaching practice?</i>
<i>Learning processes emphasized:</i>	trying out their code and adapting it to the task <i>e.g. emphasis on analyzing robot behavior in order to refine and reflect on the code that defines this behavior</i>
<i>Expected relevance of alternative knowledge</i>	not relevant <i>e.g. students are expected to investigate the structure of an insect's body (biology) in order to construct their robot</i>

“HOW TO” IN THE CLASSROOM

In this section of the activity plan we describe how we expect the teaching and the learning process to evolve. We might use phases or activities for this description. The phases or activities should support the objectives stated and make use of the materials, tools and teaching and learning processes mentioned earlier in the activity plan. Next we provide an example of phase description

PHASE 1: INTRODUCTION (WHO AM I? WHO ARE YOU?)

Duration: 10 min

Orchestration: plenum discussion

Description: A short introduction of the tutor and all of the students (Name, Age, Knowledge about robots etc.).

Indicate which of the stated objectives are supported by this phase

Expected student constructions: -

Expected forms of student dialogue: -

Teaching method: Instruction, Discussion

PHASE 2: INTRODUCTION TO ROBOTICS, GETTING TO KNOW HEDGEHOG

Duration: 20 min

Orchestration: plenary discussion

Description: Tutor should lead the discussion about what are robots, fields of application, pros and cons of robots. After the discussion, the tutor should explain the Hedgehog Controller and how to use it.

Indicate which of the stated objectives are supported by this phase

Expected student constructions: -

Expected forms of student dialogue: -

Teaching method: Instruction, discussion

PHASE 3: MINDMAP

Duration: 30 min

Orchestration: individual work

Description: Tutor should explain what a mindmap is (give some examples). The topic of the mindmap should be robots, the tutor can give some hints like fields of application, material etc. . Afterwards the students should create a mindmap.

Indicate which of the stated objectives are supported by this phase

Expected student constructions: Mindmap

Expected forms of student dialogue: -

Teaching method: Instruction, demonstration by example

PHASE 4: PRINT SOMETHING TO THE CONSOLE

Duration: 10 minutes

Orchestration: individual and class work

Description: Handout the robots and explain how to use the Hedgehog IDE. Afterwards show the students how to print to the console and ask the students to print the names of all of the team members on the console.

Indicate which of the stated objectives are supported by this phase

Expected student constructions:

Expected forms of student dialogue: helping each other in the team

Teaching method: Instruction, demonstration by example, discussion

PHASE 5: INTRODUCTION TO DRIVING

Duration: 20 min

Orchestration: team work, whole class discussion

Description: Explain the students the move function of the Hedgehog controller and show them how to influence the direction and speed of the motors

Indicate which of the stated objectives are supported by this phase

Expected student constructions:

Expected forms of student dialogue:

Teaching method: Instruction, demonstration by example, discussion, experimentation

PHASE 6: DRIVE FORWARD

Duration: 30 min

Orchestration: team work

Description: Students should program the robot to drive a fixed distance in a straight line

Indicate which of the stated objectives are supported by this phase

Expected student constructions: Drive forward program

Expected forms of student dialogue: helping each other in the team

Teaching method: discussion, experimentation

PHASE 7: INTRODUCTION TO CURVES

Duration: 10 min

Orchestration: team work, whole class discussion

Description: Explain the students the two different types of driving curves and explain them how the factors speed and time influences the shape of the curve

Indicate which of the stated objectives are supported by this phase

Expected student constructions: -

Expected forms of student dialogue: -

Teaching method: Instruction, demonstration by example, discussion, experimentation

PHASE 8: DRIVING A 90° CRUVE

Duration: 20 min

Orchestration: team work

Description: Students should program the robot to drive a 90° curve

Indicate which of the stated objectives are supported by this phase

Expected student constructions: Curve Program

Expected forms of student dialogue: helping each other in the team

Teaching method: discussion, experimentation

PHASE 9: DRIVE A RECTANGLE

Duration: 40 minutes

Orchestration: team work

Description: Students should use their knowledge from the previous phases to drive a complete rectangle with the robot. The rectangle is not required to be 100% correct since the robots do not drive perfectly straight.

Indicate which of the stated objectives are supported by this phase

Expected student constructions: Rectangle Program

Expected forms of student dialogue: helping each other in the team

Teaching method: discussion, experimentation

PHASE 10: EXPLAINING THE FORM "SAVE THE WORLD"

Duration: 10 min

Orchestration: team work, whole class discussion

Description: Together with the students, brainstorming about which problems there are in today's world and how robots could solve them/make the world a better place.

Indicate which of the stated objectives are supported by this phase

Expected student constructions: -

Expected forms of student dialogue: -

Teaching method: Instruction, discussion

PHASE 11: SAVE THE WORLD

Duration: 20 min

Orchestration: team work

Description: The students should think about how to design their robot to complete a task which could save the world. They should draw a sketch of their robot to describe it.

Indicate which of the stated objectives are supported by this phase

Expected student constructions: Save the world sketch

Expected forms of student dialogue: discuss in the team about their ideas

Teaching method: discussion

PHASE 12: BUILDING AND PROGRAMING THE ROBOT

Duration: 100 min

Orchestration: team work

Description: The students should now try to build and program a simulation of their save the world task from Phase 2. They can use paper and pen or something else to setup a simulated environment in which their robot performs the task. As a minimum requirement, the students should build a static claw.

Indicate which of the stated objectives are supported by this phase

Expected student constructions: A claw to push things and a program which simulates the save the world task

Expected forms of student dialogue:

Teaching method: discussion, experimentation

PHASE 13: PRESENTATION OF THE ROBOT

Duration: 10 min

Orchestration: team work, presentation

Description: The teams should now present their robots and explain the difficulties they had during the building process. They should also point out the difference between the planned and the actual robot

Indicate which of the stated objectives are supported by this phase

Expected student constructions: -

Expected forms of student dialogue: Presentation of their work

Teaching method: demonstration by example, discussion

PHASE 14: INTRODUCTION TO SENSORS

Duration: 10 min

Orchestration: plenum discussion

Description: Explain the purpose of sensors and show some examples what they are used for. Explain the difference between analog and digital sensors and how you can use them in the code.

Indicate which of the stated objectives are supported by this phase

Expected student constructions: -

Expected forms of student dialogue: discussion

Teaching method: (Instruction, demonstration by example, discussion)

PHASE 15: INTRODUCTION TO LOOPS

Duration: 10 min

Orchestration: group work

Description: Show the students how they can improve their current programs with using loops. (e.g show them how to drive a rectangle using a loop). Explain the difference between for and while loops and show them how to use sensors with while loops.

Indicate which of the stated objectives are supported by this phase

Expected student constructions: -

Expected forms of student dialogue:

Teaching method: (Instruction, demonstration by example, discussion, experimentation)

PHASE 16: DRIVE UNTIL BUTTON IS PRESSED

Duration: 40 min

Orchestration: team work

Description: Student should now program their robot to drive until a button (probably mounted in front of the robot) is pressed afterwards

Indicate which of the stated objectives are supported by this phase

Expected student constructions: -

Expected forms of student dialogue: discuss in the team about their ideas

Teaching method: discussion

PHASE 17: REMOTE CONTROLLED ROBOT

Duration: 40 min

Orchestration: team work

Description: Now the student should use two buttons and program the robot to turn left or right dependent on which button is pressed. If no button is pressed robot should drive forward.

Indicate which of the stated objectives are supported by this phase

Expected student constructions: -

Expected forms of student dialogue: discuss in the team about their ideas

Teaching method: discussion

ASSESSMENT PROCEDURES

Suggestions for procedures, methods and tools that can facilitate the achievement of the teaching objectives stated at the beginning of the activity plan. (e.g. post activity tests, reflective videos etc)

Presentation of the task to the teacher

Presentation of their robot and their program to the whole class in Phase 9: Save the world:

Presentation of the robot

7.2 REVISED ACTIVITY PLANS

Exploring with Dash, and, programming Dash

AUTHORS:

JoannaPullicino, Annalise Duca, Angele Giuliano

SHORT DESCRIPTION OF THE ACTIVITY (SUMMARY)

These were workshops run with students whose average age was 10 years, and, at primary level. The robots used were Dash and Dot although the practical aspects were explored with Dash. Dash is a ready made robot and our activities focused mostly around discovering the functionalities of Dash, using its sensors, and programming Dash to move in a maze, race or move between two fixed posts.

During these sessions, run between October and December 2016, the tutors reflected with the students about teamwork and collaboration (Annex 1 to this document), creativity (held a spontaneous draw a postcard session - WORKSHEET 2) and sustaining attitudes to STEM by expanding on career prospects and brushing on gender in Science.

Furthermore, a set of questions were handed out to Learning Support Assistants (Annex 1 to this document) to hear their views about how their students could/could not engage with robots.

PS during these months, AcrossLimits was holding sessions still with Primary students - same age/school level as had been done during Spring 2016. Nonetheless, certain aspects from the ten commandments⁷ were included to upgrade the workshops accordingly.

FOCUS, SET UP AND REQUIREMENTS OF THE ACTIVITY

CURRICULUM

Select NO if the scenario is not aligned with the curriculum of your country and YES if it is. Please mention the relevant subject matter.

NO YES Subject:

CONTENT

Choose categories and give a rating of the level of emphasis on concepts from each of the following domains

Science (0-10) Technology (0-10) Business (0-10) Engineering (0-10) Arts (0-10) Mathematics (0-10)

⁷ Reference to the recommendations that resulted from the fist year evaluations.

6 8 0 0 0 3

OBJECTIVES

<i>Subject related</i>	e.g. Basic programming and loops (If then, repeat until)
<i>Technology use related</i>	e.g. Using remote control and Drag and Drop visuals
<i>Social and action related</i>	e.g. Develop collaborative skills, learn how to take turns and listen to each other, reach a compromise and decision etc.
<i>Argumentation and fostering of maker culture:</i>	e.g. Groups were encouraged to make the robot intelligent and to work at any point in time and not only once. They were encouraged to test before they tell the tutors that their work was ready.

TIME**Duration:** e.g. 8 hours split across two mornings**Schedule:** e.g. 2 sessions of 4 hours each.**MATERIALS AND ARTIFACTS**

<i>Digital artifact</i>	e.g. Drag and Drop visual
<i>Robotic artifact</i>	i.e. Not applicable
<i>Student's workbook and manual</i>	e.g. worksheets with a set of graded exercises
<i>Teacher's instruction book and manual:</i>	e.g. Powerpoint presentations

STUDENTS AND SPACE**STUDENTS (TARGET AUDIENCE)**

<i>Sex and Age:</i>	boys& girls, average 10 years of age. Classes were at times single gender; other times they were a mixed group.
<i>Prior knowledge:</i>	None of the students had prior knowledge on Dash. Around 5% of students attended short summer courses outside their school on Lego Mindstorm
<i>Nationality and cultural background</i>	around 96% Maltese. Remainder from Europe or outside European countries.
<i>Social status and social environment</i>	Mainstream public school, Private and Church schools.
<i>Special needs and abilities</i>	Autism, Down's syndrome, ADD, dyslexia, Soc. Em. Behavior Disorders. Less than 4% had problems understanding English.

SPACE INFO**Organizational and cultural context:** School gymnasium or hall.**Physical characteristics:** indoors**SOCIAL ORCHESTRATION**

POPULATION

Students: Groups of 24 to 27

Tutors: 2 occasionally 3

GROUPING:

Grouping criteria	Mixed abilities. Single or mixed gender. Each class had students with special needs.
Setting:	Students seated on paper mats on the floor, facing projector during talk time by tutors. When exploring with Dash, students were again on the floor and Dash on the mat.

INTERACTION DURING THE ACTIVITY (EMPHASIS)

Actions	e.g. Exchange ideas and dialogue
Relationships	e.g. Collaborative and competitive (during races)
Roles in the group	e.g. role exchange in the group
Support by the tutor(s)	e.g. Intervene, monitor, facilitate

LEARNING PROCEDURES

EXPECTED STUDENT ACTIVITY

Students during the activity are expected to engage in the following actions: construct, observe, communicate, create, present their work in a blog, exchange ideas, etc.

STUDENT LEARNING PROCESSES

<i>Designed Conflicts and misconceptions</i>	Not applicable
<i>Learning processes emphasized:</i>	1. observe the robot's behavior once programmed 2. communicate and discuss tasks set and decide on the way forward 3. create your experience on a 2 differently designed postcards(one postcard was not printed on both sides; the other, was printed on only one side).
<i>Expected relevance of alternative knowledge</i>	None

“HOW TO” IN THE CLASSROOM

In this section of the activity plan we describe how we expect the teaching and the learning process to evolve. We might use phases or activities for this description. The phases or activities should support the objectives stated and make use of the materials, tools and teaching and learning processes mentioned earlier in the activity plan. Next we provide an example of phase description

PHASE 1: INTRODUCTION AND EXPERIMENTATION

Duration: 2 hours

Orchestration: group work

Description: The pre-questionnaire was first carried out. This was followed by an introduction to what are robots and what isn't a robot. Advantages and disadvantages of robots in everyday life, and, how or why humans use them.

Collaboration, communication and teamwork are discussed and students are asked to reflect on what are the requisites for good teamwork (Part A, Annex 1). Examples of science careers and employments are presented to them to sustain the applicability of STEM subjects and nurture STEM in their thinking and possibly future choice of subjects. Gender is brushed upon to explain that any STEM career can be equally followed by males or females and hence to break down any stereotype images that the students might have had.

A demonstration of Dash and its functions, sensors and actions was explained to the children. The robot was then handed out and they were allowed firstly to experiment and explore freely.

Indicate which of the stated objectives are supported by this phase: Subject related, Technology use related and Social and action related

Expected student constructions: Not applicable

Expected forms of student dialogue: communication and taking turns

Teaching method: Instruction, demonstration by example, discussion with the students and experimentation by the students themselves.

PHASE 2: SEQUENTIAL PROGRAMMING, GROUP REFLECTION AND INDIVIDUAL CREATION OF A POSTCARD

Duration: 2 hours

Orchestration: Group work (groups of 2 or 3) and individual

Description: Students implement their first programs as per the puzzle sheet. No loops. The first programs moved the robot on a predefined path on the floor, made sounds, turned on/off its lights etc. They were then asked to reflect and think about the outcome of this first workshop, their impression of teamwork and collaboration and the advantages and disadvantages of working together (Annex 1, Part B and C).

Finally, students were given a postcard - printed on one side with Dash and Dot, and empty on the other side. This was a 'free to think' and 'do as you wish' exercise where students were asked to draw and/or colour and/or describe their experience of during the workshop (Annex 2). This was done individually by each student.

Indicate which of the stated objectives are supported by this phase: Subject related, Technology use related and Social and action related

Expected student constructions: Not applicable

Expected forms of student dialogue: discussion, communication, taking turns, taking decisions

Teaching method: Instruction, demonstration by example, discussion, experimentation

PHASE 3: REFLECTION AND USING LOOPS

Duration: 3 hours 30 minutes

Orchestration: group work (groups of 2 or 3)

Description: Follow on from the previous session and further reflection on teamwork/collaboration.

Students try to find a way to simplify their programs by avoiding using the same sequence of blocks many times in the same program. They use loops with their programming blocks. With teacher assistance, they recognize the usage, the conditions and the characteristics of the new programming structure and also the role of the sensors in executing a loop block.

Indicate which of the stated objectives are supported by this phase

Expected student constructions: not applicable

Expected forms of student dialogue: discussion, communication, taking turns, taking decisions

Teaching method: Instruction, demonstration by example, discussion, experimentation

PHASE 4: CREATIVITY AND EVALUATION

Duration: 30 minutes

Orchestration: Individual and class work

Description: The students are handed out a postcard, same size and shape as the one from the first session. It is different that it is empty at the back and at the front.

In addition with the activity sheets that students complete during activity phases, they also fill in an evaluation questionnaire. The teacher gets short informal open interviews from a group of students (2 - 3) who had been informed previously (during the first workshop) to share their experience.

Indicate which of the stated objectives are supported by this phase: Subject related, Technology use related and Social and action related

Expected student constructions: Not applicable

Expected forms of student dialogue: discussion, communication, creativity and thinking

Teaching method: Discussion

ASSESSMENT PROCEDURES

In this section we include the worksheets they were used during the implementation of the activity both as an instrument to support the teaching and learning process and as means to assess students

WORKSHEET 1

REFLECTIVE QUESTIONS:

Before Starting Workshop No 1: (Part A)

1. What do you think is the Golden Rule to work together? {Write all the comments on a blank paper}
2. How do you feel about group work?

Before Postcard Activity No 1: (Part B)

1. Apart from working together as a group, what have you learnt today (prompt regarding programming/technology)?
2. Do you have any previous experience working together/collaborating from other projects (prompt: this could be together at school or in other circumstances outside the school where they engage together e.g. sports, dancing sessions, scouts/guides etc.)
3. How does it feel, or, what are your impressions about teamwork?

End of Workshop No 1: (Part C)

1. Now that you have worked as a group, reflect on one thing that you would like to change to work better in a group/team. Write a sentence on this and bring it with you to the next workshop.

Before Starting Workshop No 2: (Part D)

1. Discuss on points from previous activity: What would you change to work better in a team?
2. Remind them of the Golden Rules set from Workshop 1

WORKSHEET 2

Postcard cover page

ANNEX 1

QUESTIONS TO LEARNING SUPPORT ASSISTANT

Age of student/s you assist:

What are the student/s conditions/learning difficulty etc.?

Does your student/s prefer to work alone? Why?

Could working in a group (teamwork) of 2 - 3, benefit your student/s. How?

In your opinion, do you think that the use of robots would be beneficial for your student/s in particular subjects? Yes/ No? Which subjects? Why?

Educational Robotics and Creativity Workshop

AUTHORS:

ESI CEE Team: Ivaylo Gueorguiev with the support and direct contribution of Pavel Varbanov, Petar Sharkov, Prof. Galina Momcheva, Dr. George Sharkov, Prof. Maria Nisheva, Christina Todorova and Georgi Georgiev

SHORT DESCRIPTION OF THE ACTIVITY (SUMMARY)

This workshop inspires students to think and dream about using robotics in real life. The students discuss and learn what a robot is and how robots can be used in everyday context through demonstration and creativity exercises. The activity is specially designed to develop skills as follows:

Creativity: within the workshop students learn and practice how to construct and generate innovative ideas to address real life problems using Tony Buzan mind-mapping techniques.

Digital fluency: Students discuss, learn and use the robotics key elements while generating ideas about the creative use of robotics and building and programming a real robot.

Communication: While working in team students build a robot following generic instructions. They have to clearly communicate their plans and ideas how to construct the body of the robot; to correctly connect the robot electronics and to program the robot.

Collaboration: While students in each team are changing their roles during each task, they learn how to work effectively and respectfully with others in order and to build relevantly complex robotics system.

Robotics is intriguing and fun, which is why we believe it makes a wonderful tool to engage students in Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics. We know that learning by doing makes children fall in love with creativity and robotics and helps them maintain their in-born curiosity about natural life and technology.

FOCUS, SET UP AND REQUIREMENTS OF THE ACTIVITY

CURRICULUM

NO YES Subject:

While creativity through mind-mapping could significantly contribute to the students' ability to learn⁸, structure information and memorize⁹, the workshop is not directly connected with the formal school curricula.

⁸ A study conducted at Newchurch Community Primary School in Warrington showed a variety of improvements in pupils learning after Mind Mapping was introduced. This evidence includes improved concentration, staying on task for longer periods of time, improved questioning and

CONTENT

Choose categories and give a rating of the level of emphasis on concepts from each of the following domains

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Science	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Technology	<input type="checkbox"/> Business	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Engineering	<input type="checkbox"/> Arts	<input type="checkbox"/> Mathematics
(0-10)	(0-10)	(0-10)	(0-10)	(0-10)	(0-10)
5	10	0	10	0	0

OBJECTIVES

<i>Subject related</i>	Digital fluency: Students discuss, learn and use the robotics key elements while generating ideas about the creative use of robotics and building and programming a real robot. In particular students learn and discuss key robotics elements (technology); construct a robot (technology & engineering) , develop a visual program to control the robot and to execute tasks (technology); develop the creative thinking skills needed to find different applications of robotics in other fields
<i>Technology use related</i>	Digital fluency: The technology used by the students include: Arduino microcontrollers; motor drivers; ultrasonic sensors; Scratch or Snap visual programming software.
<i>Social and action related</i>	Creativity: within the workshop students learn and practice how to construct and generate innovative ideas to address real life problems using Tony Buzan mind-mapping techniques. Collaboration: While students in each team are changing their roles during each task, they learn how to work effectively and respectfully with others in order and to build relevantly complex robotics system.
<i>Argumentation and fostering of maker culture:</i>	Communication: While working in teams, students build a robot following generic guidelines. They have to clearly communicate their plans and ideas how to construct the body of the robot to correctly connect the electronics and to program the robot. Students are made aware by tutors that they would make mistakes and have to identify and rework the corresponding parts in order to build and program the robot.

TIME

Duration: 1-2 weeks (8 hours in total)

Schedule: 2 sessions, 4 hours per session

answering during class discussions and improved independence. (
⁹ Toi, H (2009), ('Research on how Mind Map improves Memory'. Paper presented at the International Conference on Thinking, Kuala Lumpur, 22nd to 26th June 2009) shows that Mind Mapping can help children recall words more effectively than using lists, with improvements in memory of up to 32%. (Cain, M. E. (2001/2002), 'Using Mind Maps to raise standards in literacy, improve confidence and encourage positive attitudes towards learning'. Study conducted at Newchurch Community Primary School, Warrington.)

MATERIALS AND ARTIFACTS

<i>Digital artifact</i>	<p>Students work with Scratch or Snap visual programming software; Arduino IDE, python s2a_fm and pymata are used to connect the robot to a computer and to control it, along with visual interfaces.</p> <p>Additional: BirdBrain Robot Server is used if Finch robot is used for the programming or demonstration games and the Choregraphe suite is used to demonstrate the NAO humanoid robot.</p> <p>Students productions: (i) Scratch code that programmed the robot to go forwards, backwards and stop; (ii) Scratch code that programmed the robot to turn left and right around one of the chains and around the center.</p>
<i>Robotic artifact</i>	<p>Robotic Arduino-based tank developed and specifically tailored for children’s use by ESI CEE. The customized kit consists of: gearbox; chassis; chains and wheels; Arduino controller; motors driver; breadboard; wires and jump wires; ultrasonic module; Bluetooth module or USB cable; batteries and battery holders, safely designed pins suitable for children’s use to avoid soldering.</p> <p>NAO and Finch robots for demonstration are optional.</p> <p>Students productions: tank robot</p>
<i>Student’s workbook and manual</i>	<p>Visual Guide for constructing the robot; examples of Mind Maps.</p> <p>Students productions: mind-maps illustrating different creative applications of robotics.</p>
<i>Teacher’s instruction book and manual:</i>	<p>Manual How to connect and program the robot.</p> <p>Mind-map presentation.</p>
<p>Note: the workshop artifacts are uploaded and maintained at: https://github.com/esirobot/practical-robotics-workshop-tank-with-USB-cable. The particular workshop was conducted with the artifacts attached as a zip. File</p>	

STUDENTS AND SPACE

STUDENTS (TARGET AUDIENCE)

<i>Sex and Age:</i>	Boys & girls, 8-12 years;
<i>Prior knowledge:</i>	No prior knowledge required. The workshop is designed for “all students in the class”;
<i>Nationality and cultural background</i>	Bulgarian, suitable for students of diverse cultural background, capital city and other cities

<i>Social status and social environment</i>	Mainstream public schools
<i>Special needs and abilities</i>	Students with the disabilities might need additional support by qualified personnel.

SPACE INFO

Organizational and cultural context: Workshops in school, either in classroom or computer room during regular school time

Physical characteristics: indoor only

SOCIAL ORCHESTRATION

POPULATION

Students: up to 28 students

Tutors: 2-4; **School teachers:** 1

GROUPING:

Grouping criteria	No specific criteria – students or school teachers decide how to form the groups
<i>Setting:</i>	The workshop is conducted in a school classroom equipped with at least 7 computers for students and one computer for the tutors. The tables are arranged as “islands” for each team of 4 students. Enough space is left for demonstrations of robots. Large screen and white board with markers are positioned in a way to be visible by the students

INTERACTION DURING THE ACTIVITY (EMPHASIS)

Actions	Through creativity mind-mapping exercises students are motivated to think “out of frame” and to debate about the use of robots in everyday life. They exchange ideas and summarize them on a team level. While building and programming the robot students maintain dialogue about how to complete next steps. They debate and negotiate when they have doubts or have to fix any mistakes. When the robot is built and programmed students have to agree on how to play with the robot during the free time allocated for games and experiments.
<i>Relationships</i>	Tutors promote collaborative behavior within the teams and between the teams.
<i>Roles in the group</i>	The roles in the team are designer/builder – the student who builds the robot or programs the robot and team members who support the work as they directly help the builder or provide advice and check the quality of the work. The tutor requires that the students change their roles after every step of building the robot or programming it, so every student could gain experience by changing different roles within the team.
<i>Support by the tutor(s)</i>	During most of the time the tutors facilitate the activities through asking questions and maintaining debates and discussions. The tutors provide guidelines and explain definitions at the beginning of the

	<p>robotics session when the key elements of the robots are taught and at the beginning of the creativity session when the key principles of mind-mapping are explained. In both cases instructions are provided after and if needed and are based on open discussions or direct questions and are followed by demonstrations and exercises.</p> <p>The principle which the tutors convey is “let’s first think how to solve the problem before asking the tutor”. When support by the tutors is essential the tutors ask questions but do not provide direct instructions.</p>
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LEARNING PROCEDURES

EXPECTED STUDENT ACTIVITY

Students during the activity are expected to engage in the following actions: construct, observe, communicate, create, present their work as a team to the tutors, exchange ideas, etc.

STUDENT LEARNING PROCESSES

<p><i>Designed Conflicts and misconceptions</i></p>	<p>One of the creativity games includes a planned conflict, aiming to question students’ preconception of problem-solving. Students face a contradiction between the possible solution and their internal boundaries, set by themselves.</p> <div style="display: flex; align-items: center;"> <div style="margin-left: 20px;"> <p>The game consists of 9 dots. Students are asked to cross out all the dots with 4 straight lines. The solution requires that students should inevitably draw outside the dots (allegorically outside the box).</p> </div> </div> <p>In another exercise, the students have to generate ideas about the applications of a paper clip and the non-applications of a paper clip (what you can’t use a paper clip for). Students have to think within their team. Normally, students are thinking only about metal paper clips, which has not been stated in the task itself. With a little help from the tutor, they realize that the paper clip could be made of different materials, could be of different sizes, could be hollow, etc. and they realize that there are no “non-applications” of the paper clip. The goal of this game is to make children realize that their creativity is limitless and they should not base their ideas on mere practicality or preconceptions, but that it is important to train your creative thinking nevertheless.</p>
<p><i>Learning processes emphasized:</i></p>	<p>The focus of the workshop is to stimulate creativity, communication and collaboration while building a robotic kit. The students are encouraged to unleash their imagination and creativity and generate ideas about what a robot could do and present their ideas as Mind Maps.</p> <p>At the end of the workshops students have free time to play with the robots and to experiment with them.</p>
<p><i>Expected relevance of alternative knowledge</i></p>	<p>Although the robot has a predefined design, the way that the visual guide for its construction is presented, suggests that the students have</p>

	to make experiments, to discuss within their team the possible solutions and reach conclusions within the group based on communication and experimentation. The visual guide provides just pictures of different stages of the building process and no instruction on how to connect parts. The same approach is applied when programming the robot – the students have to first “discover” what the movements of the motors should be for the robot to turn left and right around the opposite chain and around the center and then program it.
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“HOW TO” IN THE CLASSROOM

Total duration of the activities will be within 8 hours. The programming session, during which the students develop code and animate the robots is used as a buffer in case other activities took less or more time for the students to complete.

Orchestration: teams of 3-4 students per table, equipped with one computer, preferably laptop with the required software installed (see [digital artifacts](#) for more information), and one robotic kit; enough free space in the center of the room for demonstrations; demo robots such as NAO; omnidirectional models, the Finch Robot or mobile telepresence robots;

Description:

MODULE 1 INTRODUCTION AND PRE-EVALUATION (40 MINUTES)

The tutors introduce themselves, explain what they do and why they came to the school. They also explain what they find fascinating about robots and what is the task for the specific day. Next they ask from the students whether they like robots, if they have had any experience with them in order to informally introduce themselves by their interest within the topic of robotics. The purpose is to become familiar with the students get to know some names and show that they are interested to learn with whom they are going to work with.

Following that, the rules and safety instructions are explained:

Rules:

- Everybody listens to the others and respects their ideas.
- No direct competition, lets cooperate and have a fun.
- Questions and strange ideas are highly encouraged.
- We are tutors but also your friends – everybody can argue with us regarding the content but not regarding the discipline.
- The parts you are given are only for construction, not for eating.
- Handle everything with attention in order to remain safe.
- Respect other team members’ opinions and let everyone work equal amount of time – we all have to learn.

Tutors try and emphasize to the students that in order to complete the task they need to collaborate with other students. The work of one person, no matter how good it is, is not going to be better than the collective work. Disagreement in a group is not a bad thing, instead it can be very productive if the group knows how to handle it.

Handling disagreement involves:

- a) asking questions that promote understanding (i.e. if a group member makes a suggestion then they others are expected to ask why this suggestion is appropriate for what the group attempts to do);
- b) asking questions that challenge suggestions (why is this a good idea?);
- c) being open to trying new ideas;
- d) respect the other's opinions and do not offend the team members if an idea is not appropriate;
- e) the group takes responsibility for all the choices made and responsibility is not an issue of the individual (the one who made a wrong suggestion);
- f) trying to identify what each member is good at and use his/her abilities to support group work;
- g) try to engage all group members in the task.

Students fill out Pre-Workshop Questionnaire and complete the Draw a Scientist evaluation activity.

MODULE 2 WHAT IS A ROBOT (40 MINUTES)

The tutors ask students “what is a robot” to generate ideas what are the key components of the robots. Once an idea is generated by the students the tutors encourage other student to comment and contribute.

After most of the interested students have a chance to contribute the tutors use one of the demo robots to conclude the key elements such as processors, drivers, actuators and sensors. They demonstrate those parts with the robotics kits and give a chance to the students to examine the parts. Analogy with nature is provoked. E.g. the tutors explain how the ultrasonic sensor works and ask students to name an animal that uses the same principles (bat; dolphin, etc.). Finally, the origin of “robot” terms is explained.

The tutors ask student if they have a robot at home and to guess different types of robots. Once a student explains his/her ideas the tutors encourage other students to comment and contribute. The tutor structures the students’ ideas to main categories such as industrial robots; home robots; humanoids; drones; toys and others. Then tutors ask student to further elaborate how their home appliances (automatic washing machine, autonomous vacuum cleaner, etc.). are similar to the robots. At the end the tutors ask students to further elaborate ho the robots will change when they grow up.

MODULE 3 CONSTRUCT A ROBOT (120 MINUTES)

The tutors remind the students about the **safety instructions**:

- Do not put the parts in your mouth – this can cause serious injury;
- Do not try to connect batteries before the instructors check the model for short circuits – the robot can cause fire.
- Be careful when using the jump wires and the pins – you can hurt yourself.

Students are once again encouraged to:

- learn from their experience and mistakes;
- have fun and play;
- discuss and respect the ideas of the others;
- shift their roles within the team after each step;
- contribute constructively to the team
- be helpful and make necessary compromises to accomplish the task
- solve the problems by themselves and to ask for tutors support only after they did their best to find a solution.

Students are introduced to the robotic kit. Tutors say a few words about the parts and what are the parts used for. They show an example of the built robot, so as to motivate the students and give them an idea towards what they are working on. Tutors give recommendations for work, including, to put the small parts in the lid of the box in which the kits come. The application of some tricky parts is demonstrated by the tutors – for instance the Patafix glue and the pins.

Students build the robot using visual guides on printed cards or slideshow on computers. Instead of employing direct instruction to introduce a concept or explain an example, constructionist methodology is applied to provide students with an example and ask them to test it and observe.

MODULE 4 ROBOT'S TOUCH (40 MINUTES)

Once the models are built the researchers demonstrate in action different type of robots such as NAO, VGo, omnidirectional robots or maybe the Finch robot and facilitate a Q&A session. When a student has a question the tutors first ask other students if they can answer the question and then elaborate based on the discussion.

During or after this and the previous module, students are asked in groups questions on what was most difficult for them during this session or what they consider to be their biggest achievement. They are asked questions about teamwork as well.

MODULE 5 LET'S IMAGINE (120 MINUTES)

The tutors ask students to discuss what is creativity and how important is it in the real life. They are using the predefined games and demos to demonstrate different aspects of creativity. Furthermore, tutors ask questions about the difference between a robot and a person ultimately reaching the conclusion that a person's brain and the person's heart is what ultimately makes a difference. Children are led to reach the consensus that the brain is that thing that helps us remember and help us make associations between different concepts. The heart on the other hand is what leads us to be imagine things and to apply our imagination to ultimately invent new things and new applications of things. Combined with the brain, they are what makes us creative.

Using games to illustrate the functions of the brain and the heart, children reach the point of creating a Mind Map on the applications of robotics in different aspects of their life. Different games include:

The intimidation of what seems impossible:

A memory game in which students try to remember 15 numbers in the order they were said by the lecturer. The game aims to show children that although a regular person is usually not able to remember this by hearing it only once, when you come to exercise your brain's creativity and memory potential every day you build the capacity to do that. This exercise also aims to show that the brain's potential is somewhat limitless and by making a conscious effort your brain's ability becomes limitless.

Thinking "out of the frame" while generating and constructing new ideas:

The game consists of 9 dots. Students are asked to cross out all the dots with only 4 straight lines. The solution requires that students should inevitably draw outside the dots (allegorically outside the box). This game aims to convey the idea that the only thing that puts borders to our capacity to solve problems is our brain itself. Listening carefully and

thinking creatively is what helps us to find solutions as much as the knowledge we already have accumulated.

The paper clip

Students have to generate ideas about the applications of a paper clip and the non-applications of a paper clip (what you can't use a paper clip for). Students have to think within their team. Normally, students are thinking only about metal paper clips, which has not been stated in the task itself. With a little help from the tutor, they realize that the paper clip could be made of different materials, could be of different sizes, could be hollow, etc. and they realize that there are no "non-applications" of the paper clip. The goal of this game is to make children realize that their creativity is limitless and they should not base their ideas on mere practicality or preconceptions, but that it is important to train your creative thinking nevertheless.

Using the mind-mapping technique to generate ideas: Students are shown as a conclusion from the games that it is easier for us to remember things and to generate new things by stimulating our brains with structure and color. Based on the conclusion from the games the tutors conclude and demonstrate the key principles of the Mind Mapping technique. Then the students construct their first simple mind map.

Create a Mind Map about the applications of robotics in everyday life: students are asked to generate ideas about use of robots and to present them as Mind Maps. They are encouraged to use drawings and colors to put emphasis on their ideas and to differentiate branches of ideas, exercising the importance of structure. Students work individually but are encouraged to share their ideas within a team and help each other to come up with ideas, exercising their collaboration skills in terms of an individual task.

MODULE 6 PROGRAM THE ROBOT (90 MINUTES)

The tutors remind the students the safety instructions and the workshop approach from Module 3. This is very important in case that the Module 3 was conducted in different day.

The tutors explain to the students the basics of programming with Scratch and how specific blocks are used to control the motors and the sensor.

Each team uses the “set up” block to switch on the robot. The teams are left to play with the ultrasonic sensor and to measure distance between the sensor and obstacles.

The rationale of this activity is to familiarize students with the functioning of the robots and the importance of sensors. This activity is performed by every group. Then the tutors demonstrate how to use events (key boards push) to create simple program – a robot moving forward. Students are left to construct and program concepts how to control the motors to move he robot backward and to stop it. Once students complete this task, they are asked to “discover” how to control the motors in order the robot to turn left and right, to go backwards (using negative numbers), to turn around the opposite chain and around the robot’s center and create a separate program for each of these activities.

Instead of employing direct instruction to introduce a concept or explain an example, following the constructionist methodology, the tutors focus on providing students with an example and ask them to test it and observe the behavior of the robot with the aim of identifying the role of specific programming concepts and structures such as logical thinking and functions. This is a teaching and learning process which makes use of the affordances of digital constructionist environments where the observation of the generated behavior (i.e. feedback) its analysis provide the grounds for the formulation of a hypothesis about how the robot works. The students are expected to generate ideas, based on the examples they are provided, how the robot can move in different directions by exercising logical and proportional thinking.

Based on the planed length of the module students might be asked also to complete other tasks such as: use sequence of commands to program the robot to go through predefined route; practice cycles to make the robot “dancing”, program the robot to turn on predefined angle or to go to predefined distance, etc.

Finally, the students are left to play with the robot or to experiment with the variety of comments that they have created or even generate new once to fit their ideas and goals. Tutors are working with groups, asking them questions to guide them towards solutions.

Some groups even find solutions to quite everyday problems, such as back pain, as illustrated below. Students stated that they created the first robot that cures back pain and were willing to showcase their robot in action. This is an example of how children’s creativity not only helps them find a new outlook on things, but also motivates and inspires them to create and maintain their interest in inventing.

MODULE 7 FINAL EVALUATION (30 MINUTES)

Evaluation session is held for students to present their achievements and evaluate their experience.

Group and/or individual interviews are conducted and students fill out Post-Workshops Questionnaires.

ASSESSMENT PROCEDURES

REGARDING DIRECT WORKSHOP OBJECTIVES

Objective	Activities to achieve the objective	Assessment (evaluation) procedures
<i>Subject related – technology, engineering, science</i>	Digital fluency: Students discuss, learn and use the robotics key elements while generating ideas about the creative use of robotics and building and programming a real robot. In particular students learn and discuss key robotics elements (technology); construct a robot (technology & engineering) , develop a visual program to control the robot and to execute tasks (technology and mathematics); develop the creative thinking skills needed to find different applications of robotics in other fields	Opinions about STEM as well as preconceptions about scientists, scientists and robotics are measured by the pre and post workshop questionnaires as well as visualized through the draw a scientist exercise. Mind Maps are used as tools to boost and visualize creativity, skills. Group interviews assess and record concepts regarding collaboration and digital fluency. Tutor reflections and observations support the assessment of this objective.

<i>Technology use related</i>	Digital fluency: The technology used by the students include: Arduino microcontrollers; motor drivers; ultrasonic sensors; Scratch or Snap visual programming software.	Photos and videos of successfully constructed and programmed robots. Attention to detail and peer review during those processes is a possible mechanism of evaluating the success of a team. Tutor reflections and observations support the assessment of this objective.
<i>Social and action related</i>	Creativity: within the workshop students learn and practice how to construct and generate innovative ideas to address real life problems using Tony Buzan mind-mapping techniques. Collaboration: While students in each team are changing their roles during each task, they learn how to work effectively and respectfully with others in order and to build relevantly complex robotics system.	Group discussions/interviews and focus group interviews are used as a tool to record students' progress, opinions and changing attitudes, along the with questionnaires. Attitudes towards team work are recorded and measured with the questionnaires as well. Tutor reflections and observations support the assessment of this objective.
<i>Argumentation and fostering of maker culture:</i>	Communication: While working in teams, students build a robot following generic guidelines. They have to clearly communicate their plans and ideas how to construct the body of the robot to correctly connect the electronics and to program the robot. Students are aware made aware by tutors that they would make mistakes and have to identify and rework the corresponding parts in order to build and program the robot.	Group discussions and interviews, alongside with photos and videos are used to record children's attitude and productions. All forms of evaluation, applied within the ER4STEM projects are further relevant for measuring this objective. Tutor reflections and observations support the assessment of this objective.

REGARDING RESEARCH QUESTIONS AND TOOL FOR ASSESSMENT

Research Question	Assessment Method or Tool
Are popular gender stereotypes about STEM held?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Draw a scientist ● Pre-Questionnaire ● Post-Questionnaire ● Interviews ● Team Reflections ● Tutor Observations & Reflections
Past experience and existing attitudes to STEM subjects and careers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Pre-questionnaire ● Interviews ● Team Reflections

<p>Past experience and existing attitudes to STEM subjects and careers</p> <p>Includes questions about the activities to help understand learners' experiences of the workshop as a whole, what participants feel they have learned and what their future intentions are</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none">● Pre-Questionnaire● Post-Questionnaire● Interviews● Team Reflections
<p>Understand the experience of participants and their reasons for particular actions</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none">● Post-Questionnaire● Interviews● Team Reflections● Tutor Observations & Reflections

An introduction to robotics (exploring planet ektonis)

Provide the title of the activity as it is mediated to students

AUTHOR:

Mavrantzas Nikolaos (Teacher – UoA)

SHORT DESCRIPTION OF THE ACTIVITY (SUMMARY)

Activity is an introduction to robotics. Students will learn how to create a robot with LEGO WeDo 2.0 kit and how to control-program it with Scratch.

FOCUS, SET UP AND REQUIREMENTS OF THE ACTIVITY

CURRICULUM

Select NO if the scenario is not aligned with the curriculum of your country and YES if it is. Please mention the relevant subject matter.

NO YES Subject: ICT.

CONTENT

Choose categories and give a rating of the level of emphasis on concepts from each of the following domains

Science Technology Business Engineering Arts Mathematics

(0-10) (0-10) (0-10) (0-10) (0-10) (0-10)

7 8 0 10 2 4

OBJECTIVES

<i>Subject related</i>	Making a LEGO robot and program it using Scratch to make it move. Understand how motors and distance sensor works.
<i>Technology use related</i>	a) LEGO WeDo 2.0. kit b) Programming in scratch environment
<i>Social and action related</i>	Develop collaborative skills, take roles within groups, solve practical problems as a team, communicate with other groups to exchange ideas and tips.
<i>Argumentation and fostering of maker culture:</i>	Practice making conjectures about how the robot will react based on the program given. <i>Programming a robot is something that a student can do and do it well. Use both Test and try and spiral methodologies. Students must follow guideline.</i>

TIME

Duration: 3 weeks**Schedule:** 3 hours per week

MATERIALS AND ARTIFACTS

<i>Digital artifact</i>	Scratch programming language
<i>Robotic artifact</i>	A LEGO, six wheel, of road, exploration vehicle with an arm free to move (adjustment by hand). It uses a motor, a multi color led and a proximity sensor.
<i>Student's workbook and manual</i>	Online, step-by-step instructions for construct a robot with lego parts and programming it with scratch. Given examples with small programs.
<i>Teacher's instruction book and manual:</i>	Teacher's notes.

STUDENTS AND SPACE

STUDENTS (TARGET AUDIENCE)

<i>Sex and Age:</i>	boys & girls, 10-11 years old
<i>Prior knowledge:</i>	basic knowledge of programming concepts with Scratch
<i>Nationality and cultural background</i>	1 pupil is from Albania and 21 from Greece
<i>Social status and social environment</i>	mainstream public school
<i>Special needs and abilities</i>	-

SPACE INFO

Organizational and cultural context: In school ICT lab.**Physical characteristics:** indoors

SOCIAL ORCHESTRATION

POPULATION

Students: 22**Tutors:** 1; **Assistants:** 0

GROUPING:

<i>Grouping criteria</i>	Random order
<i>Setting:</i>	3 or 4 students per group. Six groups total. One computer and one lego WeDo kit available for each group.

INTERACTION DURING THE ACTIVITY (EMPHASIS)

<i>Actions</i>	Exchange ideas, dialogue, negotiation
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<i>Relationships</i>	Collaborative (in group), competitive in loose form (with other groups)
<i>Roles in the group</i>	<i>Not strict</i> roles. If needed a student has to take the role of the team leader, the programmer.
<i>Support by the tutor(s)</i>	Support, intervene, monitor, facilitate, explain. Scaffolding methodology. For the last and more complicated activity there is an online page protected with code where the students can find the target program in case a team can't finish the activity in time.

LEARNING PROCEDURES

EXPECTED STUDENT ACTIVITY

Students during the activities are expected to engage in the following actions: construct, observe, communicate, create, present answers to my blog, exchange ideas.

STUDENT LEARNING PROCESSES

<i>Designed Conflicts and misconceptions</i>	<p>Students should answer some questions like:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) What is a robot; Is A drone a robot; b) Is it possible for 2 different programs to have the same result; c) What is more essential, the construction of the robot or the programming of it; <p>The first impression for making a robot is "OK, we want to do it. But it must be very difficult...". Is it;</p>
<i>Learning processes emphasized:</i>	emphasis on analyzing robot behavior in order to refine and reflect on the code that defines this behavior
<i>Expected relevance of alternative knowledge</i>	<p>Physics and especially the result of speed and moving time to the distance traveled.</p> <p>Students are expected to investigate the program of their robot vehicle to achieve the necessary accuracy.</p> <p>They'll realize that in order to work a robot in a proper way a lot of things must be arranged right: distance, speed, background, position and orientation of sensor and dimensions of other constructions.</p>

"HOW TO" IN THE CLASSROOM

In this section of the activity plan we describe how we expect the teaching and the learning process to evolve. We might use phases or activities for this description. The phases or activities should support the objectives stated and make use of the materials, tools and teaching and learning processes mentioned earlier in the activity plan. Next we provide an example of phase description

PHASE 0: PREPARATION

Duration: 1 hour

Orchestration: individual and class work

Description:

Random teams will be created and organized.

The teacher must create an account to his blog for each group. Each group should learn how to navigate to given online lessons, login, comment an activity and answer to the given questions. The 1st of the 7onlinepages can be found at: http://users.sch.gr/nikmavr/?page_id=2263

Each students is completing the “Draw a scientist” sheet.

Indicate which of the stated objectives are supported by this phase

Teaching method: (Instruction, discussion)

PHASE 1: INTRODUCTION

Duration: 3 hours

Orchestration: group work

Description: 2 Introduction videos are shown to students. Children engage in discussion about what is a robot and why or not they like robots. The LEGO WeDo kit is shown to students and they are introduced to available parts, hub, sensors, motors. They should ask some questions about robots. They must login to the online lessons platform (users.sch.gr/nikmavr) and answer the questions using comments.

Introduction to lego kit parts and their names. Simple presentation how to use the main lego parts (gears, pulleys, axles, wheels etc).

The students must connect their lego wedo hub to their PC via bluetooth. Then they should test the motor and the proximity sensor using the s2bot connection software.

An online scenario (story) is presented to the class. The teams must finish 2 missions with their robots. The robot is going to be used to planet Ektonis. At this phase the first mission begins.

Students must follow online instructions (http://users.sch.gr/nikmavr/?page_id=2281) for constructing their exploration 6 wheels vehicle.

The team must answer the questions:

- what was the most challenging part of making the robot

- What name they gave to their robot.

Expected student constructions:

They should be able to make a robot with lego parts following the step by step instructions.

They must find out how to transfer the rotation from the motor to the wheel.

Expected forms of student dialogue:

Teaching method: (Instruction, demonstration by example, discussion, experimentation)

PHASE 2: SEQUENTIAL PROGRAMMING

Duration: 2 hours

Orchestration: group work

Description: The robotic vehicle assembled by given step by step instructions at phase 1. Students implement their first program using programming blocks in a row. Now they must be able to connect the lego hub to their pc, test the connection, the motor and that Scratch can be used to control the robot. No loops or selection structures are needed.

The first program should move the robot on a straight predefined line. After a successful first program, they are asked to enhance the program and ensure that the robot returns to the initial position.

Final the robot must start from (APXH) and move forward. It must stop exactly to the 1st stop (1), wait 3 seconds and then return back to start (APXH). They must test different values for the motor power and the time that motor is on (http://users.sch.gr/nikmavr/?page_id=2294).

Final the teams must answer (online) to some questions about the 1st mission. (http://users.sch.gr/nikmavr/?page_id=2357)

Indicate which of the stated objectives are supported by this phase.

Expected student constructions

The students must test the motor axle, the pulley and the back wheels. The front wheels should be able to move over path-holes. The teams should be able to use the program blocks for changing the

motor power and configure the duration of the movement in order to send the robot forth and back to a specific point of the straight path.

Expected forms of student dialogue:

Teaching method: (Instruction, demonstration by example, discussion, experimentation)

PHASE 3: CLEARING SOME MISCONCEPTIONS

Duration: 1-2 hours

Orchestration: group work

Description: After examining the answers of the teams and the programs they made some explanations must be given and all the misconceptions must be cleared (http://users.sch.gr/nikmavr/?page_id=2473).

Create a small game using timer in order to remind students the creation and usage of variables in Scratch.

Indicate which of the stated objectives are supported by this phase

Expected student constructions

-Clear misconceptions

- Use timer and variables.

Expected forms of student dialogue:

-Teaching method: (Instruction, demonstration by example, discussion)

PHASE 4: USING SENSOR AND (WAIT...UNTIL) BLOCK

Duration: 2-3 hours

Orchestration: group work

Description: A lego arm must be added to the robot in order to support and orientate proximity

sensor (http://users.sch.gr/nikmavr/?page_id=2464).

Program robot to change the color of hubs led if something is in front of proximity sensor.

Students must program 3 repetitive actions. The robot must start from (APXH), find and stop at (A), (B) and (Γ) using the proximity sensor. At (A), (B) and (Γ) are positioned 3 generators (lego columns) that are standing near the movement path. Then the robot finishes its mission and returns back. With teacher assistance, they recognize the usage, the conditions and the characteristics of the new programming structure (wait...until) and also the role of the proximity sensors. In order to check if the program is OK they must change the position of the 3 lego columns and test that the robot stops in front all of them and then return back to start (APXH).

Indicate which of the stated objectives are supported by this phase

Expected student constructions

Add an adjustable robotic arm. Use variables and the (wait...until) block. Change the color of hub's led.

Expected forms of student dialogue:

Teaching method: (Instruction, demonstration by example, discussion, experimentation)

PHASE 4: FEEDBACK AND EVALUATION

Duration: 30 minutes

Orchestration: individual and class work

Description:

Last discussion and evaluation.

In addition with the activity sheets, that students complete during activity phases, finally they discuss in classroom the difficulties, the different solutions, the limitations that may have found in every step. They also fill in an online questionnaire (http://users.sch.gr/nikmavr/?page_id=2571).

Indicate which of the stated objectives are supported by this phase

Expected student constructions

Expected forms of student dialogue:

Teaching method: (Instruction, demonstration by example, discussion, experimentation)

ASSESSMENT PROCEDURES

All information and teams answers (as page comments) can be found online, visiting http://users.sch.gr/nikmavr/?page_id=2263. Seven online pages were published at my blog for this workshop. All data are public. No photos and videos of my students are published.

Building a robot and making it smart

AUTHOR: MARIOS XENOS (UOA)

Marios Xenos (Teacher- Researcher Uoa)

SHORT DESCRIPTION OF THE ACTIVITY (SUMMARY)

Make an autonomous system (vehicle) that disposes garbage at a dump

FOCUS, SET UP AND REQUIREMENTS OF THE ACTIVITY

CURRICULUM

Select NO if the scenario is not aligned with the curriculum of your country and YES if it is. Please mention the relevant subject matter.

NO YES Subject:

CONTENT

Choose categories and give a rating of the level of emphasis on concepts from each of the following domains

<input type="checkbox"/> Science	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Technology	<input type="checkbox"/> Business	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Engineering	<input type="checkbox"/> Arts	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Mathematics
(0-10)	(0-10)	(0-10)	(0-10)	(0-10)	(0-10)
0	10	0	7	0	3

OBJECTIVES

<i>Subject related</i>	Introducing basic robotic characteristics and build an autonomous vehicle.
<i>Technology use related</i>	Programming in LEGO programming environment, assembling LEGO sensors and motors
<i>Social and action related</i>	Taking and exchanging roles in a group. Communicate with other groups to find solutions
<i>Argumentation and fostering of maker culture:</i>	identifying an authentic problem, make assumptions, test possible solutions, choose the best solution, communicate with other “makers”.

TIME

Duration: 3 sessions

Schedule: 2 1/2 hours per session

MATERIALS AND ARTIFACTS

<i>Digital artifact</i>	Lego programming environment.
<i>Robotic artifact</i>	a simple vehicle with LEGO Mindstorms NXT
<i>Student's workbook and manual</i>	Electronic manual with step-by-step instructions for the construction, Lego electronic manual, evaluation sheet
<i>Teacher's instruction book and manual:</i>	Teacher's notes

STUDENTS AND SPACE

STUDENTS (TARGET AUDIENCE)

<i>Sex and Age:</i>	boys & girls, 13-14 years old
<i>Prior knowledge:</i>	No prior knowledge of programming concepts. One student has basic previous experience on LEGO robotics
<i>Nationality and cultural background</i>	Greece
<i>Social status and social environment</i>	mainstream public school
<i>Special needs and abilities</i>	Lego programming environment is in English. English is not native language for participants

SPACE INFO

Organizational and cultural context: after school activity at Computer Lab.

Physical characteristics: indoors

SOCIAL ORCHESTRATION

POPULATION

Students: 9 (10 started but one student abandoned for personal reasons)

Tutors: 1

GROUPING:

<i>Grouping criteria</i>	Students chose their group. Students that did not want to be filmed was grouped together
<i>Setting:</i>	Students in front of computers with one lego NXT kit available for each group

INTERACTION DURING THE ACTIVITY (EMPHASIS)

<i>Actions</i>	Exchange ideas, dialogue, negotiation, debate
<i>Relationships</i>	Collaborative, competitive
<i>Roles in the group</i>	pre-defined roles, defined by students; emergent roles

Support by the tutor(s)	Facilitate, intervene, monitor
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LEARNING PROCEDURES

EXPECTED STUDENT ACTIVITY

Students during the activity are expected to engage in the following actions: construct the robot, observe its behavior, communicate inside and outside their group, exchange ideas.

STUDENT LEARNING PROCESSES

<i>Designed Conflicts and misconceptions</i>	misconceptions about programming structures conditions, misconceptions about what a robot can “understand”, misconceptions about robot “intelligence”
<i>Learning processes emphasized:</i>	Emphasis a) on how different programming structures and different sensors affect the robot behavior b) on how a robot acting in real world in contrast with what is expected to do
<i>Expected relevance of alternative knowledge</i>	Physics laws can affect the result of robot behavior

“HOW TO” IN THE CLASSROOM

PHASE 1: INTRODUCTION, ASSEMBLAGE, EXPERIMENTATION, SEQUENTIAL PROGRAMMING

Duration: 2 1/2 hours

Orchestration: group work

Description: Children are engaged in discussion about robotics and how the creator-programmer can give the desired functionalities and characteristics to a robotic device. Students are introduced to available parts, sensors, motors. They are assembling a vehicle - robot following online instructions. They are writing their first program bringing the vehicle into life. The aim here is to get familiar with basic programming structures and in particular with “sequential programming”. They are facing two real issues: a) How the real distance on the floor is related to distance parameter on the program b) How a robot can turn 90 degrees as it cannot understand “degrees” by default. They are asked to enhance the program by repeating the movements on the floor and ensuring that the robot returns to the initial position.

Objectives:

Assembling a robotic vehicle

Program the vehicle to move on a predefined path (a rectangular path) on the floor.

Expected student constructions:

A robotic vehicle

Expected forms of student dialogue:

“Technical” vocabulary, disagreements, dialogue about assumptions

Teaching method:

Discussion, Instructions, experimentation

PHASE 2: COMMUNICATION WITH REAL WORLD (INTRODUTING SENSORS)

Duration: 2 1/2 hours

Orchestration: group work

Description: Students are asked to assemble and connect an ultrasonic sensor on the robot in a way it can detect objects in front of it. Teacher gives them a predefined program with a simple loop. The program includes one “move” block that makes robot moves until it detects an object. They have to modify the program in such a way that the robot moves until detect an obstacle at 20cm away and then it turns and moves away. In this phase, students are facing two new issues: a) Robot detects the obstacle in different distances each time it runs the program. It is needed to find the reason for this “malfunction” b) How can they measure or calculate the distance that robot covers and set the proper parameters on the program? After a working ultrasonic sensor, they are introduced with the light sensor. They have to build a more complex program that takes advantage of both sensors (ultrasonic + light). The robot should detect an obstacle, moves away and stops when it detects a black line on the floor.

Objectives: Programming a vehicle with two different sensors (ultrasonic, light)

Expected student constructions: Assemblage of ultrasonic sensor, assemblage of light sensor

Teaching method: Introduction to sensors by demonstration, discussion, experimentation

PHASE 3: BUILDING A REAL SOLUTION (ENHANCING THE “SMARTNESS” OF THE ROBOT)

Duration: 2 1/2 hours

Orchestration: group work

Description: Students build an additional frame in order to hold a ball as the vehicle moves around. Then they have to program the robot to move forward for 2 floor plates, then turn and climb on a ramp until the ball falls down on a basket at the end of the ramp. In this final phase they are asked to make their robots really “smart”; not just avoid an obstacle and stop. Now they have to use their experience to program the robot to move with precision and stop using one of the two sensors. At the end of the ramp there is a wall and a dark tape mark in order students themselves take the final decision what type of sensor should use. In this phase, students work in their groups, discuss the available solutions and decide which one should follow.

At the end of this phase students discuss in classroom the difficulties, the different solutions, the limitations that may have found in every step. They also fill in the evaluation questionnaire and teacher interviews the focus group.

Robotic Insect

AUTHORS:

Agni Pachouli (Teacher – UoA) Sofia Nikitopoulou (Teacher – Researcher UoA – developed the first version of this scenario)

SHORT DESCRIPTION OF THE ACTIVITY (SUMMARY)

Students are challenged to design/construct and program their own robotic insect using an Arduino platform, electronic components and every day affordable materials. A servo motor will generate the movement of the legs, allowing their robot to move autonomously.

FOCUS, SET UP AND REQUIREMENTS OF THE ACTIVITY

CURRICULUM

Select NO if the scenario is not aligned with the curriculum of your country and YES if it is. Please mention the relevant subject matter.

NO YES Subject: Technology, Programming

CONTENT

Choose categories and give a rating of the level of emphasis on concepts from each of the following domains

<input type="checkbox"/> Science	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Technology	<input type="checkbox"/> Business	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Engineering	<input type="checkbox"/> Arts	<input type="checkbox"/> Mathematics
(0-10)	(0-10)	(0-10)	(0-10)	(0-10)	(0-10)
0	10	0	10	0	0

OBJECTIVES

<i>Subject related</i>	Study the angle and position of all materials (servo motors, circuits, sensors), as well as the construction of the legs in order for the robotic insect to be autonomous and move correctly
<i>Technology use related</i>	Design with Arduino Uno board, a mini breadboard, some electronic parts (resistances, led, sonar sensor, piezo, servo motor) and programming with open-source Arduino Software (IDE)
<i>Social and action related</i>	Improve collaborative skills, exchange ideas, take roles within groups
<i>Argumentation and fostering of maker culture:</i>	identifying an authentic problem, make assumptions, test possible solutions, choose the best solution

TIME

Duration: 3 weeks (Γ1) – 2 weeks (Γ3)

Schedule: 2 hours per week (Γ1) – 3 hours per week (Γ3)

MATERIALS AND ARTIFACTS

<i>Digital artifact</i>	Programming with open-source Arduino Software (IDE)
<i>Robotic artifact</i>	Arduino Uno microcontroller board – form: a moving robotic insect
<i>Student's workbook and manual</i>	Activity sheet with instructions for the electronic parts (piezo and servo motor), initial code for modification (programming part), evaluation sheets
<i>Teacher's instruction book and manual:</i>	teacher's notes in total

STUDENTS AND SPACE

STUDENTS (TARGET AUDIENCE)

<i>Sex and Age:</i>	boys & girls, 14-15 years old
<i>Prior knowledge:</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - little knowledge of Arduino and electronic parts (resistances, led). Before this project students were involved in activities in order to get familiar with electronic circuits and Arduino board - Good knowledge of programming concepts (like if-then concepts) in Scratch environment
<i>Nationality and cultural background</i>	27 students from Greece
<i>Social status and social environment</i>	mainstream public school
<i>Special needs and abilities</i>	All students have good English knowledge

SPACE INFO

Organizational and cultural context: in school during computer science and technology lessons (computer Lab)

Physical characteristics: indoors

SOCIAL ORCHESTRATION

POPULATION

Students: 27

Tutors: 1; **Assistants:** 0

GROUPING:

<i>Grouping criteria</i>	mixed ability, mixed gender where possible
<i>Setting:</i>	students in a computer lab, one Arduino Uno microcontroller, electronic parts and a desktop computer available for each group. Each group is seated in their own workbench.

INTERACTION DURING THE ACTIVITY (EMPHASIS)

Actions	Exchange ideas, dialogue, negotiation, debate
Relationships	Collaborative, competitive
Roles in the group	emergent roles
Support by the tutor(s)	Intervene, facilitate, support

LEARNING PROCEDURES

EXPECTED STUDENT ACTIVITY

Students during the activity are expected to engage in the following actions: design, construct, observe, program, communicate, exchange ideas, present their work in the classroom and on an educational social media platform (Edmodo).

STUDENT LEARNING PROCESSES

<i>Designed Conflicts and misconceptions</i>	
<i>Learning processes emphasized:</i>	emphasis on studying robot behaviour as a result of its design and the executed program (i.e. use behaviour as feedback on programming and robot design)
<i>Expected relevance of alternative knowledge</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - students are expected to investigate the structure of an insect's body (biology) in order to construct their robot - emphasis on mathematical thinking, the construction of the insect's legs depends on a specific geometry pattern in order for the zoomorphic robot to move

"HOW TO" IN THE CLASSROOM

In this section of the activity plan we describe how we expect the teaching and the learning process to evolve. We might use phases or activities for this description. The phases or activities should support the objectives stated and make use of the materials, tools and teaching and learning processes mentioned earlier in the activity plan. Next we provide an example of phase description

PHASE 1: INTRODUCTION AND EXPERIMENTATION WITH SENSORS

Duration: 90 minutes (10 minutes demonstration, 80 minutes construction)

Orchestration: discussion, demonstration, group work, assembly, experimentation

Description: At the beginning of the workshop, the teacher presents the overall aim, the objectives of the workshop, the training methodology and the expected training results. A brief demonstration of the electronic parts (resistance, led), sensors (piezo, sonar) and available materials (such as paperclips, wooden sticks, rope, glue etc) is being held. Finally, students watch a short video presenting an already-made robotic insect. Before students start acting, groups are asked to choose a name for their team.

Teams start implementing the worksheet activities, which support their involvement equally in programming, engineering and electronics. First, they design the electronic circuit that detects obstacles with the help of the sonar sensor. Then, they add the piezo which generates tones

according to the detected distance. Students are prompt to tinker with the programming, since the initial code is provided (file `sonar_ionidios.ino`), but modifications are needed.

PHASE 2: CONSTRUCTING A ROBOTIC INSECT

Duration: 90 minutes

Orchestration: group work

Description: Students get involved in constructing a robotic insect by using every day and affordable materials (paperclips, wooden sticks, rope, glue etc). No specific pattern or instructions are provided, instead students use their imagination and creativity to choose and combine the materials. During the construction process, students exchange ideas, disagree, negotiate, experiment, try different ideas, collaborate and improve their construction. At the end of the session, each team will have constructed a unique robotic insect.

PHASE 3: MAKING THE ROBOTIC INSECT MOVE

Duration: 75 minutes

Orchestration: group work

Description: It's time to make the robotic insect move. Student get familiar with the servo motor, as they have to figure out how it is connected on the Arduino board and how to program it. Students don't start the programming of the servo motor from scratch; an initial code is provided (file `servo_motion.ino`), but modifications are needed. They experiment with different values and settings and observe the results on the servo's motion.

Once they understand the programming part, they are challenged to find a proper position for the servo motor, as well for the legs, in order to make a functional autonomous robotic insect. Many questions arise at this point, especially regarding the shape of the legs, the position of the robotic legs and the position of the servo motor on the already-made robotic skeleton. When they manage to complete the construction, students focus on programming and debugging the code in order to achieve their goal and make their robotic insect move.

PHASE 4: FEEDBACK AND EVALUATION

Duration: 15 minutes

Orchestration: group work

Description: In addition to the activity sheets that students complete during activity phases, the groups finally fill in an evaluation questionnaire referring to the difficulties, the different solutions, the limitations that may have come up with in every step. The teacher interviews members of the case study groups, who share their experience and suggest improvements.

ASSESSMENT PROCEDURES

FORMATIVE ASSESSMENT

- Pupil voice activities (Interviews with students, Questionnaire, videos)
- Observation notes by the teacher

Robots in a maze

AUTHOR:

Vasileios Spahos (UoA- Teacher)

SHORT DESCRIPTION OF THE ACTIVITY (SUMMARY)

Design and program robots to solve the maze problem.

FOCUS, SET UP AND REQUIREMENTS OF THE ACTIVITY

CURRICULUM

Select NO if the scenario is not aligned with the curriculum of your country and YES if it is. Please mention the relevant subject matter.

NO YES Subject: Project

CONTENT

Choose categories and give a rating of the level of emphasis on concepts from each of the following domains

<input type="checkbox"/> Science	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Technology	<input type="checkbox"/> Business	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Engineering	<input type="checkbox"/> Arts	<input type="checkbox"/> Mathematics
(0-10)	(0-10)	(0-10)	(0-10)	(0-10)	(0-10)
0	10	0	6	0	0

OBJECTIVES

<i>Subject related</i>	Study the construction of a robot and the sensors that it should have in order to solve the maze problem and be able to find the solution to every maze. Also get in touch with programming structures
<i>Technology use related</i>	Programming in LEGO EV3 programming environment
<i>Social and action related</i>	Develop collaborative skills, take roles within groups, communicate with other groups to exchange ideas and tips, advice
<i>Argumentation and fostering of maker culture:</i>	Students make some assumptions about how the robot will react to the environment using sensors based on the program given, design and test possible solutions, choose the best solution, trying to optimize their solution, communicate with other "makers".

TIME

Duration: e.g. 2 weeks

Schedule: e.g. 4 hours per week

MATERIALS AND ARTIFACTS

<i>Digital artifact</i>	Programming language (Lego EV3 programming environment), visual interface, robot simulation
<i>Robotic artifact</i>	The technology and the robot form a vehicle
<i>Student's workbook and manual</i>	Manual with a possible design for robot vehicle, student sheet for programming
<i>Teacher's instruction book and manual:</i>	Teacher's notes with the three stages of construction

STUDENTS AND SPACE

STUDENTS (TARGET AUDIENCE)

<i>Sex and Age:</i>	boys & girls, 15-16 years old
<i>Prior knowledge:</i>	little if any knowledge of EV3 with little knowledge of programming concepts
<i>Nationality and cultural background</i>	17 pupils are from Greece
<i>Social status and social environment</i>	mainstream public school
<i>Special needs and abilities</i>	Lego programming environment is in English. English is not native language for participants but most of students know English

SPACE INFO

Organizational and cultural context: In School at the Robotics Laboratory; During project time in school.

Physical characteristics: indoors/outdoors

SOCIAL ORCHESTRATION

POPULATION

Students: 17

Tutors: 1

GROUPING:

<i>Grouping criteria</i>	mixed ability, mixed gender
<i>Setting:</i>	students in front of computers with one lego EV3 kit available for each group students have the ability to make some experiments on a real maze.

INTERACTION DURING THE ACTIVITY (EMPHASIS)

<i>Actions</i>	Exchange ideas, dialogue, negotiation, debate
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<i>Relationships</i>	Collaborative, competitive
<i>Roles in the group</i>	Role exchange in the group
<i>Support by the tutor(s)</i>	Intervene, monitor, facilitate

LEARNING PROCEDURES

EXPECTED STUDENT ACTIVITY

Students during the activity are expected to engage in the following actions: construct, observe, communicate, create, present their work in a blog, exchange ideas, find a solution to a problem, take part in a small competition.

STUDENT LEARNING PROCESSES

<i>Designed Conflicts and misconceptions</i>	Do the activity designers wish to bring students in conflict with mistaken conceptions documented in educational research or their teaching practice?
<i>Learning processes emphasized:</i>	emphasis on analyzing robot behavior in order to refine and reflect on the code that defines this behavior
<i>Expected relevance of alternative knowledge</i>	students are expected to investigate the structure of a vehicle and the basic parts in order to construct their robot and make it more stable and quick.

“HOW TO” IN THE CLASSROOM

In this section of the activity plan we describe how we expect the teaching and the learning process to evolve. We might use phases or activities for this description. The phases or activities should support the objectives stated and make use of the materials, tools and teaching and learning processes mentioned earlier in the activity plan. Next we provide an example of phase description

PHASE 1: INTRODUCTION AND EXPERIMENTATION

Duration: 3 hours

Orchestration: group work

Description: Children are engaged in discussion about robotic behaviors and how the creator-programmer can give the desired functionalities and characteristics to a robotic device. Students are introduced to available parts, sensors, motors. They experiment with different values and settings and observe the results. They also analyze the problem and come up with the necessary equipment that a robot should have (sensors) make a list and start constructing their robots.

Indicate which of the stated objectives are supported by this phase

Expected student constructions : One robotic vehicle per group

Expected forms of student dialogue:

Teaching method: Instruction, demonstration by example, discussion, experimentation

PHASE 2: PROBLEM SOLVING

Duration: 2 hours

Orchestration: group work

Description After finishing their robots the groups are assigned to program their robots and their behavior. In order to find a way to solve the problem we use a student as a volunteer and other students try to lead him to the exit of the class by using commands. They use the Programming environment of Lego EV3, using sequential programming, loops, selection. At the same time, they test their robot and its behavior , trying to solve possible problems they face.

Indicate which of the stated objectives are supported by this phase

Expected student constructions :

Expected forms of student dialogue:

Teaching method: Instruction, demonstration by example, discussion, experimentation

PHASE 3: CODE OPTIMIZATION AND COMPETITION

Duration: 2 hours

Orchestration: group work

Description: Students try to find a way to optimize their program by avoiding using the same sequence of blocks many times in the same program and they are trying to make their robot faster in order to take part in a small competition. Also they are trying to make their robots more attractive.

Expected student constructions

Expected forms of student dialogue:

Teaching method: Instruction, demonstration by example, discussion, experimentation

PHASE 4: FEEDBACK AND EVALUATION

Duration: 30 minutes

Orchestration: individual and class work

Description: In addition with the activity sheets that students complete during activity phases, finally they discuss in classroom the difficulties, the different solutions, the limitations that may have found in every step. They also fill in an evaluation questionnaire and teacher gets short informal open interviews from students that want to share their experience.

Indicate which of the stated objectives are supported by this phase

Expected student constructions

Expected forms of student dialogue:

Teaching method: (Instruction, demonstration by example, discussion, experimentation)

8 GLOSSARY / ABBREVIATIONS

EC	European Commission
ER	Educational Robotics
ER4STEM	Educational Robotics for Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics
ERW	Educational Robotics Workshop
Implementation Team	All members of the team that implements the workshop including but not limited to facilitators, teachers, researchers, evaluators and others.
REA	Research Executive Agency
STE(A)M	Science, Technology, Engineering, Art, and Mathematics
STEM	Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics

9 BIBLIOGRAPHY=

Bers, M. U. (2008). *Blocks to robots: learning with technology in the early childhood classroom*. New York: Teachers College Press.

Fischer, G. (2009). End-user development and meta-design: Foundations for cultures of participation. In V. Pipek, M. B. Rossen, B. deRuyter, & V. Wulf (Eds.), *End-User Development* (pp. 3–14). Heidelberg: Springer-Verlag.

Healy, L., & Kynigos, C. (2010). Charting the microworld territory over time: design and construction in mathematics education. *ZDM Mathematics Education*, 42, 63–76.

Papert, S. (1980). *Mindstorms: Children, computers, and powerful ideas*. Basic Books, Inc.

Papert, S. (2000). What's the big idea? Towards a pedagogy of idea power. *IBM Systems Journal*, 39(3-4), 720–729.

Vergnaud, G. (2009). The Theory of Conceptual Fields. *Human Development*, 52(2), 83–94.
<http://doi.org/10.1159/000202727>

Yiannoutsou, N., Nikitopoulou, S., Kynigos, C., Gueorguiev, I., & Fernandez, J. A. (2016). Activity Plan Template: a mediating tool for supporting learning design with robotics. In *Robotics in Education*. Vienna-Austria: Springer.

